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Authors	:	Shamal Faily, Ivan Flechais, Andrea Atzeni, Cesare Cameroni, Hans Myrhaug, Habib Ayse Goker, Andre Paul, Robert Kleinfeld, Stephan Steglich, Nick Allott, Sven Lachmund, Dieter Blomme, Heiko Desruelle

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Abstract

This document describes the output of deliverable 2.8: Updates to user expectations of privacy and security. As a continuation of deliverable 2.7, several significant contributions are made.

First, the key issues from related work packages that this deliverable needs to address are introduced, together with a state of the art review on risk analysis, misuse cases and HCI-Security and design.

Second, based on this review, 12 misuse cases are presented. Each misuse case contextualises a risk, which is itself constructed from threats and vulnerabilities that are specific to particular webinos environments; these environments are modelled using UML-based asset diagrams and are based on key webinos architectural and application environments. For each misuse case, we proposed recommendations for dealing with each related risk.

Third, we describe qualitative research carried out to identify factors that impact the elicitation, categorisation, and grouping of security and privacy policy concepts in multiple contexts. This research involved carrying out focus groups where recruited participants carried out an affinity diagramming exercise corresponding to the development of a context-sensitive security policy. The participants were recruited based on their similarity to one of three selected personas elicited in deliverable 2.7. In total, 3 focus groups of 3-4 participants were carried out for each of the three selected persona. A report was written for each focus group and, based on a qualitative data analysis of each report, summarised results and recommendations for webinos were proposed.

Fourth, based on issues identified during both the focus groups and other webinos activities, personal and design issues likely to impact the usability of webinos for selected personas were identified. These issues were illustrated with misusability cases describing how the webinos design leads to usability issues inadvertently causing security problems. Based on 5 selected personas, 5 misusability cases were identified. Based on the issues and misusability cases, recommendations are made for tackling the problems identified.

The results presented in this deliverable 2.8 are useful for the designers and developers in WP 3.5, 4, and 5 as input to security testing activities, guidance for mitigating likely webinos security problems, and recommendations for developing interfaces for context-sensitive security policy management tools.

Keyword list

Security, privacy, misuse case, misusability case, focus group, affinity diagramming

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1 Introduction

1.1. Motivation

The motivation for Deliverable 2.7 was to glean an expectation of what prospective end-users of webinos might expect from a security and privacy perspective. The approach used to glean this expectation involved using the analysis from Deliverables 2.1 and 2.2 as a source of data upon which a webinos context of use description could be devised.

Deliverable 2.7 was not, however, a complete exposition of user expectations for webinos. While these provided food-for-thought for work in WP 3, the exercise of designing a software architecture itself continues to raise more questions about the end-users and their security and privacy expectations when using applications powered by webinos. While the personas in Deliverable 2.7 can be used as an initial authority for understanding the expectations of the different user communities, some of these questions require further investigation as research topics in their own right.

Although Deliverable 2.7 identified possible attackers and attack vectors, webinos was largely treated as a black-box. In WP 3, webinos became something that could be treated as a white box, and the webinos attack surface became visible for the first time. Consequently, Deliverables 3.1, 3.2, and 3.5 provides the basis for exploring how security and privacy values of webinos components vary in different contexts and, based on this, how attackers might exploit both the architecture and our expectations for their own ends.

Therefore, the first objective of Deliverable 2.8 is to continue and, where necessary, revise the work carried out in Deliverable 2.7 in light of work carried out in WP 3. The second objective was to conduct research into particular webinos issues which a security analysis of webinos data and literature review of related work would provide answers for.

1.2. Key Issues from other work-packages

Other work packages and their deliverable provide important information for WP 2.8. This information is manifold. The deliverables from WP 3 provide details on the webinos architecture which includes security-related components. Deliverable 2.7 contributes the Personas, Attacker Personas and Environment Models. All this is useful for the analysis being carried out as part of D2.8. Relations between D2.8 and other work packages are summarised in the remainder of this section.

1.2.1. WP 2.7

In WP 2.7, analyses have been taken on which WP 2.8 builds upon.

- Personas and Attacker Personas help us understanding misbehaviour in webinos. Users may accidentally do something risky because of lack of knowledge or carelessness. Attackers may consider some components of webinos as particularly interesting for attacks. This is valuable input for identifying intentional and unintentional exploitation of webinos.
- The Environment Models were useful for alluding to relevant components of the webinos architecture at an early stage. Because the webinos architecture was at a more advanced stage during the preparation of D2.8 then more accurate models of architecturally significant assets can now be derived.
- The behaviour of the Personas and Attacker Personas was useful for highlighting possible areas for analysis in D3.1, in addition to possible attacks that could inform D3.5. Given the better knowledge of the webinos architecture now available then, as indicated earlier in this section, a more accurate analysis of possible risks is now possible.

1.2.2. WP 3.1

The work carried out as part of D3.1 raised several implications for the user expectations for security and privacy. For example:

- User authentication is performed by the device. The device manufacturer is responsible for proper implementation and for choosing strong authentication mechanisms. An attacker can try to spread devices on the market with weak authentication.
- Attackers are likely to be interested in breaking authentication (user and or device authentication), as this opens-up unauthorised access to a vast range of assets. Thus authentication needs to be strong.
- The Personal Zone Hub (PZH) and the Personal Zone Proxy (PZP) are key components of the entire webinos architecture. Extra care is required to make sure that obvious attack vectors are not present.
- Discovery of devices, services and applications, and handling of context in webinos may disclose personal information about users in unintended ways. Moreover, we lack an

understanding of how information architecture for user interfaces that manage and reason about context.

- It is unclear in what ways developers might use the webinos APIs, and the more general idea of providing API access to web applications is still in its infancy.

Understanding how best webinos should respond to these implications should guide the analysis activities in D2.8.

1.2.3. **WP 3.5**

WP 3.5

- covers further architectural components which are critical, such as session establishment, policy decision/enforcement and attestation;
- teaches security guidelines for the developer which are to be considered for design and implementation in order to prevent attacks.

webinos' architecture mitigates some common security problems of today's Internet due to its security-focused design. Since it introduces new components, it potentially opens-up new attack vectors. It is the project's goal to mitigate these as well. The analyses carried out in WP 2.8 complements the work in WP 3.5 by identifying additional attack vectors and finding mitigation strategies which feed into the specifications of WP3.

2 Related Work

Much of this section has been adapted from (FAIT2011), and is included here with the permission of the author.

2.1. Risk Analysis

Security is about the protection of *assets* (GOLL2006); these need to be both identified and appraised, and are defined as anything that has value to an organisation (ISO27001). Valuation of assets is particularly difficult as this needs to be expressed in terms of organisation value or, more directly, as the cost paid by the organisation should the asset be compromised. Gollman (GOLL2006) claims the identification of assets is comparatively easier than its valuation, but it is unwise to trivialise the exercise of identifying *information* assets. Information can be defined as data interpreted in some meaningful context (BEYN2002), and as knowledge communicated concerning some particular feat, subject, or event (LIBA1990). In both cases, the significance and value of information depends on the context where it is found.

Because protecting an organisation from all possible threats is untenable, security requirements are often derived by assessing their *risks* (ISO27002). *Risk* is evocative of some form of threat, danger or hazard. A multidisciplinary study commissioned by the Royal Society (LOND1983) identified two forms of risk: objective risk and perceived risk. Objective risk defines risk as the probability of harm occurring; this harm can be stated scientifically and is capable of measurement. Perceived risk relates to the subjective assumptions people hold about future events. Given the interpretive nature of information, it is this latter definition which holds sway in the Information Security literature. Closely associated with the definition of *Risk* are the concepts of *Threat* and *Vulnerability*. ISO/IEC 27002 (ISO27002) defines a threat as a potential cause of an unwanted incident, and a vulnerability as a weakness of an asset or group of assets that can be exploited by one or more threats.

2.2. Misuse Cases

Sindre and Opdahl (SIOP2005) have proposed extending the notion of use cases to support unwanted system behaviour. Such behaviour can be encapsulated by a *Misuse Case*: a sequence of actions, including variants, that a system or other entity can perform, interacting with misusers of the entity, and causing harm to stakeholders if the sequence is allowed to complete. To support the analysis of the described threat, Sindre and Opdahl propose adopting a detailed template similar to that prescribed by (COCK2001).

The simplest way of creating misuse cases is informed brainstorming, guided by a security expert asking questions about the system likely to have weaknesses; this activity mirrors the way attackers might think (HOMA2004).

Misuse cases extend the use case diagram notation in the following ways. First, the actor node is represented as a stick figure with a black, rather than white, head. Second, additional relations between use cases and misuse cases are added, specifically a misuse case can <<threaten>> a use case, although a use case describing the application of a mitigating countermeasure may <<mitigate>> a misuse case. Røstad (ROST2006) proposed augmenting this notation further by adding an actor type to represent insider attackers, and a grey — rather than black — ellipse to represent vulnerabilities; the black ellipses are then used to represent threats carried out by either inside or outside attackers. An additional <<exploit>> relation is also proposed between threat and vulnerability ellipses to indicate that a threat exploits a particular vulnerability.

A similar negative extension to use cases is the Abuse Case: a specification of a type of complete interaction between a system and one or more actors, where the interaction results are harmful to the system, actors, or other stakeholders (MCFO1999). Like misuse cases, abuse cases are scenario-based and can be graphically represented using use case diagrams. The distinction between misuse cases and abuse cases is very subtle. Sindre and Opdahl claim that the textual templates used by both are different, abuse cases deal with families of misuse rather than specific threats, and abuse cases are not modelled on the same use case diagram as use cases. Because of this subtlety, we follow the example set by much of the literature and consider both as synonymous.

2.3. HCI-Security and design

In their seminal paper on Information Security, Saltzer and Schroeder (SASC1975) espouse several design principles for protection mechanisms. One of these is the principle of Psychological Acceptability, which states: *The interface to the protection mechanism should be designed for ease of use, so users routinely and automatically apply the mechanism correctly.* In the past decade or so, there has been an enormous amount of research in the area of HCI-Sec; seminal work in this area has looked at the usability of password policies (ADSA1999) and security controls (WHIT1999).

The HCI-Sec community has considered the challenge of designing usable security from two different standpoints. The first of these is characterised by the application of usable security design principles, the most prominent example of which are Yee's guidelines for and strategies for secure interaction (YEE2005). These guidelines are written as principles a designer should consider when making decisions about secure interface design; examples of these guidelines

include: *Match the most comfortable way to do tasks with the least granting of authority, and Indicate clearly the consequences of decisions that the user is expected to make.* While such design principles are well meaning, they are not a panacea for designing usable security. For example, one of Yee's Communication principles states that a designer should "Present objects and actions using distinguishable, truthful appearances," yet nothing is said about how this might be done. However, such guidelines suggest that security and usability can be harmonious, and such guidelines are designed to appeal to the mental models of users.

The second standpoint is characterised by Sasse et al's work on applying HCI design approaches to the design of security mechanisms (SABR2001), and Zurko and Simon's work on user-centered security (ZUR1996). Based on the empirical findings from several studies about password usage, Sasse et al. found that framing the design of security controls from a technology, user, goal, task, and context perspective can lead to useful insights. For example, considering security as an enabling task that needs to be completed before a main task helps explain why users choose to circumvent controls which get in the ways of their work. User-centered security refers to "security models, mechanisms, systems, and software that have usability as a primary motivation or goal". Zurko and Simon claim that secure systems have, traditionally, been indifferent to the needs of users — irrespective of whether these are end-users, developers or administrators. Like Yee, Zurko and Simon argue for security models conducive to the mental models of different types of users, but they also propose synthesising security design techniques with established design techniques from HCI.

Sasse et al's and Zurko and Simon's work inspired, and continues to inspire, much of the current research in HCI-Sec. Surprisingly, however, the bulk of work in this community focuses on studying the usability of specific security controls rather than activities associated with designing systems that are usable and secure. In particular, a recent survey by Birge (BIRG2009) found that many HCI-Sec papers are divided into studies about usability testing on security controls, mitigating security controls, conceptual investigations about terms such as "trust" and "privacy", experience studies about user attitudes, and models & guidelines demonstrating trusted interactions and trusted user interfaces. Birge also notes that much of this research focuses on the needs of the end-user rather than the needs of the designer. One particular need that a designer has, which webinos as a project also faces, is how to inform the design of webinos security with the expectations of its prospective users *during* the design process, rather than before or after it.

3 Misuse Case Analysis

3.1. Approach

As described in the related work section, the classic means of creating misuse cases is informed brainstorming, guided by a security expert asking questions where a system is likely to have weaknesses; this activity mirrors the way attackers might think (HOMA2004). Unfortunately, there are two problems with this approach.

First, Sindre & Opdahl identified possible scalability issues when dealing with a large number of threats. They argue that the underlying problem may relate to the process used to elicit security requirements and the need for better guidelines for prioritising requirements, rather than with misuse cases per se. However, what remains unclear are the implications to usability or privacy of a countermeasure use case mitigating a misuse case, and what new vulnerabilities may be introduced as a result. There is, therefore, a need to justify the motivations for a misuse case.

Second, brainstorming may lead to imaginative ideas, but brainstorming still needs to be grounded in their knowledge of the domain of discussion. Unfortunately, participants may not have the background knowledge necessary to serendipitously identify possible attackers and, as a corollary, threats they might carry out. Therefore, in lieu of empirical data, participants may fall foul of stereotypes about who likely attackers are, and what capabilities they have. Attempting to mitigate against attacks precipitated by a super-hackers may lead to design decisions which are over-commensurate to the risks the system does actually face.

The approach taken by webinos for misuse case development deals with both each of these problems.

We deal with the first problem by using misuse cases for a different purpose; rather than using them to elicit threats, we instead use them to validate risks. We define risks as single events where an attacker carries out a threat and, in the process of doing so, exploits an identified vulnerability, where both the threat and vulnerability are in the same environment or environments. Misuse cases validate risks because they are scenarios describing how an attacker realises a risk within a given environment. By narrating a risk's impact using a scenario, misuse cases not only place the risk in a human context, it also sanity checks the analysis contributing to the definition of a risk, justifying its threat and vulnerability, the related likelihood and severity values, and the asset values.

The second problem is partially solved by dealing with the first, particularly because the webinos context of use description also contains grounded information about possible attackers.

3.1.1. Select environments and security values

The first stage involved selecting environments for bounding the misuse case analysis exercise. These environment were selected by the WP 2.8 partners based on their significance. These environments were broken down into architectural and application environments. Architectural environments are a static view of a particular facet of the webinos architecture; collectively, the architectural environments model the key architectural components of webinos. Application environments are static views of the concepts associated with a particular application exemplar. Given the potential applications of webinos, defining an exhaustive list of application environments would have been unsustainable. Consequently, the WP 2.8 partners selected three specific application exemplars of particular interest.

3.1.2. Define and model assets

The second stage involves defining assets for different environments of interest. Assets are defined based on their significance in the webinos architecture, or in applications that rely on it.

In addition to its name, each asset contains the following attributes:

Attribute name	description
Type	The type of asset; this is one of Software, Hardware, and Information
Description	A short description of the asset.
Significance	The significance of the asset that motivates its inclusion as part of this analysis.
Environments	The list of environments this asset is present in.

For each environment, an *asset model* was defined to describe how assets are associated with each other within an environment. Within each asset model, 8 additional attributes were added to each asset to reflect their security and privacy values. These attributes were:

- Security attributes
 - Confidentiality
 - Integrity
 - Availability
 - Accountability
- Privacy attributes
 - Anonymity

- Pseudonymity
- Unlinkability
- Unobservability

Each value (None, Low, Medium, or High) was discussed and agreed by all WP 2.8 partners and, in each environment model, a table describes the rationale for each asset value. Because of the subjective nature of both the attributes and the values, guidelines for what constitute each value for each attribute are defined for each environment. In some environments, certain security and privacy values may also be at tension. Therefore, for each environment, a value tensions table is defined which indicates where tensions occur and, for each tension, what the reason for the tension might be.

3.1.3. Define Vulnerabilities

Vulnerabilities are system weaknesses, and these may be elicited via several possible sources. These might be based on existing taxonomies for vulnerabilities, such as those found in (OWASP), or from knowledge about how assets might be intrinsically vulnerable when situated in certain environments. Vulnerabilities may also be arise by considering the tensions between security and privacy asset values when assets are associated; thinking about how these might be exploited might lead to possible vulnerabilities requiring these exploits.

In addition to its name, each vulnerability contains the following attributes:

Attribute name	description
Type	The type of vulnerability. This should be one of the OWASP vulnerability types (OWASP).
Description	A short description of the vulnerability
Environmental attributes	Every environment should contain a section stating the list of the assets exposed in each environment, and the severity of the vulnerability. The severity value should be one of the following: Negligible, Marginal, Critical, Catastrophic.

The table below describes how each severity value should be interpreted for each environment.

Severity	Interpretation
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Negligible	This vulnerability has no impact in the current environment.
Marginal	Exploitation of this vulnerability affects people or activities within this environment if not mitigated.
Critical	Exploitation of this vulnerability has a significant impact on people or activities within this environment, and may influence activities within other environments.
Catastrophic	Exploitation of this vulnerability has a catastrophic impact on people and activities in all environments.

3.1.4. Define Threats

Threats are a potential cause of an unwanted incident, which may result in harm to a system. Like vulnerabilities, these may be based on existing taxonomies for threats, but these may also be based on attack trees identified in the context of use description threat model. Like vulnerabilities, threats may also be identified based on conflicting security and privacy values when assets are associated. Additionally, these might also arise based on tensions between threat and asset values.

Because this work-package runs largely in conjunction with WP 2.8 then app stores are not included in this analysis, nor are any attacks included that pre-suppose particular detailed design issues that have yet to be agreed.

In addition to its name, each threat contains the following attributes:

Attribute name	description
Type	The type of threat. This should be one of the OWASP attack types (OWASP).
Method	A brief description of the method used by an attacker to carry out this threat. These attackers correspond with the attacker personas described in the context of use description threat model.
Environmental attributes	Every environment should contain a section stating the attacker (or attackers) that might carry out the threat, the list of the assets threatened in each environment, and the likelihood of the threat. In addition to this, any specific asset values held by the attacker should be stated in a table within this section.

The threat likelihood value should correspond to one of the values in the table below.

Likelihood	Interpretation
Incredible	The threat is very unlikely to occur without significant changes to the environment.
Improbable	The threat is unlikely to occur without notable changes to the environment.
Remote	This threat may occur on a small number of occasions in the lifetime of the system based on the attributes of the threat and the environment.
Occasional	Attacks corresponding with this threat are likely to occur on a weekly or monthly basis based on the attributes of the threat and the environment.
Probable	Attacks corresponding with this threat are likely to occur once or twice daily in this environment.
Frequent	Attacks corresponding with this threat take place on an ongoing basis in this environment.

3.1.5. Define Risks and Model Misuse Cases

Risks are single events where an attacker carries out a threat and, in the process of doing so, exploits a vulnerability, where both the threat and vulnerability are in the same environment or environments.

Unlike WP 3.5 which focuses on a number of classic web application threats, risks in D2.8 arise from affordances in the architectural and application asset models which admit of vulnerabilities and threats.

In addition to its name, each risk contains the threat and vulnerability name, together with a risk rating. This rating is evaluated using the table below, which is based on the vulnerability severity and threat likelihood. This table is based on (IEC61508).

	Catastrophic	Critical	Marginal	Negligible
Frequent	Intolerable	Intolerable	Intolerable	Undesirable
Probable	Intolerable	Intolerable	Undesirable	Undesirable

Occasional	Intolerable	Undesirable	Tolerable	Tolerable
Remote	Undesirable	Tolerable	Tolerable	Negligible
Improbable	Tolerable	Tolerable	Negligible	Negligible
Incredible	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible

For every environment where the risk is present, an environment specific misuse case is written. This is written as a scenario describing how the attacker(s) associated with the risk's threat exploit the risk's vulnerability.

3.2. Assets

3.2.1. Introduction

- Overview of where assets have come from and how they are broken down

3.2.2. Account

Type	Information
Description	A money account holding a certain amount of a currency. It could be a credit card, debit card, a current account, savings account, or loan account, shares account, etc.
Significance	Two accounts are crucial to perform a transaction of money from a buyer to a seller.
Environments	Shopping

3.2.3. Application Instance

Type	Information
Description	
Significance	
Environments	Profile Management, Development and Deployment, Shopping

3.2.4. Application

Type	Information
Description	Packaged application and resources
Significance	Vulnerable resources and ill-defined application policies can compromise data and devices associated with an application
Environments	Development and Deployment, Context and Events

- Note: the application certificate is a distinct component of the application asset itself, but should be considered carefully as it is the critical component that confers strong identity to the application.

3.2.5. AugmentedRouteService

Type	Software
Description	A webinos interface to an online hosted augmented route service. Directions should be accurate and conform to user's reliability expectations (see also RouteService).
Significance	Should protect accuracy and secrecy of user data.
Environments	Navigation

3.2.6. CalendarApplicationInterface

Type	Software
Description	A webinos interface to a calendar hosted on a local Webinos runtime. The browser should be easy to use and conform to user's reliability expectations.
Significance	Should protect accuracy and secrecy of user data.
Environments	Navigation

3.2.7. Car_PersonalZoneProxy

Type	Information
Description	Proxy object for Webinos enabled in car system

Significance	The interface seen by other Webinos devices
Environments	Navigation

3.2.8. Car_WRT

Type	Software
Description	A local, installed platform/software layer that provides the APIs for Webinos-enabled in-car systems.
Significance	Should protect accuracy and secrecy of user data running within the run-time
Environments	Navigation

3.2.9. Configuration File

Type	Information
Description	Manifest describing the application's contents and policies.
Significance	Corrupted or ambiguous configuration files can lead to inappropriate application usage.
Environments	Development and Deployment

3.2.10. Context Data

Type	Information
Description	Context data collected by webinos and made available to other applications.
Significance	If not properly controlled, context data could be disclosed or tampered with by unauthorised subjects.
Environments	Context and Events

3.2.11. Context Handler

Type	Software
Description	Constructs PEP request context sent to the PDP.

Significance	Mediates between the PEP and PDP.
Environments	

3.2.12. Message Manager

Type	Information
Description	Message management component associated with a PZP.
Significance	Responsible for event routing.
Environments	

- Note: the messaging management component has a strong dependency on the OS components that deal with networking and addressability, which therefore become attractive attack points

3.2.13. Device API

Type	Software
Description	API for accessing device-specific functionality.
Significance	Manipulates device features and accesses privacy-sensitive data.
Environments	Profile Management, Context and Events

3.2.14. Event

Type	Information
Description	An object incorporating messaging attributes and additional webinos specific payload data and meta-data.
Significance	Event messaging attributes are potentially spoofable. Vulnerabilities intrinsic to the underlying technology, e.g. XMPP, JSON, also weaken webinos events.
Environments	Profile Management, Context and Events

3.2.15. EventNotificationService

Type	Software
Description	Part of the webinos Personal Zone Proxy responsible for event handling.
Significance	Compromising may lead to the submission of unauthorised events, or the receipt of malicious events.
Environments	Context and Events

3.2.16. Identity Provider

Type	System
Description	Interface through which an Identity Provider registers and provides authentication credentials.
Significance	Webinos may fall back on a less secure backup if this is not available
Environments	Profile Management

3.2.17. Intention

Type	Information
Description	Feature describing the developer's intent re: privacy data
Significance	Improperly defined intentions may exploit the user's trust in an application.
Environments	Development and Deployment

3.2.18. Invoice

Type	Information
Description	An invoice with priced items (products) and a total amount to be paid. Linked to a buyer, a seller, and a transaction
Significance	An invoice is crucial for buyers and sellers to trust shopping and payment activities from within webinos applications.
Environments	Shopping

3.2.19. Basket Item

Type	Information
Description	An item (product) can be added or removed to a shopping basket. It is linked to the seller/ holder of the item. It describes a digital or a physical product.
Significance	Without items (products) available for sale within an application, there will be less trade activities as a result of webinos in general.
Environments	Shopping

3.2.20. Local Data Cache

Type	System
Description	
Significance	
Environments	

3.2.21. MediaPlaybackService

Type	Software
Description	A webinos interface to a media streaming service. The stream should be accessible and conform to user's reliability expectations. Some level of privacy and accountability needs to hold when connecting to the player.
Significance	The media stream should not be tampered with.
Environments	Navigation, Home Media and Interactive TV

3.2.22. PaymentManager

Type	Software
Description	Payment manager used by a user to shop and pay from within an application.
Significance	The ability for users to purchase items (products) from within an application in a very secure and private way is a key asset.
Environments	Shopping

3.2.23. PaymentAdapter

Type	Software
Description	Payment adapter is used by a user to pay from within an application by using a specific payment means such as a credit card type, sms, etc.
Significance	The ability for users to pay for items (products) from within an application in a very secure and private way is a key asset.
Environments	Shopping

3.2.24. PersonalAugmentedRoutePlannerData

Type	Information
Description	Personal information about augmented route planner preferences.
Significance	Loss of preferences increases setup time when decide about privacy settings.
Environments	Navigation

3.2.25. PersonalCalendarData

Type	Information
Description	Personal information about media preferences.
Significance	Loss of preferences increases setup time when integrating with different media.
Environments	Navigation

3.2.26. PersonalMediaPreferences

Type	Information
Description	Personal information about media preferences.
Significance	Loss of preferences increases setup time when integrating with different media.
Environments	Navigation, Home Media and Interactive TV

3.2.27. PersonalRouteApplicationData

Type	Information
Description	Personal information about stored routes.
Significance	Loss of navigation data may let the user take another route.
Environments	Navigation

3.2.28. PersonalWebBrowserData

Type	Information
Description	Personal information about web browsing preferences.
Significance	Loss of preferences decreases usability forcing the user to manually insert missin data.
Environments	Navigation

3.2.29. PersonalZoneDeviceList

Type	Information
Description	The list of devicies in the personal zone
Significance	The data to use to select the device to connect with
Environments	Navigation

3.2.30. PersonalZoneHub

Type	Information
Description	The hub for a personal zone.
Significance	Controls addressing, information, and authentication in a zone.
Environments	Development and Deployment, Navigation, Home Media and Interactive TV, Context and Events

3.2.31. PersonalZoneProxy

Type	Information
Description	Proxy object for Webinos devices
Significance	The interface seen by other Webinos devices.
Environments	Profile Management, Development and Deployment, Context and Events

3.2.32. Policy Administration Point

Type	Information
Description	Defines the policy
Significance	Manages policy information.
Environments	

3.2.33. Policy Decision Point

Type	Information
Description	Evaluates whether or not a device can be accessed by a web application, based on the policy.
Significance	Decides policy access
Environments	

3.2.34. Policy Enforcement Point

Type	Information
Description	Allows or prevents access to device APIs.
Significance	Controls access to device APIs.
Environments	

3.2.35. Policy Information Point

Type	Information
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Description	Gathers information to be used by the PDP to evaluate an access control request.
Significance	Used by the PDP
Environments	

3.2.36. Privacy Proxy

Type	Information
Description	Policy stating the developer's intent re: privacy data associated with an application.
Significance	Improperly defined intentions may exploit the user's trust in an application.
Environments	Profile Management, Development and Deployment

3.2.37. Privileged Application

Type	System
Description	An application that can override system controls and check for specific user IDs (UIDs), group IDs (GIDs), authorizations, or privileges.
Significance	
Environments	

3.2.38. Registrar

Type	System
Description	The component of the PZH responsible for registering devices with personal zones.
Significance	A non-PZH device may run this component if a PZH is unavailable when registering devices.
Environments	Profile Management

3.2.39. Resource

Type	Information
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Description	Resource used by an application, e.g. HTML, Javascript, CSS
Significance	Corrupt resources may corrupt the entire application
Environments	Development and Deployment

3.2.40. RouteService

Type	Software
Description	A webinos interface to an online hosted route service. Directions should be accurate and conform to user's reliability expectations.
Significance	Should protect accuracy and secrecy of user data.
Environments	Navigation

3.2.41. Sandbox

Type	System
Description	Isolated environment within which an application instance is hosted
Significance	Sandbox weaknesses may introduce vulnerabilities to a running application, or cause an application instance to exploit other instances running within the runtime.
Environments	Development and Deployment

3.2.42. SecurityPolicy

Type	Information
Description	XACML policy file that is consulted by the PDP within a Webinos runtime.
Significance	Exploiting policies undermines the policy enforcement and decision process.
Environments	Context and Events

3.2.43. Service

Type	System
Description	Is the type (logical structure) of a remotely accessible webinos API

Significance	Define the logical functional capability that can be used - or abused by an application
Environments	

3.2.44. Service Instance

Type	Information
Description	The specific instantiation of the logical API capability
Significance	Can be concretely attacked to abuse the capability offered by the API
Environments	

3.2.45. Session

Type	System
Description	State data associated with a running instance of Webinos on a device.
Significance	Compromised session data might be used by an attacker to obtain data from other authorised webinos devices.
Environments	Profile Management

3.2.46. ShoppingBasket

Type	Software
Description	A digital shopping basket where the user can add/ remove items (products) to prior to checkout and paying.
Significance	Not providing this software will make shopping and payment more cumbersome for application developers that would like to embed shopping and payment support within the application.
Environments	Shopping

3.2.47. Signature

Type	Information
Description	Signature file associated with an application

Significance	Modifying this signature weakens the assurance held about an application
Environments	Development and Deployment

3.2.48. Smartphone_PersonalZoneProxy

Type	Information
Description	Proxy object for Webinos enabled smartphone
Significance	The interface seen by other Webinos devices
Environments	Navigation, Home Media and Interactive TV

3.2.49. Smartphone_WRT

Type	Software
Description	A local, installed platform/software layer that provides the APIs for Webinos-enabled smart-phones.
Significance	Should protect accuracy and secrecy of user data running within the run-time.
Environments	Navigation, Home Media and Interactive TV

3.2.50. StartFile

Type	Information
Description	An application start-up file
Significance	The critical path to starting an application
Environments	Development and Deployment

3.2.51. SynchronisedAppData

Type	Information
Description	A data area shared between particular Application Instances running on the same personal zone
Significance	Malicious data introduced to this area may corrupt all running application instances.

Environments	Development and Deployment
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3.2.52. TextInputService

Type	Software
Description	A text input service hosted locally on a Webinos runtime.
Significance	The text input service interface should not be tampered with. Some level of privacy and accountability needs to hold when connecting to the player.
Environments	

3.2.53. Transaction

Type	Information
Description	A transaction of money between to accounts
Significance	The transaction of money between two accounts should not be incorrectly altered, removed, or cancelled.
Environments	Shopping

3.2.54. Trusted Code Base

Type	System
Description	
Significance	
Environments	

3.2.55. User Profile

Type	Information
Description	
Significance	
Environments	

3.2.56. UserPrivacyPreferences

Type	Information
Description	The privacy preferences associated with a user.
Significance	Ambiguous, ignored or non-existing user privacy preferences may lead to an application betraying user's privacy expectations.
Environments	Development and Deployment

3.2.57. WebBrowser

Type	Software
Description	A web browser hosted on a local Webinos runtime. The browser should be easy to use and the web content should be displayed in a clear way.
Significance	Some level of privacy needs to hold when connecting to the web.
Environments	Navigation

3.2.58. WebinosRuntime

Type	Software
Description	A local, installed platform/software layer that provides the APIs for Webinos applications.
Significance	Should protect the user's privacy and security
Environments	Profile Management, Navigation, Home Media and Interactive TV, Development and Deployment, Shopping

3.2.59. Web Runtime Environment Specification

Type	Information
Description	
Significance	
Environments	

3.2.60. WebTV_PersonalZoneProxy

Type	Information
Description	Proxy object for Webinos enabled WebTV
Significance	The interface seen by other Webinos devices
Environments	Navigation, Home Media and Interactive TV

3.2.61. WebTV_WRT

Type	Software
Description	A local, installed platform/software layer that provides the APIs for Webinos-enabled TVs.
Significance	Should protect accuracy and secrecy of user data running within the run-time.
Environments	Navigation, Home Media and Interactive TV

3.2.62. Widget Metadata

Type	Information
Description	Widget metadata describing an application to collaborating applications.
Significance	Used by another application to establish some level of trust.
Environments	

3.2.63. ZoneSynchronizationService

Type	Software
Description	A service for synchronizing local data and events with other devices within a user's Personal Zone
Significance	Should ensure data integrity within a Personal Zone
Environments	Context and Events

3.3. Architectural asset models

3.3.1. Development and Deployment

3.3.1.1 Model

3.3.1.2 Asset Values

Asset	Property	Value	Rationale
Application	Confidentiality	Medium	A danger that resources and keys might get ripped off. From a developer's perspective, Confidentiality is more important than Integrity.
Application	Accountability	Medium	Spoofing authority could lead to unauthorised changes to a package.
App Instance	Confidentiality	Medium	This may be running code over and above what was defined in the Configuration File.
App Instance	Integrity	Medium	This may be running code over and above what was defined in the Configuration File.
Configuration File	Integrity	Medium	This asset defines permissions about what the application will do.

Configuration File	Accountability	Medium	This asset assigns responsibility to the application.
Intention	Integrity	Medium	An attacker can formulate intentions unacceptable to everyone.
Personal Zone Proxy	Confidentiality	Low	Contains a list of every installed application, some of which might be sensitive. For example, we may not want everyone to know that one application is on a particular device.
Personal Zone Proxy	Integrity	High	A privileged asset. Compromising this compromises other applications within the Personal Zone
Personal Zone Hub	Confidentiality	Low	Contains a list of every installed application, some of which might be sensitive. For example, we may not want everyone to know that one application is on a particular device.
Personal Zone Hub	Integrity	High	A privileged asset. Compromising this compromises other applications within the Personal Zone
Privacy Policy	Integrity	Medium	An attacker can make a privacy policy unacceptable to everyone.
Resource	Confidentiality	Medium	A danger that resources and keys might get ripped off. From a developer's perspective, Confidentiality is more important than Integrity.
Sandbox	Integrity	High	An attacker who can manipulate the sandbox can circumvent all its security mechanisms.
Signature	Availability	Medium	Needs to exist to allow authenticating the developer and validate integrity of the code.
StartFile	Integrity	Medium	Corrupting this could divert users to a malicious location.
Synchronised	Confidentiality	Medium	Don't want people to see this data.

App Data			
Synchronised App Data	Integrity	Medium	Don't want people to tamper with this data.
Synchronised App Data	Availability	Low	We want people to take advantage of this asset, but also not to not assume that this will always be available.
User Privacy Preferences	Pseudonymity	Medium	Don't want applications to send subject data back to a provider.
Webinos Runtime	Availability	Low	Needs to be available for an application to be deployed.

3.3.2. Context and Events Asset Model

3.3.2.1 Model

3.3.2.2 Asset Values

Asset	Property	Value	Rationale
Application	Confidentiality	Medium	The user will indicate if the app has access to context data. We should check for malware and privacy leaks in apps
Context Data	Confidentiality	Low	

Context Data	Integrity	Medium	The offered context data needs to be accurate, otherwise developers will find ways of working around it.
Context Data	Anonymity	Medium	Context data has to be linkable to a certain user. Context Data also needs to be available at the cost of privacy.
Device API	Integrity	High	A compromised API could mean a serious security breach regarding context and events and is a potential leakage point.
Device API	Accountability	Medium	Changes made to the API need to be tracked to make sure only authorized entities can do this.
Event	Integrity	Medium	Tampering with the contents of event data could lead to the circumvention of other security controls.
Event	Availability	Low	Loss of event data leads to gradual degradation of webinos services and any applications depending on these events.
Event	Confidentiality	Medium	Events should only be interpretable by authorized entities.
Event Notification Service	Confidentiality	Medium	Event Notifications should only be sent to the correct entities.
Event Notification Service	Availability	High	Event notifications are crucial for cooperating devices (and thus webinos).
Personal Zone Hub	Integrity	High	There is more context data associated with a PersonalZoneHub than with a PersonalZoneProxy. Need for synchronization between hub and connected proxies in order to ensure data integrity.
Personal Zone Proxy	Integrity	Medium	Hubs should not pretend to be proxies, or vice versa.

Personal Zone Proxy	Confidentiality	Medium	Context information should be stored securely on the device and not be disclosed to unauthorized entities. Mainly through connectivity, physical security of the device is the user's responsibility.
Security Policy	Integrity	Medium	Unwanted modification of policies may lead to unauthorised disclosure of context data.
Security Policy	Accountability	Medium	Changes to policies need to be tracked to ensure all modifications are made by authorised subjects.
Zone Synchronization Service	Integrity	Low	Synchronization between hub and connected proxies in order to ensure data integrity throughout the different devices within a user's Personal Zone.
Zone Synchronization Service	Confidentiality	Medium	Synchronization should only be performed when authorized by the user and only with the user's Personal Zone Hub.

3.3.3. Profile Management Asset Model

3.3.3.1 Model

3.3.3.2 Asset Values

Asset	Property	Value	Rationale
ApplicationInstance	Confidentiality	Medium	Secrecy of identity and session data can be compromised by accessing malicious data assumed to be trusted.
Device API	Integrity	Medium	Tampering with device APIs may compromise the generation of session related events necessary for maintaining the integrity of session and identity data.
Event	Integrity	Medium	Tampering with the contents of event data could lead to the circumvention of other security controls.
Event	Availability	Low	Loss of event data leads to gradual degradation of webinos services and any

			applications depending on these events.
Personal Zone Hub	Confidentiality	Low	May have knowledge of different sessions, which may be sensitive based on the sessions themselves.
Personal Zone Hub	Integrity	Medium	A privileged asset. Compromising this may compromise other sessions within the Personal Zone.
Personal Zone Proxy	Unobservability	Medium	Design decisions associated with the management and transfer of sessions and identity that unnecessarily advertise a proxy's presence may, in certain circumstances, introduce subject observability affordances.
Registrar	Availability	Medium	Failure of the registrar weakens any session and identity management services which cross personal zones.
Registrar	Anonymity	Low	Minor errors may lead to data leakage eventually contributing to disclosure of a subject's identity.
Session	Confidentiality	High	Disclosed sessions enables access to webinos data and services on devices within a personal zone.
Session	Integrity	Medium	Compromised sessions enables may lead to malicious modification to webinos data and services.

3.4. Application asset models

3.4.1. Home Media and Interactive TV Asset Model

3.4.1.1 Model

3.4.1.2 Asset Values

Asset	Property	Value	Rationale
PersonalZoneHub	Availability	Medium	Without PersonalZoneHub the WRT will try to use the PersonalZoneProxy
Smartphone_PersonalZoneProxy	Availability	High	Without the PersonalZoneProxy the WRT lacks of synchronization capabilities and of access to services
WebTV_PersonalZoneProxy	Availability	High	Without the PersonalZoneProxy the WRT lacks of synchronization capabilities and of access to services
Smartphone_WRT	Confidentiality	Low	Desirable, but only a minor inconvenience if runtime data is disclosed.
Smartphone_WRT	Integrity	High	Inaccurate or incomplete runtime data may cause system malfunctions. e.g. corruption of generic system data
Smartphone_WRT	Availability	High	Webinos applications can't run without Webinos Runtime
WebTV_WRT	Confidentiality	Low	Desirable, but only a minor inconvenience if runtime data is disclosed.
WebTV_WRT	Integrity	High	Inaccurate or incomplete runtime data may cause system malfunctions. e.g. corruption of generic system data.
WebTV_WRT	Availability	High	Webinos applications can't run without Webinos Runtime

MediaPlaybackService	Integrity	Low	Desirable, but only a minor inconvenience if the media stream is inaccurate or incomplete. An integrity compromise may cause negligible quality reduction (e.g. some frame in a video playback)
MediaPlaybackService	Availability	High	A significant annoyance if the availability of the media stream is compromised. An availability compromise may cause the complete loss of the media streaming
MediaPlaybackService	Accountability	High	User actions must be traced in case of services with fee
MediaPlaybackService	Anonymity	Low	It is preferable to not disclose the user identity
MediaPlaybackService	Pseudonymity	Low	It's preferable if any accountability required by Webinos to associate controller services to the media stream did not disclose the controller subject's identity
MediaPlaybackService	Unlinkability	Low	It's preferable if the user may make multiple uses of resources or services without others being able to link these uses together
PersonalMediaPreferences	Availability	Low	Lack of availability to these preferences is an annoyance more than anything else. Without personal preferences the user need to manually setup the device

PersonalMediaPreferences	Confidentiality	High	Personal media preferences may store very sensitive data, e.g. CC numbers used for "pay per view" services
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3.4.2. Navigation Asset Model

3.4.2.1 Model

3.4.2.2 Asset Values

Asset	Property	Value	Rationale
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PersonalZoneHub	Availability	Medium	Without PersonalZoneHub the WRT will try to use the PersonalZoneProxy
PersonalZoneDeviceList	Availability	Medium	Without the PersonalZoneDeviceList it is more difficult to connect to devices in the personal zone
PersonalZoneDeviceList	Confidentiality	Low	If device list is disclosed an attacker may know address of devices in the personal zone
Car_PersonalZoneProxy	Availability	High	Without the PersonalZoneProxy the WRT lacks of synchronization capabilities and of access to services
Smartphone_PersonalZoneProxy	Availability	High	Without the PersonalZoneProxy the WRT lacks of synchronization capabilities and of access to services
WebTV_PersonalZoneProxy	Availability	High	Without the PersonalZoneProxy the WRT lacks of synchronization capabilities and of access to services
Car_WRT	Confidentiality	Low	Desirable, but only a minor inconvenience if runtime data is disclosed. e.g. disclosure of generic

			system data
Car_WRT	Integrity	High	Inaccurate or incomplete runtime data may cause system malfunctions, e.g. corruption of generic system data
Car_WRT	Availability	High	Webinos applications can't run without Webinos Runtime
Smartphone_WRT	Confidentiality	Low	Desirable, but only a minor inconvenience if runtime data is disclosed.
Smartphone_WRT	Integrity	High	Inaccurate or incomplete runtime data may cause system malfunctions, e.g. corruption of generic system data.
Smartphone_WRT	Availability	High	Webinos applications can't run without Webinos Runtime
WebTV_WRT	Confidentiality	Low	Desirable, but only a minor inconvenience if runtime data is disclosed.
WebTV_WRT	Integrity	High	Inaccurate or incomplete runtime data may cause system malfunctions. e.g. corruption of generic system data.
WebTV_WRT	Availability	High	Webinos applications can't run without Webinos Runtime
RouteService	Integrity	High	A significant annoyance if

			the integrity of the route service is compromised. An integrity compromise may cause wrong routes
RouteService	Availability	High	A significant annoyance if the availability of the route service is compromised. An availability compromise may cause the miss of some direction
RouteService	Accountability	High	User actions must be traced in case of services with fee
RouteService	Anonymity	Low	It is preferable to not disclose the user identity
RouteService	Pseudonymity	Low	It's preferable if possible accountability required by the service does not imply user's identity disclosure
RouteService	Unlinkability	Low	It's preferable if the user may make multiple uses of resources or services without others being able to link these uses together
AugmentedRouteService	Integrity	High	A significant annoyance if the integrity of the route service is compromised. An integrity compromise may cause wrong routes
AugmentedRouteService	Availability	High	A significant annoyance if the availability of the augmented route service is compromised. An availability compromise

			may cause the miss of some direction
AugmentedRouteService	Accountability	High	User actions must be traced in case of services with fee
AugmentedRouteService	Anonymity	Low	It is preferable to not disclose the user identity
AugmentedRouteService	Pseudonymity	Low	It's preferable if possible accountability required by the service does not imply user's identity disclosure
AugmentedRouteService	Unlinkability	Low	It's preferable if the user may make multiple uses of resources or services without others being able to link these uses together
MediaPlaybackService	Integrity	Low	Desirable, but only a minor inconvenience if the media stream is inaccurate or incomplete. An integrity compromise may cause negligible quality reduction (e.g. some frame in a video playback).
MediaPlaybackService	Availability	High	A significant annoyance if the availability of the media stream is compromised. An availability compromise may cause the complete loss of the media streaming
MediaPlaybackService	Accountability	High	User actions must be traced in case of services

			with fee
MediaPlaybackService	Anonymity	Low	It is preferable to not disclose the user identity
MediaPlaybackService	Pseudonymity	Low	It's preferable if service delivery does not require user's identity disclosure
MediaPlaybackService	Unlinkability	Low	It's preferable if the user may make multiple uses of resources or services without others being able to link these uses together
CalendarApplicationInterface	Integrity	High	Unreliable behaviour can result in missing commitments, appointments and meetings, making the application useless
CalendarApplicationInterface	Availability	High	A significant annoyance if the availability of the calendar application is compromised. An availability compromise may let the user miss commitments
PersonalCalendarData	Confidentiality	High	A confidentiality compromise may cause unauthorized disclosure of user commitments.
PersonalRouteApplicationData	Confidentiality	Medium	A confidentiality compromise may cause unauthorized disclosure of user routes.

PersonalAugmentedRoutePlannerData	Confidentiality	Medium	A confidentiality compromise may cause unauthorized disclosure of user routes.
PersonalMediaPreferences	Availability	Low	Lack of availability to these preferences is an annoyance more than anything else. Without personal preferences the user need to manually setup the device.
PersonalMediaPreferences	Confidentiality	High	Personal media preferences may store very sensitive data, e.g. credit card number used for "pay per view" services
WebBrowser (on line transaction)	Confidentiality	High	On line transactions must be confidential. A confidentiality compromise may cause loss of sensitive data (e.g. credit card number).
WebBrowser (on line transaction)	Integrity	High	On line transactions must not be changed by unauthorized parties. An integrity compromise may cause the alteration of sensitive data (e.g. the cost)
PersonalWebBrowserData	Confidentiality	Low	A confidentiality compromise may cause the unauthorized disclosure of user browsing habits.
PersonalWebBrowserData	Availability	Low	Without personal

			preferences the user need to manually setup the browser
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3.4.3. Shopping asset model

3.4.3.1 Model

3.4.3.2 Asset Values

Asset	Property	Value	Rationale
PaymentManager	Confidentiality	High	Any access information between the payment manager and an application instance must be kept very confidential, because other application instances might want to use the information
PaymentManager	Integrity	High	Tampering with any parts of the payment manager source code could lead to fraudulent and/or incorrect transactions, if the code that performs the transaction was to be embedded somewhere in the payment manager.
PaymentAdapter	Confidentiality	High	Any information related to the access and use of the payment adapter by an application instance must be kept very confidential, because other application instances could incorrectly or maliciously perform payments, if they got hold of the payment adapter instance and any payment information related to it.
PaymentAdapter	Integrity	High	Tampering with the source code could lead to fraudulent and/or incorrect transactions, because the transaction happens as a direct result of using the payment adapter.
Account	Confidentiality	High	Any information related to an account must be kept very confidential, with the exception that the receiving account holder has specified information about the receiving account. If account information is not kept very confidential, then people can start to attack the disclosed account.
Account	Integrity	High	The illicit transaction of money between two accounts, or the tampering of the current amount within an account, will lead to distrust in webinos.

Invoice	Confidentiality	High	Any access to the invoice information could lead to the incorrect loss/gain of money or items. One example is a user making incorrect reimbursement claims to people that were not involved in the transaction. Other misuse examples could be an attacker wanting to know which items were traded, the price of the traded items, or trying to trace the transaction information.
Invoice	Integrity	High	The duplication or tampering of invoices could lead to loss/gain of money or items to the wrong persons. Another example of misuse could be a person wanting to modify some price information on the invoice. A third example would be the deletion of the invoice.
Item	Confidentiality	High	Any information about items involved in a shopping scenario, including the unsuccessful ones, must be kept confidential. This is because attackers using another application instance could obtain knowledge about what the user is buying or have interest for. This information could be used in an attempt to obtain access to the traded item, or as means to bring harm to the user by misusing the information.
Item	Integrity	High	Any information about items being subject for shopping by a user must have high integrity. This is because the information could incorrectly be changed by an attacker to alter information about the shopping. One example could be a user buying "milk", for the attacker later to change the product information to be "cigarettes". Another example could be the user believing that she is buying music for Euro 5, and the attacker changing the price - either just before the transaction or at a later stage.

Transaction	Confidentiality	High	Any information about a transaction between two account holders can be misused in various ways. One example could be an attacker wanting to know who is involved in a transaction. Another example could be an application instance trying to incorrectly cancel a transaction upon the shipping/ delivery of the traded item(s).
Transaction	Integrity	High	If an application can perform a transaction without the consent of the holder of money or items, then this can lead to the incorrect loss/gain of money or items for a holder.
ShoppingBasket	Confidentiality	High	A shopping basket will be provided to the application instance if a user would like to shop something. The shopping basket must be kept secret from all other application instances. This is because other application instances could incorrectly see/alter the contents of the shopping basket. The attacker could by such incorrect access obtain a perfectly valid transaction involving items that s/he is not the legitimate holder of. Another misuse could be an attacker performing online-to-door shopping on behalf of a user when the user is away on holiday. The items could be delivered to the door the next day as the attacker is waiting outside the user's home to receive the items.
ShoppingBasket	Integrity	High	The integrity of the shopping basket must be high, otherwise an application instance could incorrectly add items to the shopping basket of another application instance. An attacker could by this obtain a valid transaction by adding items valid for one application instance to the shopping basket of another application instance. The attacker could then show that there was a valid purchase, and the correct holder of the

			item would then loose money.
ApplicationInstance	Integrity	High	The integrity of an application instance must be high. The application instance could be altered by modifying the behaviour at runtime. An example could be the injection of code at the time of transfer or while it is being executed. Alternatively the application code could be altered between application sessions. One example could be the change to obtain money laundry, another could be to obtain cheap goods, and a third could be to make the correct holder of items loose money by setting the price of all items to a very low amount.
WebinosRuntime	Integrity	High	The payment API is part of the webinos runtime. If the webinos runtime is altered, then this could corrupt the payment functions.

3.5. Vulnerabilities

Given the scope of webinos and the current stage of webinos' design, a exhaustive list of webinos vulnerabilities would be impossible to complete. Instead, the following vulnerabilities were identified before during the asset modelling exercise, and afterwards as a consequence of discussions in other work packages.

3.5.1. Automatic login

Type	Configuration Vulnerability
Description	With automatic login enabled, anyone can authenticate himself as the default user

3.5.1.1 Navigation

Severity	Critical
Assets	PersonalWebBrowserData, PersonalAugmentedRoutePlannerData, PersonalCalendarData, PersonalMediaPreferences, PersonalRouteApplicationData, WebBrowser, CalendarApplication

3.5.1.2 Home Media and Interactive TV

Severity	Critical
Assets	PersonalMediaPreferences

3.5.2. Cloud hosted PZH

Type	Environmental Vulnerability
Description	Vulnerabilities associated with the virtual appliance hosting a PZH also affect the PZH

3.5.2.1 Profile Management

Severity	Marginal
Assets	PersonalZoneHub WebinosRuntime

3.5.3. Improper privacy protection

Type	Sensitive Data Protection Vulnerability
Description	Sensitive data do not have more protection than other data

3.5.3.1 Navigation

Severity	Critical
Assets	PersonalWebBrowserData, PersonalAugmentedRoutePlannerData, PersonalCalendarData, PersonalMediaPreferences, PersonalRouteApplicationData

3.5.3.2 Home Media and Interactive TV

Severity	Critical
Assets	PersonalMediaPreferences

3.5.4. Improper timeout

Type	Session Management Vulnerability
Description	The session is not automatically closed after a reasonable time of inactivity

3.5.4.1 Navigation

Severity	Critical
Assets	PersonalWebBrowserData, WebBrowser

3.5.5. Incorrect gain/loss of money or items in conjunction with shopping and payment

Type	API Abuse Vulnerability
Description	An attacker can abuse non-integrity of shopping and payment information in conjunction with the payment API achieve incorrect gain/loss of money for the user and other entities.

3.5.5.1 Shopping

Severity	Critical
Assets	Payment Manager, Payment Adapter, Shopping Basket, Invoice, Transaction, Account, Item

3.5.6. JSON Injection

Type	Input Validation Vulnerability
Description	An attacker can abuse the deserialisation process by supplying malicious JavaScript expressions as parameter values.

3.5.6.1 Profile Management

Severity	Marginal
Assets	Event

3.5.7. Lack of data provenance

Type	Data Protection Vulnerability
Description	An attacker can abuse the lack of provenance associated with context and event data to bypass policy enforcement mechanisms

3.5.7.1 Context and Events

Severity	Critical
Assets	Device API ,Context Data

3.5.8. Lack of information integrity for shopping and payment

Type	Data Protection Vulnerability
Description	An attacker can abuse non-integrity of shopping and payment information in conjunction with the payment API to attack the user or another entity involved in the shopping and payment scenario. Alternatively also to gain benefits for the attacker.

3.5.8.1 Shopping

Severity	Critical
Assets	Payment Manager, Payment Adapter, Shopping Basket, Invoice, Transaction, Account, Item

3.5.9. Lack of sensitive data protection for shopping and payment

Type	Sensitive Data Vulnerability
Description	An attacker can abuse the sensitive data in conjunction with the payment API to attack the user or another entity involved in the shopping and payment scenario.

3.5.9.1 Shopping

Severity	Critical
Assets	Payment Manager, Payment Adapter, Shopping Basket, Invoice, Transaction, Account, Item

3.5.10. Permissive convergence preferences

Type	Obscuring potential information flow
Description	Permissive convergence preferences might be unintentionally linkable to other Webinos applications.

3.5.10.1 Device Feature Integration

Severity	Marginal
Assets	PersonalMediaPreferences

3.5.11. PZH unprotected access

Type	Configuration Vulnerability
Description	If the PZH access is unprotected everyone can access the PersonalZoneDeviceList

3.5.11.1 Navigation

Severity	Marginal
Assets	PersonalZoneDeviceList

3.5.12. Session Fixation

Type	Session Management Vulnerability
Description	Authenticating a user without invalidating any existing session identifier gives an attacker the opportunity to steal authenticated Webinos sessions.

3.5.12.1 Profile Management

Severity	Critical
Assets	Session

3.5.13. System data trust

Type	Environmental Vulnerability
Description	Security based on event locations is insecure and can be spoofed.

3.5.13.1 Context and Events

Severity	Critical
Assets	Device API ,Context Data

3.5.14. Unencrypted data transmission

Type	Configuration Vulnerability
Description	By default the transmitted data is not encrypted

3.5.14.1 Navigation

Severity	Critical
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Assets	PersonalWebBrowserData, PersonalAugmentedRoutePlannerData, PersonalCalendarData, PersonalMediaPreferences, PersonalRouteApplicationData
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3.5.15. Unlimited clients number

Type	Availability Vulnerability
Description	The attacker may cause availability problems creating many clients

3.5.15.1 Home Media and Interactive TV

Severity	Critical
Assets	MediaPlaybackService

3.5.16. Weak credential

Type	Authentication Vulnerability
Description	A weak credential may be easily broken by an attacker

3.5.16.1 Home Media and Interactive TV

Severity	Critical
Assets	MediaPlaybackService

3.5.17. Weak cryptography

Type	Cryptographic Vulnerability
Description	Data is encrypted using a weak cryptographic algorithm

3.5.17.1 Navigation

Severity	Critical
Assets	PersonalWebBrowserData, PersonalAugmentedRoutePlannerData, PersonalCalendarData, PersonalMediaPreferences, PersonalRouteApplicationData

3.6. Threats

Like the vulnerabilities section, the following threats were identified during the asset modelling exercise, and afterwards during webinos discussions in other work packages.

3.6.1. Asymmetric resource consumption

Type	Resource Depletion
Method	The attacker forces the victim to consume more resources than it should be allowed

3.6.1.1 Home Media and Interactive TV

Likelihood	Occasional	
Attackers	Frankie	
Assets	MediaPlayerService	
Property	Value	Rationale
Availability	Medium	The attacker may saturate the bandwidth asking for many audio streams

3.6.2. Autologin abuse

Type	Exploitation of Authentication
Method	If the autologin is enabled, an attacker can authenticate himself as the default user

3.6.2.1 Navigation

Likelihood	Occasional	
Attackers	Frankie	
Assets	PersonalWebBrowserData, PersonalAugmentedRoutePlannerData, PersonalCalendarData, PersonalMediaPreferences, PersonalRouteApplicationData, WebBrowser, CalendarApplication	
Property	Value	Rationale
Confidentiality	Medium	The attacker can access user personal data

3.6.2.2 Home Media and Interactive TV

Likelihood	Occasional
Attackers	Gloria, Frankie
Assets	PersonalMediaPreferences

Property	Value	Rationale
Confidentiality	High	The attacker can access very sensitive user personal data (e.g. CC number)

3.6.3. Cross Site Request Forgery

Type	Embedded Malicious Code
Method	The attacker tricks the victim into loading a page that contains a request that inherits the webinos identity and privileges of the victim to perform an undesired function on the belief of the victim.

3.6.3.1 Profile Management

Likelihood	Probable
Attackers	Ethan
Assets	ApplicationInstance,Session

Property	Value	Rationale
Confidentiality	Medium	The attack allows the malicious code access to session data, some of which may be long-lived.
Anonymity	Low	The malicious request associated with the CSRF may involve harvesting small amounts of data which, collectively, could lead to the disclosure of a subject's identity.

3.6.4. Cryptanalysis

Type	Probabilistic Techniques
Method	The attacker uses weaknesses in cryptographic algorithms to decipher the ciphertext without knowing the secret key

3.6.4.1 Navigation

Likelihood	Remote
Attackers	David
Assets	PersonalWebBrowserData, PersonalAugmentedRoutePlannerData,

	PersonalCalendarData, PersonalMediaPreferences, PersonalRouteApplicationData	
Property	Value	Rationale
Confidentiality	High	The attacker can access all user personal data on the mass memory (password, CC number, etc.)

3.6.5. Dictionary attack

Type	Probabilistic Techniques
Method	The attacker uses a list of common passwords to try to bypass security mechanisms

3.6.5.1 Home Media and Interactive TV

Likelihood	Occasional	
Attackers	Ethan	
Assets	MediaPlayerService	
Property	Value	Rationale
Accountability	High	The attacker may break the owner password to access pay TV subscription and receive channels with fee

3.6.6. DoS attack

Type	Resource Depletion
Method	The attacker makes a resource unavailable for the purpose it was designed

3.6.6.1 Home Media and Interactive TV

Likelihood	Occasional	
Attackers	Frankie	
Assets	MediaPlayerService	
Property	Value	Rationale
Availability	High	The attacker can stop the streaming service

3.6.7. Man-In-The-Middle Attack

Type	Spoofing
Method	The man-in-the middle attack intercepts a communication between two systems. For example, in an http transaction the target is the TCP connection between client and server. Using different techniques, the attacker splits the original TCP connection into 2 new connections, one between the client and the attacker and the other between the attacker and the server. Once the TCP connection is intercepted, the attacker acts as a proxy, being able to read, insert and modify the data in the intercepted communication.

3.6.7.1 Profile Management

Likelihood	Remote	
Attackers	Harold	
Assets	Webinos Runtime	
Property	Value	Rationale
Integrity	Medium	Harold relies on unencrypted traffic to modify runtime state.

3.6.8. Network eavesdropping

Type	Sniffing Attacks
Method	The attacker captures packets transmitted by others' computers

3.6.8.1 Navigation

Likelihood	Probable	
Attackers	Frankie	
Assets	PersonalWebBrowserData, PersonalAugmentedRoutePlannerData, PersonalCalendarData, PersonalMediaPreferences, PersonalRouteApplicationData	
Property	Value	Rationale
Confidentiality	High	The attacker can access all wireless transmitted/synchronized user personal data (password, CC number, etc.)

3.6.9. NFC replay Attack

Type	Abuse of Functionality
Method	Using a ghost and leech device, an attacker forwards a request to the victim's reader device and relays the answer back in real time via a webinos overlay network.

3.6.9.1 Context and Events

Likelihood	Remote	
Attackers	David	
Assets	Device API, PersonalZoneProxy, Webinos Runtime	
Property	Value	Rationale
Confidentiality	Medium	David is interested in obtaining confidential information available to the webinos runtime.
Accountability	High	David relies on seamless convergence and a lack of traceability to carry out this attack.

3.6.10. Online Fraud

Type	Data Structure Attack Threat, Embedded Malicious Code Threat, Injection Threat, Resource Manipulation Threat , Protocol Manipulation Threat, Exploitation of Authentication Threat
Method	A malicious application instance misuses a user's shopping and payment information for the incorrect gain/loss of money or products for either the user, the seller, the attacker, or any other person.

3.6.10.1 Shopping

Likelihood	Likely	
Attackers	Ethan	
Assets	PaymentManager, PaymentAdapter, ShoppingBasket, Invoice, Transaction, ApplicationInstance, Account, Item	
Property	Value	Rationale
Confidentiality	High	Ethan is interested in obtaining payment information, such as credit

		card and passwords, related to individual transactions
Integrity	High	Ethan is interested in obtaining information about the items that were bought related to the individual transactions

3.6.11. Personal Zone Subversion

Type	Exploitation of Authentication
Method	The attacker can use stolen user credential to take control of the personal zone

3.6.11.1 Navigation

Likelihood	Occasional	
Attackers	Ethan	
Assets	PersonalZoneHub, PersonalZoneDeviceList, Car_PersonalZoneProxy, Smartphone_PersonalZoneProxy, WebTV_PersonalZoneProxy, Car_WRT, Spartphone_WRT, WebTV_WRT, MediaPlayerService, PersonalMediaPreferences, RouteService, PersonalRouteApplicationData, AugmentedRouteService, PersonalAugmentedRoutePlannerData, CalendarApplication, PersonalCalendarData, WebBrowser, PersonalWebBrowserData	
Property	Value	Rationale
Confidentiality	High	The attacker can access all user personal data
Integrity	High	The attacker can corrupt all user personal data
Availability	Low	The attacker may subtract all resouces to the user but is more likely he uses a reasonable amount of them to not be detected

3.6.12. PZH access abuse

Type	Exploitation of Authentication
Method	If the PZH access is unprotected, the attacker can retrieve the personal zone device list

3.6.12.1 Navigation

Likelihood	Probable
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Attackers	Frankie	
Assets	PersonalZoneDeviceList	
Property	Value	Rationale
Confidentiality	Medium	The attacker can access user personal data

3.6.13. Repudiation Attack

Type	Resource Manipulation
Method	Malicious manipulation or forging the identification of new actions. This attack changes the authoring information of actions executed by a malicious user in order to log wrong data to log files. Its usage could be extended to general data manipulation in the name of others, in a similar manner as spoofing mail messages. If this attack takes place, the data stored on log files can be considered invalid or misleading.

3.6.13.1 Device Feature Integration

Likelihood	Remote	
Attackers	Ethan	
Assets	PersonalMediaPreferences, Smartphone_WRT	
Property	Value	Rationale
Integrity	Medium	Ethan's ability to manipulate media preferences and other personal or log data should be considered a significant attack.

3.6.14. Session hijacking

Type	Exploitation of Authentication
Method	The attacker exploits the web session control mechanism to hijack the user session

3.6.14.1 Navigation

Likelihood	Occasional
Attackers	Frankie
Assets	PersonalWebBrowserData, WebBrowser

Property	Value	Rationale
Confidentiality	Medium	The attacker can access user session data
Accountability	High	The attacker can access user active session of the service. If it is a service with fee, the attacker can spend user money

3.6.15. Spyware

Type	Anonymity Threat
Method	A malicious application captures private information and sends it out of a device without user acceptance.

3.6.15.1 Context and Events

Likelihood	Probable	
Attackers	Jimmy	
Assets	ContextData	
Property	Value	Rationale
Anonymity	Low	The disclosed context data is granular enough that a non-trivial amount of effort would be needed to render a subject identifiable.

3.7. Risks and Misuse Cases

Following discussions about the elicited threats and vulnerabilities between March and August 2011, the following security and privacy risks and misuse cases were elicited.

Possible mitigations to these risks are described in the Recommendations section.

3.7.1. Capture hidden analytics

Threat	Spyware
Vulnerability	Lack of data provenance
Rating	Intolerable

3.7.1.1 Context and Events *Misuse Case*

Peter is about to head to Berlin for a long weekend and decides to download the Berlin Gallery Guide from the Android app store. This application gives Peter a quick overview of art galleries in Berlin and allows him to take snaps and submit reviews about places visited. Before downloading the app, Peter checks what the application has access to. Additionally, before running the app for the first time, he also scans the application's terms and conditions, briefly noting that the application captures information about time. Several days later, Peter is walking out of the Neue Nationalgalerie and submits some of his thoughts about the gallery as a review.

One month earlier, Jimmy was in the midst of a dilemma. His Berlin cafe guide was more successful than he thought, but he really wished that he had captured more analytics information; his new Berlin Gallery Guide might be just the opportunity he needs to get this data. While Peter really wants to capture information about location rather than time of review, this would mean re-drafting the privacy policy associated with the app to better reflect his intentions; this is both time consuming and, to his mind, unnecessary. "I mean" Jimmy thought, "I'm the only person using the data, and I'm not going to abuse it so who really cares if I capture location data rather than time in my app. The PDP associated with the running application won't notice the difference and, perhaps, maybe that means capturing this data is ok." Eventually, Jimmy convinces himself to reuse his previous privacy policy and configuration file entries related to permission, but change the Javascript code to store location data as context data rather than time.

Several weeks later, Jimmy feels vindicated by this decision as useful, fine-grained location data starts to arrive via his gallery guide app, including unauthorised location data arising about Peter's visit to Neue Nationalgalerie.

3.7.2. Control cloud-based PZH

Threat	Man-In-The-Middle Attack
Vulnerability	Cloud hosted PZH
Rating	Tolerable

3.7.2.1 Profile Management *Misuse Case*

Harold is preparing a workshop presentation on how easy it still is to exploit the migration process of virtual machines. In readiness for this, he decide to monitor the traffic at a cloud service provider which he knows uses insecure network paths to maximise throughput between

its site. Harold decides to track one particular VM site transfer and, using his exploit tools, Harold is able to manipulate the in-memory object code of sshd.

When the transfer is complete, Harold is able to ssh to the VM as root and look around the VM. While examining the available processes, Harold notices a disproportionate amount of resources being used by a process called *node*. Curious, Harold begins examining this process in more detail with a view to talking about one of his 'owned' applications in his workshop talk.

3.7.3. Exploit network bandwidth

Threat	Repudiation Attack
Vulnerability	Permissive convergence preferences
Rating	Tolerable

3.7.3.1 Device Feature Integration Misuse Case

Ethan has discovered that, invariably, webinos users have over-permissive convergence settings between devices used in the home and, with by altering the right settings, it is possible to change network service settings. This is especially useful given that some network providers, as part of their business model, allow users to change their bandwidth settings online via webinos. This is a boon for Ethan's botnet business the convergence affordances allow him to easily increase the bandwidth available to his botnet clients.

A number of botnet client machines were running webinos, so he tried connecting to one of them and running a customised webinos web service client to discover any available webinos services. Sure enough, he discovered a text input service running on a mobile phone. Ethan was able to easily connect to this and manipulate the machine owner's "use maximum bandwidth" setting. If he was lucky, the machine owner's network provider would automatically increase this home's bandwidth without the owner ever finding out.

3.7.4. Multimedia stream availability problem

Threat	Autologin abuse, Asymmetric resource consumption, DoS attack
Vulnerability	Automatic login, Unlimited clients number
Rating	Undesirable

3.7.4.1 Home Media and Interactive TV Misuse Case

Frankie is scanning the internet looking for something to attack. When he finds an unprotected webinos enabled TV (Alice's TV) he tries to fiddle with it.

He discovers that it is possible to remotely select and receive an alternative audio stream. He asks for the English audio stream, the French one, the German one, the Spanish one, and so on to try to saturate the bandwidth.

Alice is watching the TV, the streaming starts to have some freeze and after a while is completely halted. She wonders what happened. Cables are properly plugged in. "This webinos enabled TV is a real rip-off" she thinks "the old one was better".

3.7.5. Online fraud with webinos payment API

Threat	Cross Site Request Forgery
Vulnerability	Session Fixation
Rating	Intolerable

3.7.5.1 Shopping Misuse Case I: The delivery of a free festival guide for a charge

Ethan has found festival information that is for free. He wants to gather people's credit card information to use it for a later opportunity by using barcodes. He also wants to charge visitors for the free guide through barcode interaction. Peter is about to become a victim of Ethan's con.

Peter is on a business travel, and has combined his trip with a four-star hotel stay in the weekend to relax. Peter picks up the festival leaflet and scans the barcode with his mobile. A web page is loaded in the mobile browser. It asks if Peter would like access to the festival guide. Peter adds the festival guide to the shopping basket and proceeds to checkout. He fills in credit card information and pays Euro 3.5. Upon completion, a web page asks Peter if he would like to add the festival guide to his favourites. He answers yes, and starts to use the guide that actually was for free.

Ethan achieved a micro-payment + Peter's credit card information. Peter is happy and completely unaware of what Ethan might want to do next in the main con.

3.7.5.2 Shopping Misuse Case II: The payment for a service that never will be delivered

Ethan has made a new master con act. It is based on making the victims to feel very good and even be aware of the payment. It uses barcodes, a web browser, and the webinos payment API to perform the payment.

Jessica has found a smart poster with information about a charity working with children with malaria. She gains interest for it and scans the barcode with her mobile to obtain more information. The web page asks her if she would like to donate Euro 10 by sending a text message to Ethan's premium sms service. She answers yes, fills in her email, and a text message is automatically sent to the service through the webinos payment API. She browses the information about malaria, feels good, and happily receives the payment on her mobile phone bill the next month.

Jessica doesn't know that Ethan will use the donation fully by himself. Ethan will also use the mobile number and her email address in the future.

3.7.6. Overlay network facilitated relay attack

Threat	NFC relay attack
Vulnerability	System data trust
Rating	Tolerable

3.7.6.1 Context and Events *Misuse Case*

As Alice was walking away from the bar with her drinks, she narrowly avoided dropping one of her glasses as man brushed past her. "Sorry", he mumbled as he walked briskly towards the toilets.

David devised a new scam which took advantage of the recent take-off of NFC based mobile payment, and the new webinos platform that could link different apps and devices together. The scam involved dropping a leech mobile phone into someone's bag which contained a webinos enabled NFC phone. The leech would attempt to get the victim's phone to join his personal zone which, David estimated, would not be too difficult. Once in place, David could then purchase things via NFC, while webinos routed the request to the victim's NFC reader via the personal zone overlay network. David tinkered around with different devices, settings, and applications, and was quite surprised at how easy this scam appeared to be. Consequently, he would need to make the most use of this exploit quickly before other people got in on the act.

David's plan was to find somewhere where there would be lots of young but unsuspecting people who might not notice something being put into their bags. David decided a nightclub on a Friday night would be a good bet. As David entered the club at shortly after midnight, he noticed a large group of people mingling near the bar. As he approached, he noticed a large

women trying to carry multiple drinks with a hand-bag slung around her shoulder. Confidently, with his leech device in hand, David walked towards this woman.

3.7.7. Playback service accountability issue

Threat	Dictionary attack
Vulnerability	Weak credential
Rating	Undesirable

3.7.7.1 Home Media and Interactive TV Misuse Case

Alice likes very much her new webinos enabled TV, because when away from home she can watch subscribed pay TV channels on the notebook or smartphone. But the TV is protected with a weak password, so Ethan can easily access Alice's TV and retransmit the pay TV signal via internet to some friend, asking for a fee much lower than the original one.

3.7.8. Steal Webinos session

Threat	Cross Site Request Forgery
Vulnerability	Session Fixation
Rating	Tolerable

3.7.8.1 Profile Management Misuse Case

As a new source of income, Ethan has opened an account with an affiliate stock photo service. Ethan carries out some rudimentary google hacking to identify forums that might be open to stored XSS vulnerabilities. Eventually, Ethan finds a forum that is used by a Webinos enabled camera app that synchronises images with a cloud based photo sharing service.

Ethan develops an XSS/CSRF exploit by loading malicious code into the application's blog page. On viewing the blog, the script obtains the Webinos session data and, via some local and external javascript and php, sends the session data to another site which uses the Webinos APIs, close a device's session, re-opens the session to the device, obtains the images, and submits these to the affiliate stock photo service using the service providers web services API. Ethan realises the exploit might only work on certain devices, but he thinks that something is better than nothing...

Several days later, Helen is taking some snaps of her family at home using a recently downloaded camera application that syncs her taken images to the cloud based provider. After taking a few pictures around the garden, Helen browses the community developed help data in the application. Helen doesn't realise that, by checking this help data, her family photos are about to net Ethan some additional income.

3.7.9. Unauthorized access to sensitive data

Threat	Autologin abuse
Vulnerability	Automatic login, Improper privacy protection
Rating	Undesirable

3.7.9.1 Home Media and Interactive TV Misuse Case

Gloria is at Alice home. Later they will watch a movie with friends on the new Alice's webinos enabled TV.

Alice is in the kitchen to prepare popcorn. Waiting for others to come, Gloria uses her own webinos enabled mobile to access Alice's TV. She wants to receive on her mobile the original language audio stream. Browsing TV options he finds unprotected Alice's sensitive data: CC number used to pay "pay per view" services, history of recently accessed channels and services, video recording programming, etc.

When Alice is back in the living room with the popcorn, Gloria warns her about the privacy problem he discovered.

3.7.10. Unprotected transmission

Threat	Network eavesdropping
Vulnerability	Improper privacy protection, Unencrypted data transmission
Rating	Intolerable

3.7.10.1 Navigation Misuse Case

Justin books a hotel room using his web TV, and webinos creates a calendar entry about this holiday.

The Web TV's PZP sends the calendar entry to the PZH, which synchronizes the calendar with other nearby Justin's devices via WiFi. Frankie in the neighbourhood is eavesdropping unprotected WiFi communications, and now he knows when Justin's house will be clear...

3.7.11. Untrusted car mechanic

Threat	Cryptanalysis, Personal Zone Subversion
Vulnerability	Improper privacy protection, Weak cryptography
Rating	Tolerable

3.7.11.1 Navigation Misuse Case

Justin takes his car to the machine shop for maintenance. The access to the in-car system is password protected. David removes the mass memory device and makes a copy of the content to look for CC numbers and other attractive data. The data encryption algorithm is weak, and David breaks it.

In the PZP cache David finds Justin's personal zone credentials. David earns some money selling them to Ethan, who can use these credentials to control the Justin's personal zone and use it in his botnet.

3.7.12. Use of other people's service

Threat	Autologin abuse, PZH access abuse, Session hijacking
Vulnerability	Automatic login, Improper timeout, Improper privacy protection, PZH unprotected access
Rating	Undesirable

3.7.12.1 Navigation Misuse Case

Justin gives Frankie, the parking attendant, car keys to park it.

Frankie at the moment has not other customers, so he decides to fiddle with the in-car system. The computer requires no authentication so he can enter and nose about navigation history. He realizes that the web browser is logged in a music service with fee. He listens to the music waiting for the next motorist coming.

After listening few songs, he uses his own webinos enabled smartphone to get the Justin's personal zone device list via Justin's PZH. From the list he selects the in-car system. When on the in-car system touch screen appears the confirmation dialog box, he taps on OK and the devices are now connected. Frankie can exit from the car and access Justin's music service form his own smartphone.

When Justin comes back to the parking, Frankie disconnects the smartphone form the music service and from Justin's personal zone and then brings back the car to the owner.

3.8. Recommendations

In this section, we propose responses to each of the previously defined risks. In some cases, these risks are already partially or fully mitigated by the webinos architecture.

3.8.1. Capture hidden analytics

Mitigating against the Spyware threat is difficult because Jimmy's knowledge of the application is such that information about context can be sought via others means. It is, however, possible to mitigate this risk by responding to the lack of data provenance vulnerability. This requires adding an access control mechanism to the context data store that is sufficiently fine grained that it can distinguish between types of device context data. While the webinos context model supports this distinction, the current model appears to be focused on how users (as opposed to developers) exploit context.

3.8.2. Control cloud-based PZH

Although steps have been taken to mitigate against man-in-the-middle attacks on webinos processes, it is difficult to mitigate against all such attacks on the environment where a PZH is running. It is, however, possible to prevent or deter attacks that exploit the vulnerability by stipulating requirements for hosts that run PZH. Consequently, future revisions to the webinos architecture should pay due attention to the environmental expectations for devices that host PZHs.

3.8.3. Exploit network bandwidth

Like the previous risk, it is difficult to mitigate against threats that are launched on devices that have already been compromised. However, applying the webinos Attestation API might form the basis of a control that can detect unauthorised changes to customisable preferences. Such a control can be implemented by individual app developers, although a service of this nature may be useful enough to warrant additional functionality as part of the webinos runtime.

3.8.4. Multimedia stream availability problem

This is basically a configuration problem, the "autologin abuse" threat can be overcome by denying the possibility to use the autologin. Nowadays may not be evident to a user why a TV requires an explicit authentication, so the temptation to use the autologin might be strong. The "unlimited clients number" vulnerability can be addressed by webinos runtime checking available resources (when it's possible) before to allow new clients.

3.8.5. Online fraud with webinos payment API

Both the risk, and the remaining risks in this section, are important because they highlight vulnerabilities in the ecosystem that webinos is part of. In particular, affordances that webinos can take advantage of can also be exploited by attackers. At this point of time, there is no specific mitigation strategy for responding to this risk. If webinos encompassed app stores as well as applications then recommendation systems may be one way of mitigating this threat. Unfortunately, as a risk mitigation strategy this may not be sustainable given recent reports of malware on the Android app store. Consequently, at the time of writing, this risk remains unmitigated.

3.8.6. Overlay network facilitated attack

Although the basis of this risk precede webinos, the overlay network makes this attack easier to perform and, by extension, more likely to occur. At this stage, we propose mitigating this risk by focusing on the vulnerability. This entails making manual authentication mandatory when a new device joins a personal zone.

3.8.7. Playback service accountability issue

Webinos fosters the usage of strong passwords or stronger authentications methods. Credentials are stored and managed by the PZH, so the usage of public key certificates and complex passwords is made easier. A possible weak point is the PZH keyring unlock. It would be useless to have strong credentials protected with a weak password.

3.8.8. Steal webinos session

Mitigating this risk by dealing with the threat alone is challenging without impacting the usability of developers, i.e. integrating controls into APIs or other developer tools. Therefore, a short term way of mitigating this risk is by focusing on improving webinos sessions to reduce the criticality of the vulnerability. One strategy involves mandating expiry dates/time for webinos sessions. However, whether implementing this or any other session based control will depend on where the control should be implemented, i.e. within the core webinos runtime, as part of the API, or as a mandated developer practice. Consequently, this control needs to be considered in more detail when a specification for webinos sessions is made available.

3.8.9. Unauthorized access to sensitive data

The "autologin abuse" issue can be addressed like in the "multimedia stream availability problem" misuse case, but to deny the autologin may not be enough. An additional level of authentication may be required to protect sensitive data (e.g. CC numbers), because the user can watch TV with other people, who is not intended to access these data.

3.8.10. Unprotected transmission

Transmissions encryption should be used as much as possible, especially for wireless ones. Devices should use strong encryption algorithms, compatible with their hardware resources.

3.8.11. Untrusted car mechanic

Mass memories should be encrypted using strong algorithms. A possible alternative is to have a strong encryption only on PZH and keep the PZP cache (which contains most sensitive data) exclusively in volatile memory. This solution is less secure than the previous one, and if the PZH is unavailable at the device startup it is impossible to use the PZP as fall-back, because the PZP cache is empty.

3.8.12. Use of other people's service

Like in the "multimedia stream availability problem" misuse case, the autologin should be denied.

As for TV, even for in-car navigation and entertainment systems may not be evident to a user why an explicit authentication is required, so the idea to enable the autologin can be very attractive.

Another thing that might be useful to do, is to protect the PZH access, in order that only authorized people can retrieve the device list.

There are also non-webinos solutions.

Developers can address the "improper timeout" vulnerability automatically closing sessions after some time of inactivity.

Car manufacturers may expand valet keys functionalities. Nowadays some car manufacturer provides a valet key, to give the parking attendant, that can be used to enter the vehicle and to start it, but can't be used to open the boot or the glove compartment. We can envisage a webinos enabled car with a valet key which can start the engine but can't start the navigation and entertainment systems.

4 Experiments

4.1. Overview

Research approaches in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) tend to focus on evaluating the usability of a design artefact. However, as indicated in the related work section, usability is also important for the artefact's designer as well as the artefact itself. This is particularly important for webinos, whose end-users may include developers as well as consumers. It is recognised that making the jump from design data to design is a difficult problem, but some argue that this is a creativity and sense-making issue rather than a research problem per se (BEHO1998). Nonetheless, the HCI research community agrees that methodology research in design is immature (CACO2008).

Recent work by Zimmerman et al. (ZIFO2007) has attempted to draw together the different perceptions of design held by the HCI community. They propose a model of research through design, where interaction designers integrate *true* models and theories from behavioural science with the *how* knowledge afforded by engineering innovations. All these explorations are grounded in *real* knowledge produced by field researchers. It is this model that forms the inspiration for the experimental research approach in this deliverable, both for the focus groups and the questionnaire. In particular, problems and issues arising in other webinos deliverables will be re-framed as research questions that can be examined. The results that arise from this research then form the basis of technical opportunities for re-informing revisions to the webinos architecture, or on-going work towards Workpackages 4 and 5.

4.2. Categorising Security & Privacy Policies

For a policy management tool to be usable then concepts like subjects, targets, rules, policies, and policy sets need to be understood by people who need to make decisions about them. Unfortunately, coming up with synonyms for these concepts is only one part of the problem because these also need to be categorised in a way which is meaningful for making decisions. This raises the question of what groupings might be meaningful to different policy stakeholders, and hows should be designed to make optimum use of these.

During our initial investigation into the security and privacy expectations of webinos users and developers, several personas were developed. These personas are not, however, data-driven; they are grounded argumentatively in the assumptions that the webinos project team were making about different types of users. As such, although these personas provide useful guidelines for thinking about how different users might reason about existing security controls,

they provide few clues about possible innovation which might make security and privacy decisions easier for the corresponding users to make.

The objective of this experiment is to understand what factors impact the categorisation and grouping of security and privacy policy concepts in multiple contexts. Insights from this experiment will be used to inform the information architecture of webinos policy management tools.

4.2.1. Focus Group Methodology

This experiment was carried out using a focus group research methodology. Focus groups are carefully planned discussions, which are designed to obtain the perceptions of group members around a design problem (KOB2008). Focus groups participants are selected based on their individual characteristics relating to a given topic, where each session is guided by a facilitator to ensure that discussion activities remain focused. The outcome of a focus group research method is a report of themes which appear to have emerged throughout the sessions. These themes may be have been agreed by the participants, although they might have also emerged from qualitative data analysis of session transcripts.

Although focus groups are a widely used research method, they suffer from two particular weaknesses. First, group dynamics can undermine the flow of the focus group design. Second, small sample sizes make it difficult to generalise results.

We propose mitigating these weaknesses in two ways. First, a participative design activity will be used to channel the contributions made by participants. This activity will involve carrying out an affinity diagramming exercise for a specific design problem (BRAS1996). This technique involves capturing data items contributed by participants and consolidating these points into groups that are meaningful to participants. The affinity diagramming technique was chosen because it ensures that the constraints of the activity do not constrain the input provided by participants about the research problem; more details about how affinity diagramming is applied are described later in this section. Second, to provide some measure of triangulation, 3 focus groups will be held for 3 different user categories, and 3 sessions will be held for each user category; 3-4 participants will take part in each session.

Each focus group session was divided into 5 stages:

- Stage 1: Introductions: Introduction to webinos and the design exercise background. 10 minutes
- Stage 2: Object clustering: affinity diagramming for security and privacy sensitive information associated with the webinos proposition presented. 20 minutes

- Stage 3: Subject clustering: A continuation of the affinity diagramming exercise to incorporate subjects which should or should not access the sensitive information. 30 minutes
- Stage 4: Context clustering: A continuation of the affinity diagramming exercise to explore the impact of context on the identified clusters. 20 minutes
- Stage 5: Debrief: A walkthrough of the developed model, and a short discussion about how the participants found the exercise. 10 minutes

There was also a 10 minute break between stages 3 and 4.

In the following sections, we describe the approach taken.

4.2.1.1 Setup material

In addition to a meeting room, the following items were required for each session:

- 1 lead facilitator and, where possible, 1 assistant
- 1 whiteboard or vertical surface
- black, green, red, and blue marker pens (2 of each)
- a flip chart
- 400 Yellow post-it notes
- 100 Orange post-it notes
- 100 Green post-it notes
- 100 Red post-it notes
- 100 Light blue post-it notes
- 1/2 video cameras
- 1 camera for taking shots of the affinity diagram and participant groups at various stages
- 1 projector and PC/laptop
- Refreshments for the break between stages 3 and 4

These numbers assume that a pack of post-it notes contain 100 individual notes. Each participant was given an individual yellow post-it note pad, and the group had access to post-it notes for the other colours.

There are no specific requirement for room setup, although at least one table and some chairs are required made available for the participants to sit at the beginning and end of each session. The table also acts as a surface for paraphernalia such as post-it notes, pens, paper, blue tac, etc

A video camera was carefully placed to give optimal coverage of the board that much of the group activity will be centred around.

Informed consent forms were also given to participants on arrival and signed before stage 1 is concluded.

The projector and accompanying PC and laptop was primarily used for projecting the briefs for stage 1. The briefs for the other stages were delivered verbally.

4.2.1.2 Participant recruitment

The user categories selected for this experiment were based on the personas created in WP 2.7, where each characterises a set of archetypical behaviours associated with each type of potential webinos user. User-centered design best practice indicates that rather than designing for all possible users, we should instead design with a limited number of users in mind. This leads to a cleaner conceptual and information architecture which may also be useful for the larger user population.

The selection criteria for each prospective participant was based on the characteristics of the associated persona. Because the dynamics associated with the group forming process may influence the results of each session, snowball sampling was used to recruit participants already acquainted with other participants.

4.2.1.3 Exercise scenario

The sessions for each category was based around a different scenario, where each is a webinos proposition of value to the participants. Although the scenarios were informed by other webinos artifacts, such as the personas in WP 2.7, the target platforms in WP 2.6, and the value propositions in WP 5, these were written from a first person perspective, i.e. participants were expected to think about how they, rather than others, would approach the scenario.

The scenario was developed throughout stages 1 – 4 of the session. In the first stage, the proposition itself was introduced, together with its potential. In the second phase, the opening stages of the scenario were presented together with a pre-amble for the object clustering exercise. In the third stage, the scenario was developed to incorporate the need for clustering to be informed by what subjects can and can't have access to. In the fourth stage, the scenario is developed to explore the impact of context on the pre-existing clusters.

4.2.1.4 Stage 1: Introductions

Participants were briefly introduced to the webinos project using the webinos video. Following this, they were presented with the general artifact around which the exercise scenario is based. As the proposition this was based on didn't exist then screenshots / mockups were used to illustrate this system. The facilitator emphasised the need for participants to appreciate the potential of this system before moving on, and responded to any clarifying questions that the participants had about the proposition, and how webinos facilitated it.

As most participants has not have encountered affinity diagramming before, an example of what these look like and how they are constructed was also presented.

Time wise, this stage took around 10 minutes, i.e. 2.5 mins for the webinos movie, 3 mins for the scenario presentation, 3 mins for an overview of affinity diagramming, and 1.5 minutes for a short question and answer session.

4.2.1.5 Stage 2: Object clustering

In the second part, the participants were presented with the scenario and the first part of the exercise to be carried out. The brief was read to participants, following which a yellow post-it note was issued to each participant.

Using the yellow post-it notes provided, participants wrote items they felt were important and affixed them to the whiteboard. This started as an individual exercise, but participants eventually started discussing concepts and how they relate to the scenario. Facilitator intervention was occasionally required to clarify some of the finer points of affinity diagramming. In some cases, the facilitator also intervened when orphaned concepts were found that were not part of another group of concepts. 20 minutes were nominally set aside for this stage.

4.2.1.6 Stage 3: Subject clustering

In the third part, participants were asked to think about who or what should or should not be allowed to access this data; these agent names were written on green and red post-it notes respectively and added to the white-board. This entailed grouping the items according to what should and should not be allowed for each agent and re-clustering accordingly. This allowed participants to consider the other clusters while, simultaneously, re-using the yellow post-it notes and making opportune use of the available whiteboard real estate. At the end of each subject affinity diagramming exercise, a photo was taken of each diagram and uploaded to a laptop; this allowed participants to review them if they and when they felt this was necessary.

At the end of stage 3 there was a short break during which time no audio and video recording is made.

4.2.1.7 *Stage 4: Context clustering*

In the fourth part, participants were asked to think about the impact that context might have on how data is accessed and by whom. Participants wrote physical, social, or cultural context names on light blue post-it notes and, like the previous part, show the relationship this has to the current model on the board.

4.2.1.8 *Stage 5: Debrief*

The final stage was broken down into two parts. In the first part, the participants are invited to walkthrough the context affinity model. This was primarily a sanity check to ensure that everyone in the group understood the model and was clear enough that it could be explained to someone else. In the second part, the facilitator led a short debrief session to discuss how the participants found the design session and the issues discussed in general.

4.2.1.9 *Analysis and reports*

Session organisers were responsible for managing the audio and visual data created during each session. At the end of each session, the organisers prepared a short report summarising the outcome of the session and the main themes emerging from the models and the associated discussions. Once all the sessions had been completed, the focus group reports was qualitatively analysed using Grounded Theory (COST2008) to identify emerging themes around the around the original research questions.

4.2.2. Results

4.2.2.1 Helen

4.2.2.1.1 Helen Focus Group 1

4.2.2.1.1.1 Session background

The session was held at Oxford on Thursday, 21st July between 1030 and 1240, and was based around the **Helen** persona.

The session was run with 3 participants. Each participant was a researcher at the University of Oxford and also the father of one or more young (pre-teen) children. Each participant was recruited directly by the session organiser.

4.2.2.1.1.2 Results

4.2.2.1.1.2.1 Object clustering

From the outset, it was clear that the different participants brought different expectations as parents; the ages of each participants child/children varied slightly, and one of the participants had multiple children. Nonetheless, it was interesting to see how, during the brain-storming for concepts, concepts were elicited based on personal anecdotes. For example, one participant highlighted said he wanted the system to foster the sense that his daughters were in control of the entertainment system, even though they weren't.

As this stage progressed, the potential capabilities of both the system and webinos led to "scope creep" in two senses. In the first sense, the participants began to imagine how other children or other people might envisage the system. Even though the scenario was explicitly about a family trip, occasionally participants generalised discussions around a concept by stating "if you are going on holiday..." In the second sense, the scope of the system considered was expanded to consider interfaces to other systems. The example one participant suggested was an interface to a webinos-powered home surveillance system, which would allow the passengers to check-up on their pets while on the move.

4.2.2.1.1.2.2 Subject clustering

The following subjects were elicited during the initial brainstorming at the beginning of this stage: children, grandparents, cousins, uncles & aunts, school teachers, GPs, friends, and classmates. Of these initial subjects, children, grandparents, and classmates were analysed. Cousins and uncles/aunts were not considered because the participants could not come up with a consensus of how the model for these stakeholders might be different from grand-parents. Following this discussion, school teachers and GPs were dropped as concepts, and it was decided to consider classmates as the participants felt these issues were also the same for non-school friends.

Although there were slight variations in permissiveness with respect to participants and their children, there was a general consensus about what their children should be allowed access to. However, while clusters began to form around the allowed section of the board, concepts which were disallowed tended to be bunched to one side. It was only after explicit intervention that the participants came up with rather generic categories for disallowed concepts.

At this stage it was also noted that grouping concepts into categories led to the elicitation of new concepts. Some of these were concepts which intersected with other categories; in these cases, the same concept was added to each different category. Other concepts, when added, led

to a discussion about the concepts location, and whether the category itself should be allowed or disallowed. For example, when the social networking category was identified within the allowed section, one participant said that a "Facebook" concept was missing. However, another participant said that the children were too young to use Facebook; this led to a discussion about whether it should be assumed that children are going to be 3 or 4 forever.

A general "interface" category formed at this stage; concepts under this category would remain unchanged for both the other subject affinity diagrams and during context affinity diagramming.

Shortly after moving onto considering the grandparents subject, one of the participants swapped the green and red post-it notes signifying the allowed and disallowed parts of the white-board respectively. This swap was proposed because, it was argued, with the exception of one or two concepts, all other concepts should be disallowed for grand-parents. As the participants spent more time looking at this subject, more concepts and categories moved from dis-allowed to allowed (and vice-versa) although, in one or two cases after subsequent discussion, some concepts were moved back to their originating part of the board. For example, one participant argued that buying applications should be dis-allowed for grandparents as this was something that parents should do. However, another participant argued that grandparents

can buy applications, but parents can chose whether the application should be allowed to be installed or not. Consequently, this concept was moved back to the allowed category.

As indicated at the start of this section, much of the initial discussion revolved around the similarities between class-mates, friends, and cousins. However, even when settling on class mates as a subject, there was still debate about how this should be interpreted. For example, choosing where to situate the "Work on homework" concept led to a discussion about how classmates are interpreted. From the resulting discussion, it was apparent that the participants may be viewing this subject from their own perspective as ex-school children, rather than that of classmates of their own children.

During this stage, two other observations were made which were common across the subject affinity diagramming exercise. First, when moving concepts between allowed and dis-allowed

areas, it was common for the entire category to move rather than a single concept. Second, a lot of discussion around concepts occurred because it wasn't clear to participants whether concepts related to data or processes. For example, when choosing how shared content should be situated, there was some debate about whether this concept referred to data or shared running applications. Consequently, an additional concept was added to acknowledge this distinction.

4.2.2.1.1.2.3 *Context clustering*

As for subject clustering, this stage began with a discussion about some of the subtle variations between contexts. The contexts that were initially elicited were a typical family trip, a hired car, loan of one's car, giving a lift to friends, car sharing, a multiple-car journey.

As the typical family trip context had been implicitly explored in previous stage, participants originally agreed to explore the car sharing context. However, after exploring the context in more detail, nuances in the context, subjects, and objects meant that the group found agreeing any consensus difficult. As a result, it was agreed to instead explore a context where friends took their respective families on a multi-car journey, even though this context was not without its nuances. For example, there was uncertainty about whether the friends of children in each car should be allowed to engage in multi-player games with children in another car.

It was noted that much of the discussion in this stage appeared to be centred around the context of the car, rather than the in-car entertainment system. This was apparent from the initial discussions which established a shared understanding of the context itself. During this discussion, the whiteboard was useful for sketching ideas related to this context.

4.2.2.1.1.3 Discussion

During the de-brief session, participants agreed that context was an ever-present part of the exercise, even though it was only explicitly applied in the final stage of the session. In particular, exploring the finer detail of a particular context led to equally fine grained exploration of the subjects and objects within in. This often led to misinterpretations about objects, subjects, or contexts being surfaced when objects were moved from either the allowed or dis-allowed sections of the board, or vice-versa.

4.2.2.1.1.3.1 Orthogonal subject groups

The initial discussion during the elicitation of subjects in the subject clustering stage indicated that the value placed by participants in different family groups does not map simply to authority levels from a security policy perspective. As such, the subjects could, theoretically, be grouped orthogonally to those used to control data access.

4.2.2.1.1.3.2 Ad-hoc concept elicitation

Subject clustering demonstrated that lots of concepts arise on-the-fly. Policy management tools that categorise objects should support a facility for allowing the ad-hoc entry of previously undefined objects.

4.2.2.1.1.3.3 Exclusive allow/dis-allow focus

The subject clustering exercise also showed that, any one time, participants tend to focus on either allowed or dis-allowed subjects. Context switching from one to other tends to occur only when categories are moved and, when this occurs, this precipitates thinking about categories across both allowed and dis-allowed areas.

4.2.2.1.1.3.4 Support material for policies

The use of the white-board to elucidate the elements of the context suggests that supplemental material might be useful for explaining a policy context's rationale to others. An example of this sort of material might be an explanatory diagram.

4.2.2.1.1.3.5 Scope creep

An unfortunate corollary of brain-storming is that ideas can be identified which can lead to thinking beyond the scope of a designed system. As the exercise progressed through the stages, this problem became increasingly obviously, culminating in problems exploring the initially

selected context in the context clustering stage. As striking a balance is difficult to do without stifling the ideation process, it would be useful to explore whether better matching participants with the problem scenario might mitigate this problem.

4.2.2.1.2 Helen Focus Group 2

4.2.2.1.2.1 *Session background*

The session was held at Polito on Tuesday 26th July between 1900 and 2100, and was based around Helen persona.

The session was run with 3 participants:

- a physicist, father two children, the first one 4 years old and the second one 1 year old
- a software designer, father of two children, the first one 3 years old and the second one 2 months old
- a LAN designer, father of two children, the first one 2 years old and the second one 2 months old

Each participant was recruited directly by the session organiser.

4.2.2.1.2.2 Results

4.2.2.1.2.2.1 Object clustering

Despite opening recommendations, participants preferred to start thinking to clusters, and then tried to fill them. Their first idea was to use an "inside car" and an "outside car" cluster. However this surfaced the problem of online contents or services which can be used inside the car but are hosted outside. Consequently they put aside these clusters and distinguished between data storage and use.

Thinking to the problem of user observability and data aggregation when using a content or a service, they discerned between user request and user behaviour. They introduced the wanted and unwanted observer and this led them to the "agents" cluster, bringing forward some work of the subject clustering step.

Participants introduced the concept of user profile: a subset of user data, selected by the user himself, used to decide which data to show to agents. The user may have a different profile for each agent.

Participants thought to "reliability problems" as a broad concept, encompassing device reliability and agent reliability.

At this step participants generalized contents and services considering them the same.

4.2.2.1.2.2.2 Subject clustering

Participants took the "family and friends" and the "service provider" elements from the agent cluster of the previous step. Then they split "family and friends" among "parent", "child" whereas relatives and friends are generalized as "trustworthy person"

They introduced many missing concepts as communications, multimedia, and on-line shopping. Participants thought to the possibility to locate children via device (e.g. mobile) georeference if they lose them at a stopover, and for the children the possibility to locate parents. The LAN designer would preferred a matrix or grid scheme, while the software designer would like best the possibility to define access rules for each object (something like an access control list). This proves that there is no a mechanism better then another, but the choice is influenced by user habit and experience.

Thinking to the "trustworthy person" subject, participants extended their profile idea, including access control rules. The car owner/in-car system admin, can set up a profile customising user permissions.

4.2.2.1.2.2.3 Context clustering

Participants focused on looking for new subjects who can access the car, more than contexts. They decided that the "family" context is the one covering the previous work, so everything in this context is unmodified.

Then participants thought to subjects whom the car owner can give a ride, from a friend (trustworthy person) to a hitchhiker. They decided to collapse this in the "family and guest" context, because they think to have (or build themselves) a different profile for each category. In this step the profile idea is extended further up to encompass the idea of user account. I.e. the in-car system admin can create a profile for a guest, and then the guest can authenticate himself and access to a subset of the in-car system.

Finally they introduced the "stranger" context, thinking to people without a user profile, e.g. a mechanic. Participants first idea was to deny any access, then thinking to the possibility to call emergency numbers using other people mobile, they decided to allow access to public services and public data.

Participants thought to contexts as sets of subjects, and in their idea contexts can be hierarchically sorted based on privacy level. For example they may have a high level context with relatives as subjects and where there is the minimum level of privacy, an intermediate level context, with family and friends and higher level of privacy, and a low level context with

strangers and the maximum level of privacy.

The profile should help them to decide how much information disclose at which context level.

4.2.2.1.2.3 Discussion

They seemed non exactly focused with their current step. They introduced subjects in object clustering step, and then spent most time thinking to objects in subject clustering step and to other subjects in context clustering step.

In the object clustering step they introduced a generalization considering contents and services as a single object. In the subject clustering step they became aware of the trust transfer problem and split contents and services in new objects.

In the subject clustering step they introduced the "trustworthy person". This is not a real role but an entity defined by a property (the property to be trusted, and then to have more access rights than an untrusted person) and this can lead to ambiguity.

In the context clustering step they were a bit tired and spent time to look for an easier way to do the exercise, probably because them did not comply with time limits at any step.

The LAN designer and the software designer face security-related problems in their daily work.

4.2.2.1.3 Helen Focus Group 3

4.2.2.1.3.1 Session background

The focus group interview was held at Fraunhofer-Institute for Open Communication Systems (FOKUS) on Thursday 4th August between 1100 and 1300, and was based around Helen persona. The interview was run with 3 participants:

- a student of Technische Universität Berlin, master degree in computer science, father of one child 1 month old
- a software developer, father of two children, the first one 5 years old and the second one 4 months old
- a research associate, father of two children, the first one 2 years old and the second one 1 month old

Each participant was recruited directly by the session organiser.

4.2.2.1.3.2 Results

4.2.2.1.3.2.1 Object clustering

This phase started with an introduction by the facilitator. He presented some helpful hints regarding ICT aspects of such a home entertainment system. The participants started to cluster concepts for devices, data that is processed by the system, applications and features as well as commercial applications like an entertainment or media store. Without this introduction about ICT aspects participants had some difficulties to start brainstorming and thinking about potential concepts. One discussion point was how such a system should support telephone features because it is already supported by the embedded operating system of the car. However the system is fully integrated and connected via 4G therefore the participants decided that the system supports a feature set for calls and messaging. Summing up the participants identified various applications around audio, video, games, web and shopping based on device features like smartphone, display, camera, 4G, navigation, storage and input facilities.

4.2.2.1.3.2.2 Subject clustering

The subject clustering was started with a brainstorming session about subject clusters. Participants had written down various subjects which can interact with the system. Afterwards subjects were sorted by relevance. Facilitator and participants decided to use children, home sharing server (HSS) and content provider as relevant subjects for the next step. Participants thought that this is a good mixture between persons who can interact with the system and software systems. It is noted that the home sharing server is to be understood as media library in the household of the end user.

Subject cluster children

The first cluster were children and their user behavior regarding limited access to applications, content and devices. Participants argued that the access to shopping features like booking, app store, marketplaces and download sites should be restricted. With the background that they offer paid and for children restricted content. Furthermore features like navigation, telephone and emergency call should be reserved for parents. On the other hand children should have the possibility to play games and interact with friends via chat or instant messaging.

Subject cluster HSS

The home sharing server (HSS) is located in household of the end user and is connected via 4G with the home entertainment system in the car. To stream content between this two systems it is necessary that both have full access to each other including devices like display, camera, smartphone and human interfaces. Based on the idea of a media library as the HSS participants discussed that the access to navigation app, traffic data, emergency call, telephone features and location data should be restricted.

Subject cluster content provider

Content providers were reflected as last cluster in the subject clustering phase. Participants came to the conclusion that content providers doesn't have access to private data on devices like chat, video conferences and calls. Furthermore control data for navigation and emergency systems should be not accessible by 3rd party services. From the perspective of providers participants argued that content providers are the owner of content therefore they have full

control concerning merchadising, presentation, cost models, access on devices, human interface device support and advertisement.

4.2.2.1.3.2.3 Context clustering

The participants introduced car sharing as concept in the context clusering phase. In this concept the car will be lent to other persons which implies not that they are friends or family members. With the advantage that the concept has more restrictions for the potential diver of such a shared car. Furthermore the concept takles current debates regarding urban mobility.

Context cluster content provider

Regarding re-clustering for content provider participants came to similar results. Private content is restricted for content providers also in the case if a car will be lent. This include a cloud-based user management system which supports several user profiles on the home entertainment system. The user will be detected via an authorization facility.

Context cluster HSS

For HSS the decision was very simple. The HSS is connected with a user profile therefore an external 3rd party user has no access to the entire media library including HSS features.

Context cluster children

In the case of children participants find the same situation as during subject clustering. The access to devices and content is restricted for children. Participants couldn't find any differences if the car will be lent to another family. Based on the background that the family has an user account for the cloud-based home entertainment system.

4.2.2.1.3.3 Discussion

In comparison to the Clara focus group participants were obviously more motivated during three phases of clustering. In retrospect participants had problems to find the right starting point at the beginning of object clustering. Missing ideas and imagination were the main problems. The facilitator introduced object clustering via helpful hints. With the disadvantage that he introduced already known concepts like information flow, devices, applications, features, etc.

For object clustering participants identified various applications around audio, video, games, web and shopping based on device features like smartphone, display, camera, 4G, navigation, storage and input facilities. Concepts like children, home sharing system (HSS) as external service and content provider were introduced. In the case of context clustering participants couldn't identify significant differences in comparison to the subject clustering.

4.2.2.2 Jimmy

4.2.2.2.1 Jimmy Focus Group 1

4.2.2.2.1.1 Session background

The session was held at Oxford on Thursday, 19th July between 1030 and 1220, and was based around the Jimmy persona.

The session was run with 3 participants. Each participant was a software engineer employed by the University of Oxford; collectively, the participants developed and maintained the Software Engineering web-site the exercise scenario was built around. Each participant was recruited directly by the session organiser.

4.2.2.2.1.2 *Results*

4.2.2.2.1.2.1 *Object clustering*

Rather than carrying out unstructured ideation, the participants seemed to follow a rigorous process for identifying core concepts, but going through the "who"s and the "what"s associated with the system. This was apparent when, after identifying some initial concepts, one

participant noted that they had elicited the "who"s, so it now it was time to start eliciting the "what"s. Later in this stage, another participant drew analogies between this exercise, data modelling, and concept modelling using UML.

In the first half of this stage, the elicited concepts seemed to be focused on the intrinsics of course management rather than the possibilities afforded by webinos and mobile web-apps. When the participants were encouraged to start grouping concepts then a number of new concepts were identified. However, rather than thinking outside the box, the group appeared to spend more time introspecting on the intrinsic nature of the concepts themselves and possible attributes.

Towards the end of this stage, it was noticed that one concept, transcript, was isolated from the other clusters. When challenging about this, the group discussed how this concept fitted in with the categories that already existed, rather than considering how the concept challenged (or led to a rethink about) the pre-existing categories.

4.2.2.2.1.2.2 *Subject clustering*

At the beginning of the session, 10 subjects were elicited: course attendee, potential attendee, observer, lecturer, TA, administrator, examiner, "assignment only" student, moderator, cancelled participant. Due to time constraints, there was only time to explore 3 of these: course attendees, potential attendees, and administrators.

During the course attendee affinity diagramming, it was noted that general categories began to emerge during the grouping of concepts rather than after. For the allow section, these were primarily based around concepts that needed to be modified, "need to know", and "nice to know" concepts. Initially, "disallow" concepts were grouped together but, when challenged, these were grouped into "don't need to know" and "not allowed to know" categories.

During the object clustering stage, a general functionality concept emerged for what were perceived to be general administration concepts, e.g. schedules, calendars, reminders, etc. This cluster remained unchanged for both the subject and context clustering stage of the exercise, although whether this category was situated in an allow or disallow section varied based on the subject or subject/context combination.

The concept groupings were different for the potential attendee affinity diagram, and there was some movement of concepts between the allow and disallow sections of the board. In a number of cases, when moving one concept, participants noticed other concepts in the same or nearby categories which needed to be moved as well. However, rather than choosing categories for emergent groups of concepts, the participants instead grouped concepts by pre-existing category names. One of the consequences of this was a tendency to restrict thinking about concepts in terms of this rigid set of categories. For example, when moving the one concept, a participant queried whether this should be a 'need to know' or 'nice to know'. Another participant responded by saying that, from their perspective, it didn't matter either way.

Initial discussion during affinity diagramming around administrators centered around what these subjects needed to know. In particular, the participants believed that administrators did not need to know about certain concepts, but the practicalities of how administrators use the current system meant that they did. As such, the group gradually formed the consensus that,

moving forward, administrators needed the capabilities to enact or modify all concepts. At the end of this stage, the participants agreed that they weren't entirely sure how administrators should be defined so they assumed that the administrative staff associated with the current system would be a suitable model upon which to base their thinking. Ultimately, discussion around the wisdom of this choice led to a more broader discussion about what capabilities future administrators of this system would need, and what capabilities the system itself should support.

4.2.2.2.1.2.3 Context clustering

At the stage of this stage, 19 different contexts were elicited. 12 of these were permutations of before/during/after courses, pre-study, marking, and moderation. The remaining contexts were home, work, out and about, inside university, inside classroom, "other people around", and "alone". Due to time constraints there was only time to explore two context/subject combinations: course attendees at home before a course, and lecturers at home after a course.

As the contexts were being written on the board, participants started thinking about the sheer number of contextual possibilities arising from a cartesian product of context and subject. This seemed to flummox the participants to the extent that it was necessary to prompt the participant to pick one context and subject to progress the exercise.

The affinity diagramming process for course attendees at home before a course was largely similar to that for the subject clusters, however the completion of this first subject/context combination led to further group discussion about whether being at home or university made that much difference. In particular, thinking about physical locations where the mobile web-app would be used led to discussions around lecturers carrying out activities which *should* be done at university but may well be undertaken at home, and what consequences might arise if the mobile web-app facilitates activities being carried out in inappropriate locations. For this reason, the group decided to explicitly explore the context of a lecturer working at home after a course.

It was clear that all participants had a clear working model about the lecturer subject for the 'at home after course' context. This was most apparent when, towards the end of this exercise, one participant verbally walked through the model from the perspective of a lecturer. One of the possible corollaries of this clearer expectation about users and contexts was a comparatively greater movement of clusters between categories and across allowed/disallowed sections.

4.2.2.1.3 Discussion

During the de-brief, the participants agreed that the focus group exercise provided a better indication of how the mobile web-app might look compared to sitting down and trying to code it. The notion of thinking about context was also useful, but participants acknowledged that rigorously attempting to go through the product of objects, subjects, and contexts was both

tedious due to similarities between contexts, but also mind-blowing because of subtle nuances between what appear to be similar contexts. The participants also acknowledge that the context that they use more often is time, because of the timelines associated with administering each course.

4.2.2.2.1.3.1 Existing system focus

Throughout the exercise, the participants tended to focus on the existing system and existing system roles, rather than the possibilities of what a mobile web-app might bring. This brings to mind two questions. First, is this thinking specific to developers of an existing system, or do users of an existing system with a comparative knowledge of the domain hold a similar "existing system" bias? Second, when making policy decisions, can a balance be struck between over-constraining and under-constraining a system based on both existing or perceived affordances of a system? One way of answering this latter question might be to synthesise a context of use for affinity diagramming based on a vignette of webinos being used in a future context, which encapsulates the social and cultural consequences arising of design decisions made.

4.2.2.2.1.3.2 Categories and abstractions

This session also demonstrated how developer participants fit concepts around categories, rather than vice versa. Based on the analogies drawn between this exercise and other design activities, this may have occurred because the developers treated categories as abstractions that support longer-term design activities. This is as opposed to spending less time on categorisation and accepting these might evolve as concepts move between different clusters. At this stage, it is unclear whether policy management tools should support longer-lived, more flexible categorisations of objects or subjects, or both.

4.2.2.2.1.3.3 General functionality

Results from a number of focus groups indicate that participants seem to group what they consider general functionality in one place. It remains unclear whether this is good or bad, but it does suggest that breaking this conceptual grouping from a policy standpoint is likely to be disruptive.

4.2.2.2.2 Jimmy Focus Group 2

4.2.2.2.2.1 Session background

The session was held at Telecom Italia Lab, Turin, on Wednesday, 13rd July between 1900 and 2100, and was based around the Jimmy persona.

The focus group was composed of 4 mobile developers working in Telecom Italia's Turin premises, both consultants and internal developers. The participants were recruited starting from friends working in Telecom Italia Lab. All of them are friends and work in the same group.

4.2.2.2.2 Results

4.2.2.2.2.1 Object clustering

During first part of the exercise, the affinity diagramming focused on what the system should do and who will use it, in fact autonomously introducing part of the subject clustering phase. All participants hold a Master of science, so the scenario resulted clear and was analyzed through personal experience of what was the every day university life.

From those discussion emerged data concept (like Content Types) and, mainly, practical issues, like client required capabilities, overall system functions, access controls, data classification and protection.

In particular, the discussion of what services the system should expose went on very tightly with who should use the system. Easy of use and access to candidate user categories (i.e. system

administrator, teacher, teacher assistant, student) was an orienting concept in the discussion, probably due to practical experience and peculiar mindframe of participants.

User security and privacy, (approached as part of the user experience) was lengthy discussed, with care on how to achieve them in practice. Among others, hot security topics discussed was sensitive contents (e.g. what is sensitive or not, like student credit cards or exam location) content authentication (suggested technical solution was digital signature attached to all posted content) and secured provisioning (as they defined the process to add and remove users).

Curiously, a concept emerged is that it is very difficult to (meaningfully) organize access control to sensitive data through a hierarchical categorization of data itself (e.g. plain, sensitive, very confidential, secret, top secret) or, even worse, in a just binary classification like sensitive or not. To solve the problem, there is a need of a matrix of what could be accessed by who, de facto anticipating part of the experiment next phase's discussions.

Participants was very careful to not introduce undiscussed concepts. Before write it on a post-it, many terms were collectively considered, and some mentioned concept (e.g. teacher visiting time) was not added in the affinity diagram since not considered discussion-enriching (e.g. because comprised in some other higher level concepts). From one hand this carefulness made the diagram more "clean" and clear, but from the other introduce the risk to drop out concepts that in a next phase would be enriched and become more valuable.

4.2.2.2.2.2 Subject clustering

During the discussion, some objects have been refined to differentiate among different actor duties and rights. Some clusters have been revised as consequence of a more role-focused analysis. In particular, iterative refining phases allow to create finer-grained concept on the base of who is the owner, e.g from generic student data to data owned by a specific student and data who are not owned by a student but can be accessed only by student attending the course whose data refer to.

Some of the subjects introduced in the previous step are refined and then added the (non-human) "Bank interface" and the "SMS system" roles. Student and teacher were split between course student/teacher and other student/teacher.

For objects not listed under any red/green label, no strong opinions came forth during this phase.

4.2.2.2.2.3 Context clustering

Participants agreed in the first part of the discussion that the location per se does not introduce any difference, since the system is designed to interact remotely.

After, participants considered role changes as different contexts (former teacher, former student, former course teacher, former course student), when possibly different access may be considered. Interestingly, this slightly differs and enrich the former role discussion in previous phase, since introduce the concept of "data dynamism", a data should be accessible by a certain person at one time, but not in another time, since his/her role is changed. So, a secure system must consider appropriately role management as well.

At last, participants reconsidered if different location would influence the access, but concluded that not much the place, but instead the "security level" of the environment should modify what should be accessible (including the type of device in the evaluation of environment security level). E.g. they thought that admin access to sensitive data should be allowed only when accessing through a secure connection.

4.2.2.2.3 Discussion

Even if roles was a concept already present in the first phase, explicitly mentioning it enabled a deeper discussion of what data means, and emerged that the same data concept is different (and should be identified by a different post-it) on the base of who is the owner or legitimate user or user class (e.g. student data).

Participants took longer than expected to do the exercise, so concentration waned in the latter step. Tools to simplify the representation of concepts (and also to diminish the number of used post-it, accordingly to concept of sustainability and paper waste) would increase the willing to develop new concept close to the end of the experiment.

Participants struggled a bit to start thinking about clusters. They began adding new roles and considering them as different context. Even if useful, it appeared that a clear statement of what can be considered a context change would have made more fast and straightforward some initial discussion. In a later phase, it appears worth to converge discussion on core points, to achieve effectiveness after quite much time of argumentation.

Along this line, at the end of the exercise, participants remarked their appreciation to tools capable to avoid post-it duplication. The suggestion to use a matrix, as firstly introduced in the subject phase, was re-stated as useful to focus only on concepts and to spend less time on representation matter.

4.2.2.2.3 Jimmy Focus Group 3

4.2.2.2.3.1 Session background

The session was held in the Focus Group Room of the Usability lab at City University on Friday, 12th August 2011, between 1400 and 1700. It was based around the Jimmy persona. The usability lab facility is available for industry companies to conduct usability studies and focus groups. The session was run with a total of 4 participants all based within City University.

- 2 PhD Students from the School of Informatics
- 1 Member of IT technical support
- 1 HCI Researcher

The participants were recruited directly by the session organiser. Two video cameras, two digital cameras, and a digital audio recorder were used to record the session.

During the second phase of the task, there was some difficulty in identifying categories in which to group the concepts. Respondents felt that there was a lot of overlap in terms of concepts being able to fit into two categories. Initially the 'services' group contained a large majority of the concepts, but after some discussion it was found that this could be split into resources, admin support, and facts. This activity was helpful in identifying further concepts as, via discussion, new ideas emerged.

Course engagement	Services	Resources	Facts	Admin
Alerts (for social events)	Your own area (for personal files)	Course material	Prospectus	Who has attended lecturers
Events	Good uber search engine (for global search)	Ability to push content to my PC	Lecturer profiles	Object identifiers for students
School message board	University eBay	Powerpoint slides	Student demographics	Room facilities
Social media	Being able to reserve a book in library	Module choices	Pass rates	Room booking
History of events (audio/ video/ text)	Integration with ISGs within lecturers	News/ updates	Rankings: university-wide and department-wide	
Centre/ school files (facilities,	Digital library app	Live lecture stream		

4.2.2.2.3.3 Subject clustering

There were a total of 11 subjects identified in this stage:

- Corporate employers
- Prospective students
- Government
- Marketing
- Lecturers
- Journalists/Press
- Administrators
- Researchers
- Industry Partners
- Funding Bodies
- Current Students

Due to time constraints, we were only able to focus upon 2 specific subjects in our discussion.

1) Current Students

When looking at the 'current student' subject, there seemed to be reluctance on disallowing access to many, if not all of the identified concepts. This seemed partly due to the fact that students were identified as one of the main stakeholders in the previous exercise, and a lot of the concepts were devised with students in mind.

There was an interesting discussion around the availability of course timetables for all subjects being available to all students. There were issues raised around how easy it would be for student A (on a different course) to identify the whereabouts of student B just by knowing which course they were taking. There was one respondent in the group who was uncomfortable with this. The argument for having such information available was that it would be something could help any potential applicants in determining their university or course choice (especially part-time students). This discussion in particular raised some interesting points about how individuals' personal privacy could be affected to serve the needs of a wider community.

Similarly to the 'current students' subject, respondent's expressed some difficulties in identifying concepts which lecturers should not have access to. There were some interesting conversations around items such as message boards and forums, as some participants found that lecturers shouldn't have access to private or student-only forums. The counter argument was that by having such access, lecturers could obtain critical feedback about their courses and University services in general, which could help improvements to be made in these areas.

Current students				
Allowed access to				Disallowed access to
Alerts (for social events)	Your own area (for personal files)	Course material	Who has attended lectures	Staff holidays
Events	Good uber search engine (for global search)	Ability to push content to my PC	Object identifiers for students	Current exam scripts
School message board	University eBay	Powerpoint slides	Room facilities	
Social media	Being able to reserve a book in library	Module choices	Room booking	
History of events (audio/video/text)	Integration with ISGs within lecturers	News/updates	Pass rates	
Centre/	Digital	Live lecture	Rankings:	

- When looking for a room
- My timetable
- Looking for opportunities to make money
- Organising and preparing for studies

Due to time constraints, only four context/subject combinations were looked at in detail during this exercise.

There was a mixture of physical contexts and mental contexts that were elicited during this stage. Although several different physical contexts were identified, it was observed that several of them could be grouped into 'remote working' and 'campus-based working'. The mental contexts identified were rather interesting, as they would not necessarily match with all subjects, so some time was spent at the beginning of this stage to identify which pairings of context/subject were most important.

1) Lecturers & Working Remotely

				Lecturers	Working remotely
Allowed access to				Disallowed access to	
Alerts (for social events)	Your own area (for personal files)	Course material	Who has attended lectures	Student private files	
Events	Good uber search engine (for global search)	Ability to push content to my PC	Object identifiers for students		
School message board	University eBay	Powerpoint slides	Room facilities		
Social media	Being able to reserve a book in library	Module choices	Room booking		
History of events (audio/ video/ text)	Integration with ISGs within lecturers	News/ updates	Pass rates		
Centre/	Digital	Live lecture	Rankings:		

2) Students & Working Remotely

Allowed access to				Disallowed access to
Current students		Working remotely		
Alerts (for social events)	Your own area (for personal files)	Course material	Who has attended lectures	Student private files
Events	Good uber search engine (for global search)	Ability to push content to my PC	Object identifiers for students	
School message board	University eBay	Powerpoint slides	Room facilities	
Social media	Being able to reserve a book in library	Module choices	Room booking	
History of events (audio/video/text)	Integration with ISGs within lecturers	News/updates	Pass rates	
Centre/	Digital	Live lecture	Rankings:	

Both of the above pairings yielded the same results as participants felt that the main purpose of developing a mobile app was so that all of the information available within the portal could be made available from technically any type of location.

There were interesting discussions around how much students should be allowed to access resources outside of the physical University environment, as some suggested that this could discourage students from coming into the University. Counter arguments to this point were that as mature adults, the onus would be on the student to decide how much or how little they

would chose to access the teaching resources remotely rather than physically attending lectures/tutorials. A point was also made on the possibility of lecturers also working remotely and giving a lecture via the webcam, so it appeared that the app could work for subjects in similar ways.

In order to stimulate further discussions, the participants were asked to think of a totally different subject – Journalists, and the press.

3) Journalists/press & Looking for oppourtunities to make money

			Journalists	Looking for oppourtunities to make money		
Allowed access to			Disallowed access to			
Alerts (for social events)	Case studies	Room facilities		Powerpoint slides	Student personal files	Digital library app
Events	Good uber search engine	Room booking	History of events	Staff holidays	Live forum/ chat forum	Personal dropbox
Social media	Student demographics	Pass rates	Talks	Live lecture stream	Lecture notes	Ability to push content to my PC
Prospectus	Social events	Rankings:		School message board	Who has attended lecturer	Object identifier for students
Lecturer profiles	Integration with amazon	Institution files (sharing)		University eBay	School files (facilities, equip, message)	Reserve a book in a library
				Integrations with ISGs within lecturers	News/ updates	Current exam scripts
				Module choices	Anonymous grade cards	Private, institution, academic files

In this context it became clear that there would be many items that such subjects should not have access to. There did appear to be a grey area for journalists however, in that it was decided that they should have access to limited historical data associated with the University and teaching materials (primarily for promotional services).

4) Alumni & Looking for oppourtunities for collaborative work

The alumni subjects seemed to have access to a lot more concepts than the journalists (more concept items had been added to the diagram), but they were also limited in the amount of information they received related to specific course material in particular.

Allowed access to			Alumni	Looking for opportunities for collaborative work		
Allowed access to				Disallowed access to		
Demographics	Lecturer profile	Social events		Grades	Object identifier	School message board
Pass rates	Integration with amazon	Institution files	History of events	Powerpoint slides	Course material	University eBay
Case studies	Events	Rankings	Talks	Your own area	Staff holidays	Current exam scripts
News/ updates	Digital library app	Social media		Students private files	Room reservation	Private, institution, academic files (sharing)
Prospects	Live forum/ chat	Room facilities		My dropbox	Live lecture stream	
Room booking	Taster sessions	Alerts		Integrations with ISGs within lecturers	Module choices	
Reserve a book in a library				Who attended lectures	Lecture notes	

4.2.2.2.3.5 Discussion

There were some issues with timing during each of these phases, and our session did run over somewhat. In future sessions, it would be advised to focus on 2-3 main subjects (i.e. the most important) during stage 2, and 2-3 subject/context pairs in stage 3.

Looking at the contexts in which the app would be used was also a stumbling point for the participants as they were considering both physical and mental contexts, which we found difficult to prioritise when working on the later phase of allow/disallow, for future sessions it would be advisable to specify either one or the other.

Having more structure in stage three could help in eliciting more detailed affinity diagrams, i.e. the inclusion of variables such as ‘need to know, nice to know, not allowed to know,’ as this removes the binary yes or no response which was not always easy to categorise.

As we were working with respondents fitting the Jimmy persona, it was clear that whilst working through exercises, they were thinking rather technically in terms of how the application would function which would probably be a different type of approach when compared to some of the other personas. For this reason, it seems suitable to run a similar activity across multiple persona types to observe difference in the outputs.

4.2.2.2.3.6 Main take-aways

The participants were indeed able to think and reason about which information or documents that the subjects should be allowed access to. Current students and lecturers were granted the widest access to information and documents in the mobile application for the university. Journalists, however, seemed to be granted least access. The alumni was granted more access to the information and documents.

Perhaps social closeness could be used as an indicator regarding how much a subject should be granted access to information and documents. The willingness to share information and documents certainly seems to be influenced by how close the subject is to the university. Thus, the closeness in social relation seems to influence an information sharing choice.

Sharing information seems to be affected by both the context and the social relation between the persons involved. Providing technology that makes automatic information sharing choices on behalf of a user therefore seems very difficult, if not impossible to obtain. Rather, it seems that users should explicitly make these choices on their own, and that technology should only enable and deliver on the information sharing choices.

The task of allowing and disallowing access to objects given a subject and/or a given context, seemed to work very well for the participants. The answer to whether a person should be allowed or disallowed access seems to be: "It depends on who it is, what object is being shared, and in which context the sharing is supposed to happen".

The suggestion is to try to answer the following question:

- How to allow/ disallow access to any object for any subject, regardless of the context?

This question could also be expressed as:

- How to make an object public/private/shared to any subject or context?

The recommendation is to try to answer this question in a user interface design context.

4.2.2.3 Clara

4.2.2.3.1 Clara Focus Group 1

4.2.2.3.1.1 *Session background*

The session was held at Polito on Tuesday, 19th July between 16:00 and 18:00, and was based around the Clara persona.

The participants were 4 first year students (three computer engineering students and an industrial engineering and management student), comfortable with scenario described since quite similar to their university facilities. These participants were recruited from a first year course. One student voluntarily answer and then gathered other three class-mate friends.

4.2.2.3.1.2 Results

4.2.2.3.1.2.1 Object clustering

The participants defined the "smart data sharing" as a data sharing respectful of privacy. They highlighted the "WiFi availability" as an alternative to the more expensive mobile connectivity (e.g. 3G). Discussing the "courseware portability and sharing" object, students concerned about the restriction in courseware use, e.g. to view lectures via streaming only, without the possibility to download the records for off line use, or to read texts without the possibility to modify them to add notes.

4.2.2.3.1.2.2 Subject clustering

The participants defined five subjects: system admin, admin, student, teacher, other. Then they elaborate admin, student and teacher. They introduced new objects to define sensitive data and applications. Privacy issue raised in same context as enabler of discussion: the participants deny teacher access to students' forum to feel free to express their opinions about courses and teachers. They don't consider course specific applications managed by the teacher. If objects are not under the green post-it, access is considered denied.

4.2.2.3.1.2.3 Context clustering

The participants think that using authentication, all subjects can do the same things everywhere (this is what it means the "always request password" object). The only exception is the admin, who can access sensitive data from his office only. They think also to teaching lab context and to the possibility to allow access only to course relevant applications and data, but they discard the idea because consider it not relevant.

4.2.2.3.1.3 Discussion

The participants' remarks about security and privacy are often based on their experience as students and smartphone users.

In the subject clustering phase a student mentioned the possibility to use a table to manage access control, but the idea was dropped by other participants.

They introduced the applications cluster with only one object, the students' forum. This led to a trust problem because in the diagram only students have access to applications cluster, while the access by teachers is forbidden.

In the context step, the participants discarded the teaching lab context because "lab machines are already controlled and, communications with smartphone are not involved", so in their opinion webinos was not involved. They often focused on webinos video example rather than on the identification of relevant elements in a more generic way.

They considered the idea to distinguish among different contexts in conflict with portability. They thought that portability imply the possibility to do same things everywhere.

4.2.2.3.2 Clara Focus Group 2

4.2.2.3.2.1 Session background

The session was held at Fraunhofer-Institute for Open Communication Systems Berlin on Thursday, 28th July 2011 between 14:30 and 17:30, and was based around the Clara persona. The underlying scenario is described in the Clara section of focus group reports.

The session was run with 4 participants between 22 and 24 years of the Bachelor's programme computer science Technische Universität Berlin. Each participant was a software engineer with focus on open communication systems. The participants have already worked in engineering projects in the domain of mobile applications and distributed systems. Each participant was recruited directly by the session organiser.

4.2.2.3.2.2 *Results*

4.2.2.3.2.2.1 *Object clustering*

All participants are involved in web development projects of Fraunhofer FOKUS and Technische Universität Berlin. They have a profound knowledge in development of mobile, distributed applications. At the beginning they were introduced into the webinos subject. With this background knowledge the Clara scenario was discussed with the participants. It was difficult to motivate the focus group at the beginning of the object clustering step. Because they had no clear idea how to identify main concepts of the user centric video playback system. The facilitator started motivating the participants to think about concepts like information flow between users and home entertainment system, potential features and activities for interaction as well as connected devices and their capabilities. With this assistance the participants were able to write down the first ideas on post-its.

In retrospect on the scenario devices such as headphone, TV set and smartphone were quickly identified and grouped. Afterwards the participants began discussing about control and access from different perspectives. On the one hand access control can be carried out on the consumer from third parties via Country Code Data or Digital Rights Management otherwise the consumer has various options to interact with the system and to access features like Media Library, Player, Recorder, Noise Regulation, etc. Furthermore, it should be noted that media store features are indispensable for home entertainment systems. The scenario outlined that a movie comes with extra audio and subtitle streams for different languages as well as a special stream for hearing

impaired users where the environmental noise is reduced in order to make the actors speech clearer. These aspects were reflected by the participants during the discussion on information flow between home media entertainment system, consumer and content provider. The result of the discussion was to enrich meta data with an audio stream for hearing-impaired users with support of a real-time translation capability. After extensive considerations the focus group identified six clusters: Mediastore, Consumer Control, Devices, Meta Data, Interactions and Media Access & Control.

4.2.2.3.2.2.2 Subject clustering

Facilitator and participants started with a brainstorming session to identify persons, 3rd party providers and external systems which can interact with the home entertainment system. Following subjects were identified: government, friends, family, content provider, and marketplace. The participants argued that from the perspective of childrens family and friends have similar access policies to the home entertainment system. Therefore family and friends were defined as one subject. Regarding content provider and marketplace participants emphasized that content providers have a significant impact on the marketplace. Based on the idea that a content provider is the owner of a marketplace which is not absolutely necessary in all cases. Despite this limitation participants decided to consider content provider as subject for the next steps. Government was identified as last subject as they have regulating effects on content like movies and games which are restricted to age limitations. Afterwards participants started with the re-clustering.

Content Provider

A significant result of the clustering is that content providers should have limited access to devices and home media entertainment system features. In other words the user should have the main controls about the system. Otherwise content providers have full control about commercial exploitation via marketplaces and positioning of promotional campaigns for video and audio content. Furthermore providers can also specify in which quality movies will be offered including support of hearing-impaired users. In conclusion the participants decided that content providers have the full control about pricing, commercialization, digital rights management, content quality and access channels for sale and consumption like TV sets, smartphones, desktops. For the participants it was relatively easy to think about the category content provider and to find the right associations. During the discussion about commercialization concepts participants extended the object cluster meta data with paid and free content.

Family&Friends

The category family&friends are the users of the home entertainment system and they are also the consumers of various content types. Consequently it was very easy for the participants to decide that controls about content and system lies by the user. The only restriction concerns user verification, country code data, recommendations and digital rights management. That are all concepts where the user has no influence and control. It must be highlighted "to have control about a concept" was equated with "to have influence on a concept". That means the participants clustered a lot of concepts to the green site. For example consumers can influence a video stream in form of a feedback channel or by using the time shift feature, but they have no control about quality and included commercials.

Government

The last step of this phase was to think about the role of governmental organisations in the entire life cycle of content provision. Participants argued that the government has to adopt policies to restrain extremist and endangering contents. With this assumption governmental organisations have to control which content types will be available in marketplaces. With regard to the scenario to support hearing-impaired users this support should also be regulated by policies. Thus we have also an influence of government on device features, access facilities and content types.

4.2.2.3.2.2.3 *Context clustering*

Due to limited time, the facilitator decided to elaborate two different context scenarios. At first, the participants discussed what implications exist if adults were using the home entertainment system. In this context, only the subject clusters family&friends and government were considered.

Context Adults

The affiliate diagram visualizes following results based on the assumption that the home entertainment system will be lent to friends or other family members. As discussed in the subject clustering phase, family members or friends have full access and control to system and device features as well as the entire marketplace ecosystem. The only limitation is reflected in the responsibilities of content providers like digital rights management and verifications.

The next step was to think about possible changes in the subject cluster: government. During the subject clustering phase participants had in mind how big should be the influence of the government. The main result was to restrict access to extremist, illegal material or contents harmful to young people. Therefore the affiliate diagram visualizes the same result as in the subject clustering phase. Additional participants pointed out content for adults should also be restricted by the government.

Context Children

After discovering context adults, the facilitator motivated participants to think about changes if childrens were using the home entertainment system. As represented in the affiliate diagram childrens should have limited access and control to system and device features as well as special content types like paid and age-limited content. This also includes restrictions in buying and downloading content from marketplaces. In conclusion, the entire system including the marketplace and media library, should be restricted for childrens. In comparison to the context adults, the participants argued that the system have to support considerably more restrictions for childrens in different age categories.

The last step of this stage was to think about influence of governmental organizations from the child perspective. In comparison to adults the diagram was extended with one minor change regarding consumer control. The government should provide policies to restrict access to youth endangering contents. Therefore, the system has to support user (age) verification.

4.2.2.3.2.3 Discussion

During the de-brief session, the participants agreed that context was an ever-present part of the exercise, even though it was only explicitly applied in the final stage of the session. In particular, exploring the finer details of a particular context led to equally fine-grained exploration of the subjects and objects within in. This often led to mis-interpretations about objects, subjects, or contexts being surfaced when objects were moved from either the allowed or dis-allowed sections of the board, and vice-versa.

4.2.2.3.2.3.1 Object clustering

In retrospect, basic concepts for user interactions, features, information flow, devices and merchandising concepts for the home entertainment system were identified. Regarding the scenario it should be noted that features like noise regulation, real-time translation and audio stream for hearing-impaired users are essential for the system. Another interesting aspect was that the participants differentiated between free and paid content. To restrict the consumer control by user (age) verification, digital rights management and country code data are important concepts which were reflected in all following phases.

4.2.2.3.2.3.2 Subject clustering

After the brainstorming session the participants worked out various subject classes. During time limitations participants elaborated content provider, family&friends and government. It can be concluded that the content provider should have no control about devices, private data and home entertainment system features. Otherwise the content provider has full control regarding commercialization, pricing, quality and types of content and distribution. Furthermore it should be noted that content providers have minor influences on the operating systems of smartphones and TV sets. With the background to implement digital rights management and age verification capabilities. From the user perspective in case of family&friends they have full control about device and software features of the entertainment system including marketplace and media library access. Concerning government class participants came to the conclusion that government organisations have to limit access via policies to extremist, illegal and youth endangering contents. On the other hand, based on fundamental democratic view, government organisations are not allowed to censor content or to dictate device / software capabilities.

4.2.2.3.2.3.3 Context clustering

Two contexts were considered in this phase: adults and children. In summary, it can be said that children different ages should have limited access to content and device features of home entertainment systems. This includes also limited access to marketplaces for buying and downloading content. Therefore home entertainment systems has to support concepts to implement these age limitations.

4.2.2.3.3 Clara Focus Group 3

4.2.2.3.3.1 Session background

The session was held at Polito on Wednesday, 27th July between 1530 and 1700, and was based around the Clara persona.

The session was run with 4 participants:

- a 21 years old electronic engineering student
- a 23 years old mathematics student
- a 20 years old psychology student
- a 22 years old psychology student

The session organiser directly recruited one participant, who involved three friends.

4.2.2.3.3.2 Results

4.2.2.3.3.2.1 Object clustering

The participants started defining objects, but after a couple of ideas they preferred to define clusters and then fill them. They defined "personal data" as a cluster but left it empty. They started to think about access control, and to place yes/no post-it beside objects, answering the question: "should I have access to this object?". The facilitator stopped them postponing the access control problem until the next step. "Student status" object represents information about student passed exams within the prescribed period of time.

4.2.2.3.3.2.2 Subject clustering

The participants initially thought to distinguish between "student" and "students" subject, arguing that a student can access his personal data and students can only access non personal data. Afterwards they preferred to use only the "student" subject, introducing new objects to represent other students data. They also added objects to represent other exams, to restrict teacher access, and the "academic information" object, representing university public data, e.g. courses offering, study plans, regulations.

4.2.2.3.3.2.3 Context clustering

The participants mainly restricted contexts to locations. They decided that in "home", "car" and "internet point" contexts, nothing changes for all subjects but administrator.

About the administrator, they decided to consider the device used to access sensitive data rather than the location, so the administrator must use a "secured terminal" to have access rights decided in previous step, otherwise he has same rights than "others" subject. They defined "secured terminal" as a broad concept, it may be a terminal which only the administrator can physically access or a terminal with "controlled software" (they didn't have the knowledge to talk about software attestation).

4.2.2.3.3.3 Discussion

In object clustering they focused immediately on data and information, without consider other object categories. This may be influenced by the kind of their studies. They touched on the possibility to introduce different type of data (e.g. academic regulations accessibility) but they discarded this idea.

The participants' thoughts were often tied to their personal experience as students. E.g. in the subject clustering step the participants deepened privacy related issues reasoning about their exams' grades visibility.

In the context clustering step, the participants struggled a bit to start thinking about contexts. They preferred to consider subjects and to think if they can have different access rules in different conditions. The restriction of contexts to locations, may be influenced by the exercise sheet ("if a TA was at home or out and about in Oxford while running the app, would you want him/her to have the capability of installing content on teaching machines").

4.2.3. Discussion

Each focus group report was analysed and thematically coded based on the original research question, i.e. what factors impact the elicitation, categorisation, and grouping of security and privacy policy concepts multiple contexts?

The results of this analysis are summarised in the following sections.

4.2.3.1 Framing

Although not formally acknowledged by the participants, each focus group appeared to elicit and categorise data within the frame of a working context. The ability of participants to frame data was mediated by three factors.

The first of these were the nuances in the working context; these range from varying the time-frame of a working context through to changing the family relationship of subjects in a context.

Exploring these casted a new light on pre-existing objects, but these also led to considerable discussion, slowing down the rate of progress.

The second factor was general fatigue. Framing and re-framing objects and categories within a working context was tiring as well as time-consuming. In some cases, a rigorous exploration of objects and subjects in the working context left participants so tired that contexts were specified around pre-existing subjects or locations closely related to that associated with the working context.

The third factor was the use of supporting tools - in particular sketches and check-lists. Sketches were used by one focus group as a supplement to the context clustering affinity diagramming to explain particular subtleties of a context. Mental checklists were used by a number of focus groups to check the relevance of concepts, or validate a concept's inclusion under a particular category.

Although primarily used for concept elicitation and categorisation, framing was also useful for identifying concepts and categories that form the basis of innovation within the general domain. Examples of these included the elicitation of commercialisation concepts, and regulatory concepts that might foster improved privacy as well as security.

4.2.3.2 Bias

The ability of participants to frame concepts and categories was influenced by pre-existing biases. In some cases, biases led to restrictive thinking about concepts because of pre-existing domain knowledge. This was most obvious in focus groups centred on the software engineering website where pre-existing knowledge about how courseware was used or how hardware was setup appeared to unnecessarily dismiss objects as disallowed to particular subjects and context. The majority of cases where pre-existing biases were evident appeared to be when considering the implicit working context during object and subject clustering. Sometimes, these biases were re-enforced by participants when discussions were particularly grounded around a particular frame; these frames were based on anecdotal experience of the working context or by particular prompting by the facilitators.

As well as restricting thinking, biases and grounding also facilitated the elicitation of concepts which might otherwise have been missed. In almost all focus groups, grounded discussions around particular working concepts lead to the identification of concepts which were missed during the un-grounded and context free object clustering stages.

4.2.3.3 Expectations

The ability to frame concepts was also influenced by expectations held by the participants about the behaviour of particular subjects. Some of these were formed by pre-existing biases because participants felt they were proxy users for subjects under discussion. In others, participants espoused opinions they believed subjects might find important, irrespective of whether *they* found it important. For example, in one of the “Clara” focus groups, participants proposed DRM restrictions that they felt content providers would find important.

In some focus groups, participants felt confident enough in their knowledge of subject expectations that concepts would be moved between allowed and disallowed sections of the white board by category and, in some cases, categories would be elicited before concepts, and subsequent concepts grouped by static, pre-existing categories.

Expectations were important for envisaging the impact of policy decisions but, in certain cases, this also led to scope creep when participant knowledge of subjects or the domain appeared to be deficient. One of the factors contributing to scope creep was generalisation about the

problem domain; this arose due to lack of knowledge or only a superficial treatment of concepts. The other contributing factor was generalisation due to perceived lack of relevance. Examples of this included collectively grouping “interface” or “service” technology because they seemed equally relevant to all subjects and contexts, and generalisation categories for concepts that were disallowed for particular subjects and context. In some cases, relevance generalisation lead to an implicit transfer of trust onto objects or subjects related to generalised objects or categories. For example, “administrator” subjects were, in some cases, given untethered access to concepts. Similarly, in one focus group, participants considered a context where a “secure” terminal might be used by an administrator in an untrusted location.

4.2.4. Recommendations

For subsequent webinos activities, we propose the following recommendations based on the focus group results.

4.2.4.1 *Reverse the order to policy development*

The focus groups were designed to stimulate thinking about objects which needed to be secured before subjects that would (or would not) access them, and their contexts of use. In hindsight, however, framing with a working context meant that context could not be divorced from the policy specification processes. For this reason, it may be more fruitful to begin the process by eliciting contexts of use before objects within them, or subjects that use them. While this finding is not exclusive to webinos, it is particularly important given the myriad of context types associated with the webinos context model.

4.2.4.2 *Use wizards to guide policy creation*

As well as breaking the task into a set of discrete operations, when properly used, the Wizard idiom provides a roadmap that allows users to be guided through the process of developing a security policy (TIDW2010). Based on the focus group data, the challenges associated with policy development are such that both users and developers appear to be prepared to surrender control of the non-periodic process of creating a security policy. Moreover, the physical structure of the wizard can be customised to follow a context-driven, as opposed to object-driven, path.

What is not yet clear is whether subjects or objects should immediately following from context in the wizard sequence. Moreover, because an appropriate set of defaults needs to be incorporated into each policy, some burden is added to policy developers to specify reasonable settings based on the application, the problem domain, and the expected user base.

4.2.4.3 Use supplemental tools for policy creation and management

Although wizards can guide policy creation, additional tools are needed not only for editing policies, but also for creating supplemental information. The focus group results showed that techniques such as sketches and checklists were useful. Previous work in the HCI/Sec literature has also found that, when supplemented with contextual, matrices provide improved speed and accuracy when viewing and changing policies over traditional policy management tools (REED2008). Based on both the literature and the focus group results, subject/object matrix controls for editing XACML policies in webinos should support supplemental information to allow policy editors to reconstruct the frame used by policy developers when creating the additional policy. This supplemental information may include multi-dimension matrix cells such as (REED2008), or additional controls to allow the attachment of image files or rationale documentation.

4.3. Questionnaire on user behaviour and expectations for accessing and sharing digital information

4.3.1. Motivation

The objective of the survey is to explore information sharing aspects to personalised information and documents. This will inform us about user needs and expectations to the webinos platform and its applications. As part of this, there is also a specific need to obtain more knowledge about user behaviour, self-attitudes, and expectations to security and privacy. It is important to get a sample from the population on these matters to complement the focus group experiments. Surveys are by some considered to obtain more objective results than qualitative interviews and focus groups. Since webinos is a large project, there is a need to make the right choices and priorities based on empirical data pertinent to the target user population, internationally. The quantitative results of the survey is to partially complement the qualitative focus group experiments, and also to further inform the applications and platform development.

4.3.2. Survey methodology

To explore these user needs and expectations, three categories of questions were identified: i) user demographics (Q1), ii) experience with devices and applications (Q2-Q6), and iii) security and privacy for personal information and documents (Q7-Q10). The survey targeted both online and face to face respondents of both genders with a relatively wide age distribution. The following core questions were asked in the survey (Q1-Q10):

1. Please answer a few general questions about yourself

2. How often do you use the following devices?
3. In the future, what kind of devices would you prefer to use to access your personal information?
4. What kind of activities/ applications do you use your devices for?
5. In which situations do you access information and applications on your devices?
6. In which situations would you like to have more access to relevant information or applications on your devices?
7. Which personal information and documents are you happy to share with family and friends?
8. Which personal information and documents are you happy to share with local shops and marketing agencies that you know?
9. How much do you trust the following people and organisations to handle your personal information and documents in a secure way?
10. Which personal information and documents do you think others could misuse for their own benefits, or to seek harm?

As means to shorten the response time and to obtain a high response rate, the respondents provided answers in combination of multiple choice and Likert scales (5-point). The survey first went through a preliminary design stage with face to face survey responses to obtain feedback from participants and researchers as means to improve and fine-tune the survey. Control points were also successfully added to the survey to be able to filter away erroneous responses for Q3 to Q10 in the online survey.

In the online survey, the participant had to answer each question fully in order to proceed to the next question. The answers were automatically saved upon the completion of each question. The four latter questions (Q7-Q10) were especially designed to learn more about user expectations to security and privacy. We chose to sample this by asking for self-attitudes related to information sharing and trust.

Ideally, from a statistical viewpoint, the targeted population for the survey were those who can access the web, aiming for samples reflecting an even gender and age distribution. A control sample set was collected resulting in 30 responses through face to face surveys. This data set was later compared with the online survey results to cross-check if the online survey results were robust. The pre-screening method for the face to face survey was to approach people that were in the context of using a computer. The pre-screening method for the online survey was to make the survey available on the web. An almost even gender distribution was achieved for the face to face survey. The online survey was channelled through various interest groups on LinkedIn. LinkedIn consists of a wide range of groups where people register to share information related to specific interest across industries: e.g. fashion industry, e-marketing, travel & tourism,

social media, mobile content, and so on. There are about 101 million users on LinkedIn in 2011, and 41.1% of these are women. Over 47% of all LinkedIn members live in America, 22.8% in Europe, and 13.6% in Asia. Source: LinkedIn, Jan 2011, see <http://amover.files.wordpress.com/2011/01/linkedin-demographics-2011-infographic.jpg> presented by A. Verde. Achieving an almost even gender distribution by using LinkedIn therefore was more tricky than for the face to face surveys.

Both the face-to-face and the online version of the survey had to be answered on a volunteer basis. The online survey was posted as a discussion on several LinkedIn groups. It was designed to take about 15 minutes for each respondent to complete. AmbieSense Ltd conducted the survey with feedback and contributions from Oxford University.

4.3.3. Results

The online survey was conducted in August 2011. As previously mentioned, it consisted of 10 questions to inform the development of the platform and its applications. All questions were asked in the same order, and subsequently all answers of each questions were also answered in the same order. The results of the first questions (i.e. Q2-Q6) are to be found in webinos deliverable 5.1, because these results help inform the choice and development of the suite of innovative applications to be made. However, the results for the security and privacy related questions (i.e. Q7-Q10) are to be found in here, in this section. Note that the average values reported are the arithmetic mean values of all responses. All results are unfiltered.

4.3.3.1 *Q1 - Please answer a few general questions about yourself*

This question was asked to learn about the demographics of the respondents in term of gender and age. Here are the results of the age and gender distribution for the total questionnaire:

Please answer a few general questions about yourself							
Gender							
Answer Options	Female	Male	Response Count				
Select your gender and age	55	84	139				
Age							
Answer Options	Under 20	20 - 29	30 - 39	40 - 49	50 - 59	60 and over	Response Count
Select your gender and age	4	48	42	30	6	9	139
							Question Totals
answered question							139
skipped question							0

By AmbieSense Ltd, Aug 2011

As mentioned, in an ideal world one would like to achieve an equal gender and age distribution. This is more easier to control in face to face surveys, but more tricky to control in online surveys. The survey was conducted on LinkedIn, and we were therefore aiming to achieve a gender and age distribution close to the LinkedIn demographics, which have about 41% women, and the vast majority of users seem to be older than 20 years. The reader is asked to compare the demographics of our survey with the LinkedIn demographics referred to in the previous methodology section. There were 39.6% female respondents to our survey. The main bulk of respondents, independent of the gender, were generally between 20-50 years.

4.3.3.2 Q7 - Which personal information and documents are you happy to share with family and friends?

This question was asked to explore whether there could be differences in what kind of personal information and documents that the respondents would be happy to let family members and friends have access to. The spectrum of answers could be anything from 'not share' to 'happy to share', on a 5-point scale. In general, if the trend sample shows that most people would tend to not share some personal information or documents, then this could imply from a design perspective that the privacy settings could simply be to 'not share' this with family and friends. Similarly, if the trend is that people in general seem quite happy to share some kind of personal

information or documents, then the privacy settings for this could just as well be to 'automatically share'.

101 participants answered question Q7. The bar chart shows the average value of the responses. For analytics purposes the answers with average values between 3 and 5, on the 5 point scale, are named 'likely to be shared'. Similarly, those answers between 1 and 2 on the scale are categorised as 'likely not to be shared'. The following types of personal information and documents are likely to be shared with family and friends:

- My photos
- My videos
- My music collection
- My interests and preferences
- My book collection
- My friends and social network

The following personal information and documents are likely not to be shared with family and friends:

- My information on the mobile phone
- Which web pages I visit
- My health record
- My finances, credit cards
- My passwords

Interestingly, passwords, finances, and credit card information rate so low in the terrain that one could just as well call this information for the most private information that people seem unwilling to share with family and friends. In stark contrast to this, personal photos and videos seem to be happily shared with family and friends.

4.3.3.3 Q8 - Which personal information and documents are you happy to share with local shops and marketing agencies that you know?

This question was asked to see if there could be nuances in what type of personal information and documents that people would be happy to share with local shops and marketing agencies that they might know. It was designed to compare and contrast if the average answers would vary if one substituted 'family and friends' with some other subjects that the respondents would be able to relate to. Local shops often outsource their advertising campaigns to a marketing agency or to the head office. The rationale behind asking for local shops and marketing agencies that they know, is that the respondents would be able to relate to these subjects in everyday contexts. As with Q7, also Q8 asked for answers between 'not share' and 'happy to share', on the same 5-point scale. If the average trend for Q8 shows that most people would tend not to share some kind of personal information or documents with these new subjects, then this could imply from a privacy policy view that the privacy settings could simply be to 'not share' with local shops and marketing agencies that they know. Similarly, if the average trend shows that the respondents would seem quite happy to share some kind of personal information or documents with these businesses, then the default privacy settings could be to 'automatically share'.

Which personal information and documents are you happy to share with local shops and marketing agencies that you know?

By AmbieSense Ltd, Aug 2011

Not share

Happy to share

The survey resulted in 100 responses to question Q8. The bar chart depicts the averaged values of the sample. By looking closer at the figure, it dawns that it would not be possible to operate with the same categories of 'likely to be shared', and 'not likely to be shared' as was the case for question Q7. For better sense making purposes with regards to question Q8, the answers with average values between 2 and 2.5 are named 'could possibly be shared'. Similarly, the average answers between 1 and 1.5 on the scale are categorised as 'definitively not to be shared'.

Here are the kinds of personal information and documents that possibly could be shared with local shops and marketing agencies that the user would know:

- My interest and preferences

The following personal information and documents are definitively not to be shared with local shops and marketing agencies that the user would know:

- My online availability
- Which web pages I visit
- Who I am nearby now
- My photos
- My videos
- My information on my mobile phone
- My documents
- My calendar, appointments
- My health record
- My finance, credit cards
- My emails, messages
- My passwords

All the other personal information and documents are also not to be shared; the average values for these are between 1.5 and 2 on the 5 point scale.

Interestingly, by just swapping the subjects from 'family and friends' to 'local shops and marketing agencies that they know' there is a significant change in people's expectations to privacy. It seems there is a general reluctance in wanting to share the same kinds of personal information and documents with these new subjects compared to the willingness to share with family and friends. The reader is asked to compare the answers of question Q7 and Q8 with each other. There seems to be a statistical significance in this sample that underpins this sudden difference in privacy needs. Some types of personal information and documents that people were likely to share with family and friends, has been moved down to definitively not to be shared with local shops and marketing agencies. Again, personal passwords, finance, and credit card information is found at the lowest end of the scale with very low desire for sharing.

Note that all respondents that answered Q8 also responded to Q7.

4.3.3.4 Q9 - How much do you trust the following people and organisations to handle your personal information and documents in a secure way?

There were 100 responses to question Q9. The results are exhibited in the bar chart. The purpose of the question was to look into whether trust could have anything to do with user expectations to security and privacy. As indicated by the results of question Q7 and Q8, perhaps the closeness in social relation could be used as an indicator for the willingness to share information. However, closeness in social relation does not necessarily imply that there is an increased trust level. Thus, it seemed necessary to also explore the trust level in terms of handling personal information and documents.

By exploring this exhibit a bit closer, it seems reasonable to analyse the results by dividing them into the three categories of: 'medium to high trust', 'some to medium trust', and 'little to some

trust'. The first category spans the average value range between 3 and 5, the second group is for average values between 2 and 3, whereas the latter one covers average values between 1 and 2, on a 5 point scale.

By sorting the answers into these three categories, one could say that people generally have medium to high trust in the following people and organisations to handle their own personal information and documents in a secure way:

- Family

Next, the average user would seem to have some to medium trust in the following people and organisations to handle their personal information and documents in a secure way:

- Friends
- Colleagues
- Your Government
- Your mobile operator
- Developers of web sites that you often use
- Social networking sites
- Search engine companies

Finally, users seem to have only little to some trust in the following subjects to handle their personal information and documents in a secure way:

- Developers of applications that you use
- Mobile phone manufacturers
- Local merchants and businesses that you already know
- Other Governments
- Developers of web sites that you don't know
- Unknown persons recommended to you
- Attackers
- Unknown persons, organisations

Interestingly, attackers and unknown persons and organisations figure at the very bottom with little trust. This is in sharp contrast with family, friends, and colleagues. If closeness in social relation was to be defined by the extent of which a user knows a person or organisation, then the comfort zone for users with regards to trusting others to handle the personal information and documents, seems to pretty much boil down to how close the other person or organisation is to the user in his/ her social network.

4.3.3.5 Q10 - Which personal information and documents do you think others could misuse for their own benefits, or to seek harm?

Question Q10 also resulted in 100 responses. All persons that answered Q10 also answered Q9. This question explored whether users believe that other people and organisations would be able to misuse their personal information and documents, whether it is to gain some kind of benefit, or to seek harm. There is the belief that some people don't think that information can be misused, but also equally the belief that all kind of personal information and documents could potentially be misused. By asking this, we would not only learn if users in general regard their information and documents as assets that potentially could be misused, but moreover also the degree of misuse. This will help inform the design of privacy policy settings and also what security solutions to choose. The participants provided answers between 'highly relevant' and 'not relevant' on a 5 point scale. One frequently occurring example of misuse is knowing the location of the user. Let us see what people really mean about the misuse of this in comparison with other personal information and documents too:

A closer examination of the diagram finds it reasonable to analyse the results by grouping the answers into three relevance categories: 'lesser relevant', 'quite relevant', and 'towards highly relevant'. The former category covers the average value range between 1 and 3, the second captures the average value range between 3 and 4, whereas the latter category contains average values between 4 and 5. A 5 point scale was also in use for this question Q10.

By grouping the answers into those three categories, one could say that the survey participants believe it to be towards high relevance for someone to misuse the following personal information and documents to their benefit, or to seek harm:

- My finances, credit cards
- My passwords
- My emails, messages
- My information on my mobile phone
- My own contact details
- My documents
- My health record
- Where I live and work
- My location, whereabouts
- My calendar, appointments
- My friends and social network

Furthermore, it seems that the respondents believe it is quite relevant for the following personal information and documents could be subject for misuse:

- The identity of my device
- Which web pages I visit
- Who I am nearby now
- My photos
- My videos
- My interests and preferences
- My online availability
- Where I shop, what I buy

Finally, the responses also believe it to be of lesser relevance for others to try to misuse the following personal information and documents:

- My applications and games
- My book collection
- My magazines and news papers
- My music collection

It seems worth noting that the two former categories enclose personal information and documents that could be related more personally to the user compared to the latter category. Both former categories seem to include user context information as well as documents provided

to the user, made by the user, or about the user. However, in the latter category, all of the items seem to have been provided by some one else, and therefore could be considered to be of less personal nature. This could suggest that the more personal a user perceives a document or some information to be, the more likely the user would feel that it could be misused.

4.3.4. Recommendations

This section provides recommendations on user expectations to security and privacy anchored in the online survey results. We chose to explore information sharing aspects, because security and privacy is in essence related to any kind of digital information and documents.

Information and documents that are generally made available to the public, is not of our concern, because such information is supposed to be available for all. Similarly, information and documents that are already private, i.e. accessible only to the individual user, would also not be of particular concern, because these information objects are already safely protected.

The question and tension as to whether a document or some information should or should not be accessible by others, appears when people start to share these with others. Such information objects, could be more or less personal, and the sharer must make explicit choices about who should have access to the documents. In an ideal world, the sharing person would be able to regret the sharing with others and perhaps even withdraw the shared information. However, this seems too difficult to obtain, so that allowing/ disallowing access to information objects from time to time, seems to be what would be practically achievable by webinos.

Here are some of the main findings:

- People seem most happy to share with family and friends
- People seem least happy to share passwords, personal finances, and credit card information with anyone - even family
- The more personal information and documents become, the more people believe they could be subject for misuse
- People does not want to share personal information and documents with unknown persons and organisations
- People trust their family members the most when it comes to handle their information securely
- People are most willing to share photos, videos, music, books, and interests with family and friends
- People would to some extent be willing to share interest and preferences with local shops and advertisers

- Unknown persons and organisations, and attackers, have least trust when it comes to protecting personal data
- People seem to think that information objects that are not sent to them, about them, or made by them, are of lesser relevance when it comes to misuse

The biggest factor that seem to affect a person's willingness to share personal information and documents, seems to be how close the revealing person or organisation is in his/her social network. Similarly, it seems that the closer a person is in your social network, the more likely you will trust the person to protect your personal information and documents.

4.3.4.1 Use the same privacy settings control to make any information or document public, shared, or private

The recommendaton for the development of privacy controls in webinos is to make a privacy control mechanism that can enable the users to share any kind of document or information in the same easy, user friendly, and forgiving way. Users must be able to specify the privacy settings of any information or document by stating whether the information asset is: 1) public, 2) shared, or 3) private. The recommendation is for all information objects to be private from the beginning.

For some applications it will be natural to use sharing or public as the default privacy setting. This seems most likely for applications that will be handling multi-media such as photos, videos, and music.

4.3.4.2 Explore the use of a person's social graph to provide auto-suggestions on who to share with

The implementation of the information sharing mechanisms in webinos, should ideally be able to relate the privacy settings of any information object to any user of any application or device. If webinos was able to auto-suggest the names of the people to share something with, across applications and social networks, this would likely enhance the interaction with the privacy settings of the information object that is being subject for sharing. For instance, one could be able to refer to a Facebook user, a Twitter, user, a webinos user and so on. The question is whether or not this would be practically possible.

This recommendation seems to need further research.

4.3.4.3 Leave the sharing choice on the user, but allow applications to suggest privacy settings

It seems possible to some extent to predict whether a person would be happy to share an information object with someone else by having up-to-date knowledge about a persons social network. However, one would never know how personal/ important the user thinks the given document or information is for him/her. Therefore, the recommendation is to instead let the users explicitly state their privacy preferences given the information object at hand, and to let application developers suggest/ negotiate the privacy settings at the start of the application installation through a dialouge that is informative to the user.

5 Misusability Case Analysis

5.1. Approach

Scenarios can be used from both a security and usability perspective. To usability engineers, they describe how people use a system to carry out activities achieving their personal or occupational goals. To security engineers, scenarios describe how a system might be misused towards an attacker's ends. Although flexible enough to be used in both contexts, a scenario in one context is not necessarily useful in another. A scenario describing a hacker's attack on a web-server does not necessarily provide insight into how the web-server's administrator perceives its usability.

One way of engaging developers to think about both security and usability might be to encourage them to consider the negative impact their decisions could have on the system they are building. A system could go wrong in many different ways; it could be exploited by an insider or external attacker, or it could be sufficiently unusable that key-stakeholders lose confidence in its capabilities. By focusing on the different unintended consequences of a system, developers may be encouraged to track problems back to their root causes.

Modelling misuse with scenarios is not a new idea, e.g. Misuse Cases. However, it remains unclear how useful misuse cases are for understanding the impact of misusability. Alexander (ALEX2003) suggests that misuse cases can be used for examining usability issues; he presents an example where confusion about the use of an interface causes a novice user to become a negative agent. A corollary of this approach is that the user is typecast as an attacker, but this analogous to treating the user as the cause of poor interface design.

Rather than treating the user as a problem, we need to discover the contributing factors to inadvertent misuse or abuse of a system. This means looking beyond the classic view of systems used precisely as their designers intended. An example of such thinking is Dunne & Raby's work (DURA2001) on Design Noir, which argues that our emotions and needs are played out in technology across a much broader spectrum of use originally envisaged by its designers. Other work includes value scenarios: vignettes which describe the systematic effects of a system to both direct and indirect users over an extended period of time (NAKL2007). Value scenarios describe both the positive and negative systematic effects of technology without considering users as malevolent; they do so by describing the negative impact of forgetting about certain values, such as prejudice and inequality. Not all software systems are as divisive, pervasive, or long-running as those typically described by value scenarios. Nevertheless, it may be possible to stimulate similar narratives with more supplemental information about the system, its users, and its contexts of use. This information may not be available during the preliminary stages of design where it is envisaged that value scenarios should be employed, but it might be available from the data collected during later stages.

In WP 2.7, Tasks allow the impact of security decisions on the usability of tasks to personas to be modelled, but the only way misusability can be explored is by treating personas as attackers, or identifying obstacles that giving rise to security misusability. If we consider these obstacles as exceptional behaviour, then use cases might form the basis of eliciting such obstacles. Although use cases often describe the normal course of an actor's usage of a system, exceptional behaviour can be associated with individual steps. Using this approach, accidental misuse of a system can be elicited without typecasting a persona as an attacker, but only if the requirements giving rise to the misuse are known. Yet, it may be the case that all we have are clues to what this misuse might be, and nothing that can be readily associated with a use case. Such clues might include possible ambiguity in a specification, or some assumptions about a persona's behaviour that, in some cases, might cause certain types of behaviour.

The argumentation model used in WP 2.7 illustrated how such assumptions can be used to help ground personas. If the Toulmin Model can be used to ground personas, it may also be possible to use it ground assumptions about possible system or user ambiguity as well. Characteristics derived from these may form the basis for establishing contexts where security misusability can occur. To this end, this section presents Misusability Cases: scenarios which describe how design decisions may lead to usability problems subsequently leading to system misuse. In the following sections, we describe the pre-requisite activities that need to be carried out before undertaking Misusability Case analysis, before walking through the process with an illustrative example.

5.1.1. Pre-requisite activities

The following activities need to be carried out before misusability case elicitation and analysis can commence.

- The Webinos Use Cases and requirements need to be specified and available for review. These artifacts will form the grounds upon which misusability cases are based.
- Personas need to be specified and available for review. Misusability cases describe scenarios carried out by one or more explicit personas; it is the behavioural characteristics associated with the persona which motivate why ambiguity might be exploited to satisfy particular goals.

5.1.2. Review requirements and personas for possible conflicts

The first step involves finding examples of where certain use cases or requirements might conflict with the characteristics of personas. To do this, it is a good idea to look at personas and consider the sort of circumstances that might lead them to cut corners to achieve their goals.

For example, Anna might shortcut technology to help get around, and Gloria might inadvertently misuse the system if she gets her work and personal privacy policies muddled up.

5.1.3. Identify assumptions that lead for misusability

In his Assumption-Based Planning methodology, Dewar (DEWA2002) distinguishes between *implicit* and *load-bearing* assumptions. Implicit assumptions are assumptions that planners are not consciously aware they are making; load bearing assumptions are those that the success of a plan rest on. Dewar proposes a number of techniques that can be used to identify these types of assumption, these include:

- Look for instances of 'will' and 'must': Often, the unstated tacit assumption behind each of these assumptions is 'we assume'
- Ask journalist questions (Who? What? When? Where? How? and Why?): assumptions challenged by these questions which do not yield an adequate response may be implicit or load-bearing.

The data sources upon which assumptions are based are identified and analysed based on some particular functional area that might impact a persona for interest.

5.1.4. Document persona factors and design issues

Based on the analysis in the previous step, this step involves writing the persona factors and design issues which, collectively, contribute to one or more misusability cases. The *persona factors* section describes behaviour that a persona may inadvertently engage in as a result of webinos. The *design issues* section describes facets of webinos functionality that raise questions about how the persona might use or misuse it.

5.1.5. Elicit references and misusability case characteristics

The next step involves connecting assumptions about the world with planned actions that address them. These assumptions, which were initially identified in the previous step, are modelled as references. These references act as grounds, warrants, or rebuttals that connect individual assumptions to a misusability case characteristic. These characteristics are modelled using the Toulmin's model of argumentation, and laid out in the same way as persona characteristics in WP 2.7. There are, however, two main differences. First, affinity modelling is not carried out to identify these characteristics. The activities leading up to and including the reference elicitation stage should provide a sufficient grounding in the data which means such characteristics can be elicited without additional sense-making support. Second, it is expected

that emerging characteristics may lead to new insights about supporting references. In the Policy Conflict misusability case example, the *Builds policies in the office* task characteristic lead to insights suggesting that policy editing tools might be designed for use in an office/desktop environment, rather than the ubiquitous/mobile environment where Gloria may want to edit policies. Consequently, additional references were elicited to gather supporting grounds for additional task characteristics, e.g. *Policy editing too cumbersome for mobiles*.

5.1.6. Author misusability cases

Based on these references, possible plot devices for a misusability case narrative are identified around the misusability case characteristics. The activities associated with authoring a misusability case are very similar to those for *tasks* described in the Task overview section of the WP 2.7 deliverable, i.e. the use cases associated with the contributing requirements need to be satisfied in the narrative text, the consequences of the misusability case need to be described, together with the usability breakdown for the persona/s involved in the misusability case.

5.1.7. Re-evaluate requirements

The final stage involves re-evaluating the requirements based on the misusability case. This involves identifying the considering how the requirements have been obstructed in such a way as to make the misusability case possible, and, based on these *obstructions*, modifying existing requirements or proposing new requirements to resolve the misusability case. Based on this re-evaluation, recommendations can be made for other webinos work-packages.

5.2. Gloria

5.2.1. Persona factors

Gloria is someone that personalises her online experience by setting application preferences, but also, for privacy reasons, retains separate online identities. Gloria currently uses these separate identities in different physical and social contexts; this means that, at any given time, Gloria should be aware of what identity she is using. Because webinos is designed to free Gloria of the burden of manually switching identity based on context, there is a danger that, if not properly configured, Gloria may get confused about which identity she is currently using when engaging with online services. An analogy for this might be using a mobile device which has been setup with details for 2 wifi networks, each of which covers a specific, disjoint geographic areas. Gloria's device may switch from one wifi network to another, but Gloria may be unaware of this switch because her primary activity may be contingent on these wifi networks. In the case of webinos, however, if Gloria sets up her device to move between personal zones without

any intervention on her part, she may not be aware which identity is exposed unless her activities are such that she would be conscious of an identity switch.

5.2.2. Design issues

Because Gloria is the most likely persona to specify policies on an a priori basis, Gloria is likely to engage in all use cases and alternative courses associated with policy viewing and management. However, even after Deliverable 3.1 and 3.5, there are several open questions about how the sorts of policies Gloria might create, the editors that Gloria might use for creating and editing these, and in what contexts these policies might be edited.

5.2.3. Related misusability cases

- Policy conflict

5.3. Jessica

5.3.1. Persona factors

Because it helps sustain user satisfaction and build trust, privacy is of particular interest to Jessica. Surprisingly, however, rather than privacy driving the requirements for accessibility of medical data, it is the provision of accessible medical data that appears to influence Jessica's privacy concerns, as do adhering to explicit security requirements.

Jessica's concerns about control of device capabilities appear to drive the need for managing software application risks, i.e. those risks which compromise the functionality of her applications, rather than risks arising from security and privacy concerns. Ironically, it is this fine-grained control of device capabilities and a preference for native application development which challenge her goal of developing secure, multi-platform applications. This, in turn, also challenges her perceptions about the importance of privacy.

5.3.2. Design issues

Jessica's desire to control device capabilities may lead her, as a native developer, to find ways of using over-permissive APIs to access low-level functionality that circumvents normal access controls. Moreover, a lack of specific guidances for developing distributed mobile web-apps may lead to multiple problems, such as the inappropriate use of design patterns, or the adoption of insecure coding practices that support these mis-applied patterns.

5.3.3. Related misusability cases

- From health monitoring to botnet control

5.4. Justin

5.4.1. Persona factors

A circular dependency is evident when considering the relationships between Justin's own personal goals. Because he personalises his online experience, Justin shares personal data as a means for leveraging his social networks. This, in turns, increases Justin's trust in technology, making him more likely to share personal data with 3rd parties. Because Justin shares personal data with 3rd parties, his general propensity for sharing personal data grows. This circular dependency is partially sustained by Justin's security indifference, as it is this that contributes to Justin's desire to leverage social networks. Because of Justin's trust in technology, the dependency is also partially sustained by Justin's ability to install mobile apps on an adhoc basis and his ability to schedule his diary using his mobile device.

5.4.2. Design issues

The use case for installing and updating webinos application don't appear to situated with Justin's active diary and his continual multi-tasking of activities. Although such installation makes Justin's ability to multi-task harder, this inconvenience is not significant enough for Justin to pause and rethink his indifference towards security.

5.4.3. Related misusability cases

- Unsafe application install

5.5. Helen

5.5.1. Persona factors

Helen is pragmatic in her use of technology she sometimes trades contextual information unwisely, inadvertently sharing contextual information with home devices.

With young children prone to make "mistakes" leaves tasks half finished. As coping strategy for a busy life style she adopts a fixed regime makes her behaviour predictable, therefore exposed to certain types of attack

Helens husbands city job means that the home IT infrastructure, could be a "desirable" asset to attackers

5.5.2. Design issues

Helen is likely to take a path of least resistance, assuming things are OK until proven otherwise, therefore good default policies essential. Also because of this behaviour, mistakes will inevitably happen therefore the ability to impose retrospective mechanism, eg. revoke privillage, delete data is essential.

Helens, home and work personas/data appear to easily blur. Good sandboxing of work/personal data would insulate Helen against undesirable privacy leakage. Helen seems to rely strongly on "tools" to help organise herself. Data such as a calendar becomes highly important. Good data integrity and backup become critical

5.5.3. Related misusability cases

- Insecure sharing of data

5.6. Jimmy

5.6.1. Persona factors

Jimmy is an ambitious professional software developer who loves writing mobile applications and who is always keen on getting in touch with latest technology. This is why he is also interested in writing webinos applications. Jimmy is a pragmatist. Thus he just sits down and tries things out rather than spending time on learning the essentials of a technology he uses. This bears some danger, incorrect assumptions about a system's architecture may lead to decisions which are disadvantageous from security perspective. In order to get security right, knowing the underlying security architecture is crucial. With that respect, Jimmy is a bit lazy.

5.6.2. Design issues

Because of his attitude towards theoretic grounds of systems, Jimmy picks up inappropriate architectural patterns and styles. Since he does not double check his assumptions, he does not notice if there are vulnerabilities introduced by his design decisions for his applications.

5.6.3. Related Misusability Cases

- Vulnerable webinos application

5.7. Clara

5.7.1. Persona factors

Clara is a typical teenager, she lives with her parents and likes to have fun and live care-free. One exception is that she has diabetes, which she manages by herself using modern technology such as her smartphone, her laptop and cloud services. However, because of Clara's care-free nature, her diabetes management is often neglected, which is dangerous to her health. She often forgets to measure her glucose level and bypasses her health-monitoring applications when enjoying some time out with friends. Like most typical teenagers, privacy is of lesser concern to her, and so she needs guidance in order to prevent inadvertent sharing of privacy-sensitive data.

5.7.2. Design issues

- Should a minor be able to manage access rights to his medical data?
- If Clara were to uninstall the application, should her physician be informed?
- The user and the owner of a device might not be the same person.

5.7.3. Related misusability cases

- Insecure sharing of data

5.8. Misusability Cases

Following various telephone and email discussions about the persona and design issues between March and August 2011, the misusability cases below were elicited.

Recommendations that tackle the problems raised by these misusability cases are proposed in the next section.

5.8.1. From health monitoring to botnet control

5.8.1.1 Environment

Development and Deployment

5.8.1.2 Overview

Jessica ports an existing distributed application to webinos with unexpected results.

5.8.1.3 Narrative

Jessica has developed a proprietary doctor and patient monitoring application; this the same application used by Clara.

A lack of primer for developing distributed webinos apps for classic mobile developers means that Jessica hacked a simple hello world application and ported her existing application idioms to webinos.

As Jessica was primarily concerned with the IP in the monitoring application, she focused her security and privacy concerns on the monitoring app, but set copy protection to child apps to ensure not IP leaked out that way.

Jessica submitted her application to the Appstore without any problems.

Ethan was aware of how effective the IPC mechanisms in webinos might be for botnets so he is scanning the app store for new apps that might be vulnerable. He comes upon Jessica's app.

Ethan finds an unexample of unvalidated input in the client app which allows an XSS to have access to its internals. With some manipulation, he is able to steal session data from another app and eventually own the entire monitoring infrastructure.

Ethan develops what appears to be a complementary app that might appeal to purchasers of Jessica's app. Although the app is functionally useful, it does contain obfuscated code which allows the app to act as a conduit between the monitoring app and Ethan's own command and control infrastructure for monitoring botnets.

After a few days, the app instances begin to notify him of owned monitoring networks.

5.8.1.4 Realised use cases

- WOS-UC-TA3-004: Embedding Proprietary Extensions
- WOS-UC-TA5-002: Execute the application from the web or another device
- WOS-UC-TA5-003: Installation and update of webinos applications

5.8.1.5 Usability breakdown

Persona	Jessica
Duration	Hours or longer

Frequency	Monthly or less
Demands	High
Goal Conflict	Medium

5.8.1.6 Consequences

- The implicit trust placed on developers with regards to support for native code extensions appeals to Jessica. Unfortunately, the lack of guidance for working at both high and low levels of abstraction means that Jessica is unaware of intrinsic vulnerabilities in web application development.

5.8.1.7 Characteristics

- Runtime implicitly trusts developers
 - Modal Qualifier: Possibly
 - Grounds
 - Applications installed in one go
 - Applications contain nested applications.
 - Applications are up-to-date before execution.
 - Warrant
 - No distributed application patterns
 - Rebuttal
 - None
- Developer intent circumventable
 - Modal Qualifier: Perhaps
 - Grounds
 - Proprietary extensions used
 - Applications contain nested applications.
 - Child and parent apps available programmatically.
 - Warrant
 - Copy protection stops webinos supported shared
 - Rebuttal
 - None
- Extensibility hacking encouraged
 - Modal Qualifier: Possibly

- Grounds
 - Proprietary extensions used
 - Applications instances spread across devices.
 - Widget specification extensible.
 - Application launched via events.
 - Warrant
 - No distributed application patterns
 - Rebuttal
 - None
- Applications secretly launched and run
 - Modal Qualifier: Probably
 - Grounds
 - Autostart programmatically controlled
 - Simplified communication between sub-applications.
 - Application launched via events.
 - Warrant
 - Daemonic applications
 - Rebuttal
 - None

5.8.2. Policy conflict

5.8.2.1 Environment

Context and Events

5.8.2.2 Overview

After meticulously creating context-sensitive Webinos policies from her office, Gloria finds herself unexpectedly customising her policies while on the go.

5.8.2.3 Narrative

Gloria had just finished putting the finishing touches to her office and shopping webinos privacy policy before realising she had to pop over to the Starbucks across the road to catch up with one of friends from university. She saved her settings and closed down the privacy dashboard from her PC before grabbing her phone and heading out.

As she was about to enter Starbucks, her mobile phone began to buzz in her bag. On examining it, she saw a message from Webinos saying that a request for Starbucks to access her preferential data had been refused. Gloria thought she had forgotten to set this up in her shopping context, so she fired up the Webinos privacy dashboard on her HTC to modify this. As she scrolled around the screen, trying to find the option to add the service, she realised that policy editing was much easier on the 27 inch iMac in her office. After another minute of imaginary screen pinching, she eventually found the option to add a rule allowing Starbucks to the objects visible to this policy. As she entered the rule, she noticed the webinos provided explanatory text describing the impact of adding this rule, but it was barely legible given its size in comparison to the other editor controls. No matter, Gloria thought, Starbucks could only do so much damage given her shopping policy anyway. After adding the rule, Gloria went into Starbucks to catch up with her friend.

5.8.2.4 Realised use cases

- WOS-UC-TA8-001: Receiving local messages and alerts
- WOS-UC-TA8-006: End-User Policy Viewing and Management
- WOS-UC-TA8-007: Policy authoring tools

5.8.2.5 Usability breakdown

Persona	Gloria
Duration	Minutes
Frequency	Monthly or less
Demands	Medium
Goal Conflict	High

5.8.2.6 Consequences

- Gloria was still in her work context when the Starbucks message arrived. Gloria did not realise this, so she inadvertently allowed Starbucks access to all the data in her work policy.
- The explanatory information for adding this text was illegible.
- What if the message was not from Starbucks but from somebody purporting to be Starbucks?

5.8.2.7 Characteristics

- Constructs coarse grained policy from fine-grained rules
 - Modal Qualifier: Definitely
 - Grounds
 - Keeps work and personal life separate in her online identities
 - Editors support fine and coarse grained policy editing.
 - Policies contain fine-grained rules.
 - Sophisticated policy editing tools.
 - Warrant
 - Has a second privacy policy for not being observable
 - Rebuttal
 - None

- Builds policies in the office
 - Modal Qualifier: Perhaps
 - Grounds
 - Policy decision maker at the e-book store.
 - Sophisticated policy editing tools.
 - Warrant
 - None
 - Rebuttal
 - None

- Privacy policy betrayed
 - Modal Qualifier
 - Possibly
 - Grounds
 - Interested in promotions and special deals of her preferred shops.
 - Consciously sets privacy settings.
 - Warrant
 - Applications may ignore policy changes.
 - Rebuttal
 - None

- Policy editing too cumbersome for mobiles
 - Modal Qualifier
 - Possibly
 - Grounds

- Policies contain fine-grained rules.
- Policy impact is described textually
- Webinos explains policy setting refusals.
- Warrant
 - Sophisticated policy editing tools.
- Rebuttal
 - None
- Webinos notifies user when out-of-context
 - Modal Qualifier
 - Possibly
 - Grounds
 - User alerted on policy warning.
 - Warrant
 - APIs throw errors when access control request denied.
 - Rebuttal
 - None

5.8.3. Unsafe application install

5.8.3.1 Environment

Development and Deployment

5.8.3.2 Overview

Justin installs a new diary app without realising its implications.

5.8.3.3 Narrative

Having just chatted to some of his friends on the phone to arrange a meet-up after work, Justin realises he isn't very happy with current diary arrangements and the need to synchronise between his phone, tablet, and laptop.

On his way to work one morning, Justin browses the app store and discovers a webinos app that allows him to keep all of his diaries in sync automatically. Justin assumes this might simply be a cloud-based scheduler, but he likes the look of the UI on the app store so, although he is on the train and doesn't have a huge amount of time before his train pulls in, he decides to download and setup this app on his tablet now as it appears to be quite small.

Justin started up the app for the first time, expecting to have to install existing data from his phone's calendar. He wasn't disappointed, but first Justin was asked to walk through several webinos dialogues asking him to set up things called "personal devices" and "personal zones". Justin didn't know anything about what these were so, because he was on the go, he clicked through every dialog until the application started up.

After lunch that day, Justin was sat at his desk and browsing his twitter feed using his tablet. He was suddenly reminded about his meet-up that day and his need to check the time. As he was about to reach for his jacket and his phone to check his diary, he remember the new diary app he installed. As such, he decided to give this new app a go by checking his diary using his tablet. Again, he had to download the app, click through several dialog boxes to install some sort of special runtime environment and provide more user names and passwords. This time, things seemed a bit more annoying because he had to remember some arbitrary login details he had created on the fly while installing the app to his phone while on the train. Eventually, though, the app was installed and he could check the meet-up time.

5.8.3.4 Realised use cases

- WOS-UC-TA5-003: Installation and update of webinos applications

5.8.3.5 Usability breakdown

Persona	Justin
Duration	Minutes
Frequency	Monthly or less
Demands	Low
Goal Conflict	Medium

5.8.3.6 Consequences

- Nothing is currently said about how the initial installation of webinos dependencies will take place, and the impact this might have on user's patience.
- The developers intention could be interpreted as the default intention the user should take. In this case, Justin isn't aware of exactly what he has given the app permission to access.

5.8.3.7 Characteristics

- Installation interferes with other activities
 - Modal Qualifier
 - Possibly
 - Grounds
 - Acknowledge target device.
 - Warrant
 - Uses mobile phone to organise life.
 - Uses mobile phone for complex tasks.
 - Rebuttal
 - None

- Installation interferes with other activities
 - Modal Qualifier
 - Possibly
 - Grounds
 - Installs a third-party application.
 - Shares personal data with BMW.
 - Warrant
 - Early adopter of technology.
 - Rebuttal
 - None

- Attracted to aesthetically pleasing apps
 - Modal Qualifier
 - Possibly
 - Grounds
 - Buys a pink car.
 - Warrant
 - Installs a third party application.
 - Uses and contributes to online social networks.
 - Rebuttal
 - None

5.8.4. Vulnerable webinos application

5.8.4.1 Environment

Development and Deployment

5.8.4.2 Overview

Due to an ill assumption, Jimmy decides he can skip input validation in his webinos application which opens-up a cross-site scripting vulnerability in his application.

5.8.4.3 Narrative

Jimmy is an ambitious professional software developer who is always interested in new technologies. Thus he also tries webinos. As he likes interconnected devices, he is fond of webinos' inter-device communication capabilities. He ports one of his applications (called *ZenSearch*) for webinos. This application is both a client frontend for the search service on the Internet and a media push service for the TV. The user uses *ZenSearch* for finding nice royalty-free pictures on the Internet. These pictures are transferred to the client and then pushed to the TV to display them there in full screen mode.

Jimmy is a practitioner. He rather starts experimenting and he learns from examples instead of reading the documentation and understanding the philosophy behind it. As a consequence, he is not familiar with the architecture and the security concept of webinos, as well as the security guidelines provided by the project.

Jimmy makes an ill assumption about webinos' architecture and unintentionally makes an architectural decision for his application which opens an attack vector. He assumes that input validation is not necessary in his application. Actually, by porting his existing client application to webinos, he does not pay enough attention to architectural changes which are needed. He just quickly decides that the TV does not expose a critical API which could result in serious damage when being misused. Thus he does not spend enough thoughts on security and he does not notice that input validation is required. Consequently, he introduces a cross-site scripting vulnerability (XSS) in the *ZenSearch* client application. It allows an attacker, who can manipulate the content of a Web site which is found by the search service, to execute arbitrary JavaScript code on the *ZenSearch* client's device.

The attack works as follows. The search service presents search results of Web sites which contain the pictures. Each of these Web sites may contain JavaScript code. The search service has a XSS vulnerability where the URLs of found Web sites are not sanitised properly. A specially crafted URL which contains JavaScript code is forwarded to the *ZenSearch* client without any filtering. An attacker prepares a Web site with thousands of royalty-free pictures to provide these specially crafted URLs. Due to Jimmy's decision, the *ZenSearch* client application also does not validate the URLs and the content of the Web sites which are received by the application upon search request. If the search results contain JavaScript, the code is executed by the

ZenSearch client application. Webinos transparently establishes a communication channel with other devices when a remote API is accessed. Depending on the security policy under which the ZenSearch client application is executed, an attacker can cause more or less serious damage by calling various remote APIs. One example of such damage is that the user clicks a link on the search results with injected JavaScript code. This code calls the Contacts API of another device which belongs to the same personal zone. This device is found by using webinos' Discovery API. It then accesses the contacts on that device and sends them all out to the attacker's email address without the consent of the user.

Jimmy's mistake was to assume that his ZenSearch client application cannot be a risk for the user, as it only pushes the pictures to the TV without obtaining any data from the TV. As a consequence, Jimmy thought, an attacker cannot reveal or manipulate any user data. He has overlooked that the injected code of the attacker can also establish a communication channel to another device in the personal zone of the user.

5.8.4.4 Related use cases

- WOS-UC-TA1-004: Communication between webinos devices
- WOS-UC-TA1-008: webinos Federation
- WOS-UC-TA1-012: Bridging to the home network

Related scenario: WOS-US-2.2: Creating Applications for webinos

5.8.4.5 Usability breakdown

Persona	Jimmy
Duration	Minutes or shorter
Frequency	as often as the application is used
Demands	Medium
Goal Conflict	Low

5.8.4.6 Consequences

- The attacker can remote control the webinos-enabled device and execute arbitrary JavaScript code. This opens an avenue for manifold severe attacks.
- Using the application is a risk for the user even though the application itself is harmless.

5.8.4.7 Characteristics

- Ports his existing application to webinos
 - Modal Qualifier: Definitely
 - Grounds
 - Writes ZenSearch Application
 - Application consists of front-end and back-end part
 - Ports this application to webinos
 - Warrant
 - None
 - Rebuttal
 - None

- Is an experienced and enthusiastic software developer
 - Modal Qualifier: Definite
 - Grounds
 - Likes writing mobile applications
 - Likes interconnecting devices
 - Is interested in new technologies
 - Warrant
 - None
 - Rebuttal
 - None

- Bases his decisions on assumptions without reassuring them
 - Modal Qualifier: Definite
 - Grounds
 - Does not pay attention on concepts
 - Likes trying things out and learns from examples
 - Warrant
 - None
 - Rebuttal
 - None

- Misses to see an attack vector due to focusing on his application's architecture
 - Modal Qualifier: Probably
 - Grounds
 - Does not pay attention on concepts
 - Likes trying things out and learns from examples

- Considers security as annoying and restrictive
- Warrant
 - None
- Rebuttal
 - Is a professional software developer

5.8.5. Insecure sharing of data

5.8.5.1 Environment

Context and Events

5.8.5.2 Overview

Because of her care-free nature and the bad security of the diabetes management application, Clara unknowingly shares her data with a friend.

5.8.5.3 Narrative

Clara is a typical care-free teenager. Privacy is of little concern to her and she wants her phone to be usable immediately, instead of having to type in passwords or use other security measures, even when sensitive data is involved. Because of this her phone and thus the data on the phone is not protected in a secure manner.

When going out with her friends, one of them wants to play the newest multiplayer Webinos game with Clara. To do this, Clara wants to add her friend's PZ as a trusted PZ to her own PZ. They go to this process very quickly, just clicking through the dialogs that appear, without reading what the consequences are. In this process, Clara unknowingly shared her contextual data with her friend, who can now gain access to her medical file and even add other people to the list of people that can get access to it.

After Clara and her friend are done playing, her friend continues to use his smartphone to look up some soccer scores. While he is doing this he notices he can gain access to new data. He does this and notices that he can access Clara's confidential records. When both of them are going home, he tells her he didn't know her glucose values are so high and warns her to be careful with this.

5.8.5.4 Related use cases

- WOS-UC-TA4-014: Continuous sharing of a medical file through webinos enabled devices

Related scenario: WOS-US-2.2: Creating Applications for webinos

5.8.5.5 Usability breakdown

Persona	Clara
Duration	Minutes or shorter
Frequency	Once
Demands	Low
Goal Conflict	High

5.8.5.6 Consequences

- Clara's personal data is compromised, at first only to her friend

5.8.5.7 Characteristics

- Diabetes data is stored in Clara's PZ
 - Modal Qualifier: Possibly
 - Grounds
 - Applications can store context data
 - Context data is stored in the user's Personal Zone
 - Warrant
 - None
 - Rebuttal
 - None
- Adding another Personal Zone as trusted Zone is inherently insecure
 - Modal Qualifier: Maybe
 - Grounds
 - Context data is stored in the user's Personal Zone
 - Warrant
 - None
 - Rebuttal

- None
- Data in the Personal Zone is shared (too) easily
 - Modal Qualifier: Maybe
 - Grounds
 - Context data can be shared
 - Webinos Runtime can set dynamic access control policies for data sharing
 - Warrant
 - None
 - Rebuttal
 - None

5.9. Recommendations

For subsequent webinos activities, we propose the following recommendations based on persona and design issues, and related misusability cases.

5.9.1. Develop patterns and best practice for webinos application developers

The results suggest that application developers need heuristic support in the form of best practice patterns or idioms, particularly when working with both low-level and high-level abstractions. In the short term, these should be demonstrated using the concept applications currently under development. The results also suggest that experienced web developers may treat webinos as "just another Javascript framework", who expects to learn webinos based on API documentation and sample source code alone. However, in such cases, developers may fall foul of security vulnerabilities which are more potent in cross-device environments associated with webinos. For this reason, best practice guidelines for application developers should be produced by the project as a dissemination activity.

5.9.2. Develop webinos best practice for end-users

The results also seem to suggest that the Personal Zone metaphor isn't entirely clear to end-users. Moreover, younger users may be not used to considering the privacy implications associated with their online activity, while privacy-conscious users may not aware of how to develop and modify context-sensitive privacy policies. The Unsafe Application Install misusability case also highlighted the dangers that are likely to arise if due consideration isn't given to how both the webinos runtime and personal zones are setup. In particular, if not properly managed,

habituation may lead to weak personal zone security if users confuse application privacy settings with settings for a user's entire personal zone.

While webinos may be visible to many users only through the applications they use, dissemination activities should consider ways that webinos can be usefully used during the everyday activities.

6 Conclusion

6.1. Summary of findings

6.1.1. Users and developers need better support for applying context

webinos provides a platform for both developers to build context-sensitivity into their applications, and users to ensure that their web application experience matches their security and privacy expectations. Unfortunately, results from the misuse case, misusability case, and focus groups suggest that leaving users and developers to unpack the notion of context on their own may inadvertently lead to the introduction of security and privacy vulnerabilities.

Because context is difficult to explicate, where context-sensitive data or functionality is used in webinos, specific guidance about how to apply context-sensitivity or interpret context-sensitive results needs to be provided in both the webinos platform and applications that rely on it. The recommendations arising from the focus group propose 3 recommendations for policy authors to follow when incorporating context. To validate these recommendations and help identify further idioms and styles for applying context, the guidelines should be used to evaluate the design of policy controls used for the initial webinos concept apps.

6.1.2. webinos education for users and developers

webinos not only inherits the opportunities afforded by building on existing web frameworks and standards, but also the vulnerabilities associated with them. In some cases, the webinos security architecture mitigates some common web application security risks, others are introduced as a result of the affordances introduced by the webinos architecture itself, e.g. the overlay network and the context model. Several misuse and misusability cases are introduced by mis-interpreting how webinos should be developed, e.g. capture hidden analytics, and from health monitoring to botnet control, as well as used, e.g. Exploit network bandwidth, and policy conflict. Because understanding a new metaphor with new concepts is prone to error, the release of webinos and webinos applications should be accompanied with best-practice about how webinos should be used.

6.1.3. Usability requirements for policy management tools

By adding an additional layer of abstraction to web application development, webinos has implicitly introduced tool requirements for maintaining this infrastructure. In particular, the responsibility for meeting user security and privacy policy expectations is distributed between application developers, end-users, and the webinos platform itself.

Based on the results in the focus groups, end-users need structured guidance for building a priori policies, which is driven by contexts of use relevant to webinos applications, rather than by objects and subjects in the policies themselves. Moreover, controls for editing policies need to be supplemented with additional information to allow policy authors to frame their thinking in the same working context as the developer of the original policy. Arguably, this finding will not be new to developers and administrators who have been required to deduce or manage application policies on behalf of users. However, the addition of a new metaphor (the personal zone) and the difficulties associated with specifying policies around context mean that webinos' need to deal with usable policy specification and management is now more urgent than ever.

6.2. Exploitation of deliverable

6.2.1. Security Architecture: Work Package 3.5

This work package can benefit from the deliverable by providing risks that need to be responded to by the security architecture. Further rationale for these risks can be provided by reading the misuse cases contextualising them, and the risk analysis data motivating them. Additionally, the results and recommendations from the focus group provide guidance for any policy management functionality developed as part of this work-package.

For convenience, the table below summarises the current mitigation status of the elicited risks. Risks that are fully mitigated have been prevented or avoided due to design decisions in WP 3.1 and WP 3.5. Risks that are partially mitigated have been partially addressed in the aforementioned work-packages, but additional analysis is needed to identify missing mitigating requirements. Risks that are not mitigated either cannot be mitigated due to the nature of environments webinos is situated in. Alternatively, these risks can be mitigated only by adding additional components over and above the scope of the current webinos architecture.

More details about proposed recommendations are given the Misuse Case Analysis recommendations section.

Risk	Mitigation (Full / Partial / None)
Capture hidden analytics	Partial
Control cloud-based PZH	Partial
Multimedia stream availability position	Partial
Online fraud with webinos payment API	None

Overlay network facilitated attack	Partial
Playback service accountability issue	Full/Partial
Steal webinos session	Partial
Unauthorized access to sensitive data	Partial
Unprotected transmission	Partial
Untrusted car mechanic	Partial
Use of other people's service	Partial

6.2.2. Development of Webinos: Work Package 4

Because the risk analysis results underpinning the misuse case are aligned with webinos architectural components, misuse cases form the basis of security test scripts. To do this, the vignettes described in the deliverable need to be refined to a set of attacker steps, similar to the template in (SIOP2005).

Several possible security testing tools for supporting the automated or semi-automated running of such scripts are reviewed in (HOWA2008).

Additionally, like Work Package 3.5, the focus group results provide guidance for the interface design of policy management functionality developed as part of this work-package.

6.2.3. Development of Webinos Applications: Work Package 5

This work package benefits from this deliverable in several ways.

First, similar to Work Package 4, misuse cases relating to specific applications can form the basis of security test scripts. Moreover, the misuse case responses provide a useful aide-memoire to concept application developers for preventing to likely security risks.

Second, when used in conjunction with the personas in Work Package 2.7, the persona and design issues & misusability cases provide insight into how concept application users might misinterpret the intent of concept app developers.

Third, focus group discussion and recommendation provides considerations when developing interfaces for application-specific security policies. Finally, several focus groups were centred

around the *Kids in Focus* concept application. As such, data from this focus group may be a useful source of requirements during further design and development of this application.

6.2.4. Dissemination: Work Package 7

While the research problem motivating the focus group research was motivated by design issues in the webinos architecture, the underlying policy management usability issues are generally applicable. Qualitative data analysis of the focus group report lead to findings that informed the future information architecture of webinos policy management tools, but analysis of the raw focus group transcripts may lead to more generalisable findings on the usability of security policy development.

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8 Appendix 1: Environment values and tensions

8.1. Development and Deployment

8.1.1. Confidentiality

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the secrecy of applications, application data, configuration data or policy.
Low	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy leads to limited disclosure of assets or data held on these assets to unauthorised individuals, entities, or processes.
Medium	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy leads to periodic disclosure of assets or data held on these assets to unauthorised individuals, entities, or processes.
High	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy leads to regular disclosure of assets or data held on these assets to unauthorised individuals, entities, or processes.

8.1.2. Integrity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the unwanted modification of applications, application data, configuration data or policy.
Low	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to unwanted asset modification causing minor data inaccuracy or incompleteness.
Medium	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to unwanted asset modification causing significant data inaccuracy or incompleteness.
High	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to unwanted asset modification causing major data inaccuracy or incompleteness.

8.1.3. Availability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the unwanted withholding of applications, application data,

	configuration data or policy.
Low	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy leads to unwanted withholding of applications, application data, configuration data or policy, causing irregular reduction of asset accessibility or usability.
Medium	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy leads to unwanted withholding of applications, application data, configuration data or policy, causing occasional reduction of asset accessibility or usability.
High	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy leads to regular withholding of applications, application data, configuration data or policy, causing major reduction of asset accessibility or usability.

8.1.4. Accountability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the traceability of an entity's actions on applications, application data, configuration data or policy, and vice-versa.
Low	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy may lead to reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity.
Medium	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy leads to periodically reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity.
High	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy leads to severely reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity.

8.1.5. Anonymity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the disclosure of a subject's identity when managing applications, application data, configuration data or policy.
Low	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy leads to a minor disclosure of data about a subject's identity.
Medium	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy leads to a disclosure of data significant enough to potentially render the data's

	subject identifiable.
High	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy leads to a disclosure of data which can, with the minimum of effort, render the data's subject identifiable.

8.1.6. Pseudonymity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the degradation to a person's identity or its accountability level when managing applications, application data, configuration data or policy.
Low	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy may lead to reduced or diminished identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa.
Medium	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy leads to periodically reduced or diminished identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa.
High	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy leads to the loss of identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa.

8.1.7. Unlinkability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning additional asset usage linkability afforded to others as a consequence of design decisions about applications, application data, configuration data or policy.
Low	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy introduces insignificant asset usage linkability affordances to others.
Medium	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy introduces noticeable asset usage linkability affordances to others.
High	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy introduces significant asset usage linkability affordances to others.

8.1.8. Unobservability

Value	Interpretation
None	No values concerning additional subject observability afforded to others as a consequence of design decisions about applications, application data, configuration data or policy.
Low	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy introduces insignificant subject observability affordances to others.
Medium	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy introduces noticeable subject observability affordances to others.
High	Improper management of applications, application data, configuration data or policy introduces significant subject observability affordances to others.

8.1.9. Security & Privacy Value Tensions

	An	Pan	Unl	Uno
C	-	-	-	-
I	-	-	-	-
Av	-	-	-	-
Ac	-	-	-	-

From developer perspective, there are no privacy issues in the Development and Deployment asset model. The developer intends to disclose the application, its configuration, its resource access requests and the intentions of use of personal data of the user. Thus there are no tensions between security and privacy.

Security Value	Privacy Value	Tension	Rationale
Confidentiality	any	-	No tensions. See above explanation.
Integrity	any	-	No tensions. See above explanation.
Availability	any	-	No tensions. See above explanation.
Accountability	any	-	No tensions. See above explanation.

8.2. Context and Events

8.2.1. Confidentiality

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the secrecy of assets storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events, or data held on these assets.
Low	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to limited (one-time) disclosure of assets or data held on these assets to unauthorised individuals, entities or processes.
Medium	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to periodic disclosure of assets or data held on these assets to unauthorised individuals, entities or processes.
High	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to regular disclosure of assets or data held on these assets to unauthorised individuals, entities or processes.

8.2.2. Integrity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the accuracy or completeness of assets storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events.
Low	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to minor asset or asset data inaccuracy or incompleteness.
Medium	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to significant asset or asset data inaccuracy or incompleteness.
High	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to major asset or asset data inaccuracy or incompleteness.

8.2.3. Availability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the on-demand accessibility and usability of assets storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events.

Low	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to irregular reduction of asset accessibility or usability.
Medium	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to occasional reduction of asset accessibility or usability.
High	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to regular reduction of asset accessibility or usability.

8.2.4. Accountability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the traceability of an entity's actions when assets store or collect context data or send/receive events.
Low	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events may lead to reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity.
Medium	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to periodically reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity.
High	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to loss or severely diminished traceability to an accountable entity.

8.2.5. Anonymity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the identity disclosure while storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events.
Low	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to a minor disclosure of data about a subject's identity.
Medium	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to a disclosure of data significant enough to potentially render the data's subject identifiable.
High	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to a disclosure of data which can, with the minimum of effort, render the data's subject identifiable.

8.2.6. Pseudonymity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the degradation to a user's identity or its accountability level when storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events.
Low	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events may lead to reduced or diminished identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa.
Medium	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to the periodically reduced or diminished identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa.
High	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to the loss of identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa.

8.2.7. Unlinkability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning additional asset usage linkability afforded to others by storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events.
Low	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events introduces insignificant asset usage linkability affordances to others.
Medium	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to noticeable asset usage linkability affordances to others.
High	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events leads to significant asset usage linkability affordances to others.

8.2.8. Unobservability

Value	Interpretation
None	No values concerning additional subject observability afforded to others by storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events.
Low	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events introduces insignificant subject observability affordances to others.
Medium	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events introduces noticeable

	subject observability affordances to others.
High	Storing or collecting context data or sending/receiving events introduces significant subject observability affordances to others.

8.2.9. Security & Privacy Value Tensions

	An	Pan	Unl	Uno
C	-	-	+	+
I	?	-	?	?
Av	?	?	?	?
Ac	-	?	-	-

Security Value	Privacy Value	Tension	Rationale
Confidentiality	Anonymity	-	Anonymity introduces the risk of compromising confidentiality (by leaking sensitive data to anonymous users)
Confidentiality	Pseudonymity	-	Pseudonymity enhances confidentiality of user data
Confidentiality	Unlinkability	-	Unlinkability enhances confidentiality of user data
Confidentiality	Unobservability	-	Unobservability enhances confidentiality of user data
Integrity	Pseudonymity	-	Pseudonymity reduces the integrity of user related data
Accountability	Anonymity	-	Anonymity reduces accountability
Accountability	Unobservability	-	Making a user unobservable reduces accountability
Accountability	Unlinkability	-	Design decisions related to accountability may lead to degraded unlinkability, e.g. context data

8.3. Profile Management

8.3.1. Confidentiality

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the secrecy of identities or sessions.
Low	Improper management of identities and shared sessions leads to limited disclosure of assets or data held on these assets to unauthorised individuals, entities, or processes.
Medium	Improper management of identities and shared sessions leads to periodic disclosure of assets or data held on these assets to unauthorised individuals, entities, or processes.
High	Improper management of identities and shared sessions leads to regular disclosure of assets or data held on these assets to unauthorised individuals, entities, or processes.

8.3.2. Integrity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the unwanted modification of identities or sessions.
Low	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to unwanted asset modification causing minor data inaccuracy or incompleteness.
Medium	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to unwanted asset modification causing significant data inaccuracy or incompleteness.
High	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to unwanted asset modification causing major data inaccuracy or incompleteness.

8.3.3. Availability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the unwanted withholding of identities or sessions.
Low	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to unwanted withholding of identities or sessions, causing irregular reduction of asset accessibility or usability.
Medium	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to unwanted withholding of identities or sessions, causing occasional reduction of asset accessibility or usability.

High	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to regular withholding of identities or sessions, causing occasional reduction of asset accessibility or usability.
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8.3.4. Accountability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the traceability of an entity's actions on identity and sessions, and vice-versa.
Low	Improper management of identities and sessions may lead to reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity.
Medium	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to periodically reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity.
High	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to severely reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity.

8.3.5. Anonymity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the disclosure of personal identities when managing asset identities and sessions.
Low	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to a minor disclosure of data about a subject's identity.
Medium	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to a disclosure of data significant enough to potentially render the data's subject identifiable.
High	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to a disclosure of data which can, with the minimum of effort, render the data's subject identifiable.

8.3.6. Pseudonymity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the degradation to a person's identity or its accountability level when managing asset identities and sessions.
Low	Improper management of identities and sessions may lead to reduced or diminished

	identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa.
Medium	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to periodically reduced or diminished identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa.
High	Improper management of identities and sessions leads to the loss of identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa.

8.3.7. Unlinkability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning additional asset usage linkability afforded to others as a consequence of design decisions about asset identities and sessions.
Low	Improper management of identities and sessions introduces insignificant asset usage linkability affordances to others.
Medium	Improper management of identities and sessions introduces noticeable asset usage linkability affordances to others.
High	Improper management of identities and sessions introduces significant asset usage linkability affordances to others.

8.3.8. Unobservability

Value	Interpretation
None	No values concerning additional subject observability afforded to others as a consequence of design decisions about asset identities and sessions.
Low	Improper management of identities and sessions introduces insignificant subject observability affordances to others.
Medium	Improper management of identities and sessions introduces noticeable subject observability affordances to others.
High	Improper management of identities and sessions introduces significant subject observability affordances to others.

8.3.9. Security & Privacy Value Tensions

	An	Pan	Unl	Uno
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I	?	?	?	?
Av	?	-	?	?
Ac	?	?	?	?
Security Value	Privacy Value	Tension	Rationale	
Availability	Pseudonymity	-	If there is a risk that availability may be degraded then pseudonymity asset values may err towards compromising subject identity over linkability.	

8.4. Home Media and Interactive TV

8.4.1. Confidentiality

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the secrecy of media playback services or preferences
Low	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to limited disclosure of assets or data held in these assets to unauthorized individuals, entities or processes
Medium	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to periodic disclosure of assets or data held in these assets to unauthorized individuals, entities or processes
High	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to regular disclosure of assets or data held in these assets to unauthorized individuals, entities or processes

8.4.2. Integrity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the modification of media playback services or preferences
Low	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to asset modification causing minor data inaccuracy or incompleteness

Medium	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to asset modification causing significant data inaccuracy or incompleteness
High	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to asset modification causing major data inaccuracy or incompleteness

8.4.3. Availability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the withholding of media playback services or preferences
Low	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to the withholding of asset, causing irregular reduction of asset accessibility or usability
Medium	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to the withholding of asset, causing occasional reduction of asset accessibility or usability
High	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to the withholding of asset, causing regular reduction of asset accessibility or usability

8.4.4. Accountability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the traceability of an entity's action on media playback services or preferences, and vice-versa
Low	Improper management of media playback services or preferences may lead to reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity
Medium	Improper management of media playback services or preferences may lead to periodically reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity
High	Improper management of media playback services or preferences may lead to severely reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity

8.4.5. Anonymity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the disclosure of subject's identity when managing media playback services or preferences

Low	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to a minor disclosure of data about a subject's identity
Medium	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to a disclosure of data significant enough to potentially render the data's subject identifiable
High	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to a disclosure of data which can, with the minimum of effort, render the data's subject identifiable

8.4.6. Pseudonymity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the degradation to a person's identity or its accountability level when managing media playback services or preferences
Low	Improper management of media playback services or preferences may lead to reduced or diminished identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa
Medium	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to periodically reduced or diminished identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa
High	Improper management of media playback services or preferences leads to the loss of identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa

8.4.7. Unlinkability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning additional asset usage linkability afforded to others as a consequence of design decisions about media playback services or preferences
Low	Improper management of media playback services or preferences introduces insignificant asset usage linkability affordances to others
Medium	Improper management of media playback services or preferences introduces noticeable asset usage linkability affordances to others
High	Improper management of media playback services or preferences introduces

	significant asset usage linkability affordances to others
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8.4.8. Unobservability

Value	Interpretation
None	No values concerning additional subject observability afforded to others as a consequence of design decisions about media playback services or preferences
Low	Improper management of media playback services or preferences introduces insignificant subject observability affordances to others
Medium	Improper management of media playback services or preferences introduces noticeable subject observability affordances to others
High	Improper management of media playback services or preferences introduces significant subject observability affordances to others

8.4.9. Security & Privacy Value Tensions

	An	Pan	Unl	Uno
C	?	?	?	?
I	?	?	?	?
Av	?	?	?	?
Ac	-	?	-	-

Security Value	Privacy Value	Tension	Rationale
Accountability	Anonymity	-	User anonymity may hinder accountability
Accountability	Unlinkability	-	Resource usage unlinkability may hinder accountability
Accountability	Unobservability	-	User unobservability may hinder accountability

8.5. Navigation Asset Values

8.5.1. Confidentiality

Value	Description
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None	No values concerning the secrecy of navigation services or data
Low	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to limited disclosure of assets or data held in these assets to unauthorized individuals, entities or processes
Medium	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to periodic disclosure of assets or data held in these assets to unauthorized individuals, entities or processes
High	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to regular disclosure of assets or data held in these assets to unauthorized individuals, entities or processes

8.5.2. Integrity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the modification of navigation services or data
Low	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to asset modification causing minor data inaccuracy or incompleteness
Medium	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to asset modification causing significant data inaccuracy or incompleteness
High	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to asset modification causing major data inaccuracy or incompleteness

8.5.3. Availability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the withholding of navigation services or data
Low	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to the withholding of asset, causing irregular reduction of asset accessibility or usability
Medium	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to the withholding of asset, causing occasional reduction of asset accessibility or usability
High	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to the withholding of asset, causing regular reduction of asset accessibility or usability

8.5.4. Accountability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the traceability of an entity's action on navigation services or data, and vice-versa
Low	Improper management of navigation services or data may lead to reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity
Medium	Improper management of navigation services or data may lead to periodically reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity
High	Improper management of navigation services or data may lead to severely reduced or diminished traceability to an accountable entity

8.5.5. Anonymity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the disclosure of subject's identity when managing navigation services or data
Low	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to a minor disclosure of data about a subject's identity
Medium	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to a disclosure of data significant enough to potentially render the data's subject identifiable
High	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to a disclosure of data which can, with the minimum of effort, render the data's subject identifiable

8.5.6. Pseudonymity

Value	Description
None	No values concerning the degradation to a person's identity or its accountability level when managing navigation services or data
Low	Improper management of navigation services or data may lead to reduced or diminished identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa
Medium	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to periodically reduced or diminished identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa

High	Improper management of navigation services or data leads to the loss of identity privacy at the cost of accountability or vice-versa
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8.5.7. Unlinkability

Value	Description
None	No values concerning additional asset usage linkability afforded to others as a consequence of design decisions about navigation services or data
Low	Improper management of navigation services or data introduces insignificant asset usage linkability affordances to others
Medium	Improper management of navigation services or data introduces noticeable asset usage linkability affordances to others
High	Improper management of navigation services or data introduces significant asset usage linkability affordances to others

8.5.8. Unobservability

Value	Interpretation
None	No values concerning additional subject observability afforded to others as a consequence of design decisions about navigation services or data
Low	Improper management of navigation services or data introduces insignificant subject observability affordances to others
Medium	Improper management of navigation services or data introduces noticeable subject observability affordances to others
High	Improper management of navigation services or data introduces significant subject observability affordances to others

8.5.9. Security & Privacy Value Tensions

	An	Pan	Unl	Uno
C	?	?	?	?
I	?	?	?	?

Av	?	?	?	?
Ac	-	?	-	-
Security Value	Privacy Value	Tension	Rationale	
Accountability	Anonymity	-	User anonymity may hinder accountability	
Accountability	Unlinkability	-	Resource usage unlinkability may hinder accountability	
Accountability	Unobservability	-	User unobservability may hinder accountability	

8.6. Shopping asset values

8.6.1. Confidentiality

Value	Description
None	When shopping, there is no need to keep any shopping and payment information secret. Any payment information can be made publicly available.
Low	Only in a few shopping cases the shopping and payment information must be kept secret, because the information could be personally sensitive, or open up for attackers.
Medium	In about half of the shopping cases, the shopping and payment information must be kept secret, because the information could be personally sensitive, and it encourages attackers.
High	In all shopping cases, the shopping and payment information must be kept very secure from unsolicited access by other users, attackers, or any other third parties.

8.6.2. Integrity

Value	Description
None	There is no need to ensure the integrity of the payment software nor the shopping and payment information originating from it.
Low	Only a bit of the payment software and shopping and payment information will need to be kept accurate and complete.

Medium	About half of the payment software and/or shopping and payment information will need to be kept accurate and complete.
High	All of the payment software and/or the shopping and payment information must be kept accurate and complete.

8.6.3. Availability

Value	Description
None	There is no need to ensure the availability of the payment software or the shopping and payment information at any point.
Low	Only in a few shopping cases, the payment software or the shopping and payment information must be guaranteed available for the user.
Medium	In about half of the shopping cases, the payment software or the shopping and payment information must be guaranteed available for the user.
High	In all shopping cases, the payment software or the shopping and payment information must be guaranteed available for the user.

8.6.4. Accountability

Value	Description
None	There is no need to be able to trace a user's payment/ shopping information.
Low	Incorrect shopping and payment information could in some cases lead to less traceability of an accountable user's shopping actions.
Medium	Incorrect shopping and payment information will periodically lead to less traceability of an accountable user's shopping actions.
High	Incorrect shopping and payment information will cause severely limited traceability of an accountable user's shopping actions.

8.6.5. Anonymity

Value	Description
None	There is no need to anonymise the shopping and payment information.

Low	In only a few shopping cases there is a need to anonymise the shopping and payment information so that the user can't be identified.
Medium	In about half of the shopping cases there is a need to anonymise the shopping and payment information so that the user can't be identified.
High	In most - if not all - shopping cases there is a need to anonymise the shopping and payment information so that the user can't be identified.

8.6.6. Pseudonymity

Value	Description
None	There is no need to operate with user pseudonyms when managing a user's shopping and payment information.
Low	Only in a few shopping cases there is a need to operate with pseudonyms to reduce the visibility of the user's identity.
Medium	In about half of the shopping cases there is a need to operate with pseudonyms to reduce the visibility of the user's identity.
High	In most - if not all - shopping cases it is necessary to operate with pseudonyms to reduce the visibility of the user's identity.

8.6.7. Unlinkability

Value	Description
None	There is no need to unlink users from their shopping and payment information.
Low	In a few shopping cases it is needed to unlink users from their shopping and payment information.
Medium	In about half of the shopping cases it is necessary to unlink users from their shopping and payment information.
High	In most - if not all - shopping cases it is necessary to unlink users from their shopping and payment information.

8.6.8. Unobservability

Value	Interpretation
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None	There is no need to ensure the unobservability of a user's shopping and payment information.
Low	In a few shopping cases it is needed to ensure that no other user nor third party can observe the user's shopping and payment information.
Medium	In a about half of the shopping cases it is necessary to ensure that no other user nor third party can observe the user's shopping and payment information.
High	In most - if not all - shopping cases it is necessary to ensure that no user nor third party can observe the user's shopping and payment information.

8.6.9. Security & Privacy Value Tensions

	Anonymity	Pseudonymity	Unlinkability	Unobservability
Confidentiality	?	?	?	?
Integrity	?	?	?	?
Availability	?	?	?	?
Accountability	?	?	?	?

Security Value Privacy Value Tension Rationale

9 Appendix 2: Focus group supplemental data

9.1. Helen Focus Group 1

9.1.1. Scenario

9.1.1.1 Introductions

You have recently won a car which is fitted with a new internet enabled in-vehicle entertainment system, together with a free one year subscription to one of the new 4G data provider. This system is a little like an aircraft in-flight entertainment system as it provides access to game, videos, and journey specific data such as where you are, how far you are from your destination, etc. However, unlike aircraft entertainment systems, these games can be played online with other people, and videos can be streamed from your own home entertainment system library. Moreover, internet based audio and visual streaming is also supported which allows passengers to talk in real time to other people, and collaborate on activities such as games. However, from the stories you've heard in the media, you know that with great power comes responsibility. Therefore, before you and your family use this system, you need to think about its security and privacy implications.

To do this, we will develop a model indicating how data in this system should or should not be used, by whom, and in what contexts. This model will take the form an affinity diagram that will be built up progressively over a number of stages. When complete, this model will be used to design security controls which will allow your passengers to take advantage of this new system, without being taken intentionally or unintentionally taken advantage of.

Please remember that this exercise is being built around you and what you would allow, so do think about yourself and not about what others think or rather than what you think others in your group might expect.

9.1.1.2 Object clustering

To celebrate your windfall, you and your family are planning to drive up to Scotland for a week long holiday, and you hope the new in-car entertainment system will keep the kids quiet on the journey. You plan to connect the system to your home entertainment system which contains a number of films that your kids can watch, and they will also be able to download games from your home entertainment system, as well as other compatible gaming sites as well.

The first part of this exercise will involve thinking about different aspect of the system which need to be controlled. Using the yellow post-it note pads, please list concepts associated with this system and add them to the whiteboard. Please feel to discuss your concepts with your colleagues, or remove any duplicated concepts. You should also cluster these items as you and

your group see fit. Using the orange post-it notes provided, each cluster should be labelled with a term or phrase which you feel best characterises it.

9.1.1.3 Subject clustering

After speaking to your parents about the trip and your plans to keep your kids occupied, they mentioned that they have a compatible entertainment system. This potentially allows them to play games with your children, as well as talking to them at the same time. This seems like a good way to connect your parents to their grand-children while, simultaneously, keeping them occupied. However, thinking about sharing with other people also gets you thinking about who or what else the system might be sharing information with as well.

In this part of the exercise, you should begin by noting on the board or flipchart the people or groups with an interest in the entertainment system and the data it has access to. For each of these people or groups, and starting with your own children, you should label the person/group name on a green and red post-it note, add these notes to the white-board, and re-cluster the information according to what these groups should and should not have access to. If you think of new items then you are welcome to add these as the exercise progresses.

9.1.1.4 Context clustering

Having thought about this policy a great deal, it dawns on you that subtle variations in the context within which the car and its in-car entertainment system is used might lead you re-think some of the decisions you have already made. For example, would this model still be the same if you loaned your car out to a friend and they used it to take their children away, or if you handed your car over to a garage to do repairs on the car or entertainment system. In this part of the exercise, you should write down different contexts where the in-car entertainment system might get used. These should be written on the light blue post-it notes provided. If you think of new data items or new people who should or should not be allowed access to data then this can be added as necessary. Like the previous stages, if you think of new data items or new people who should or should not have access to data then these should be added as necessary.

9.1.2. Participant match to persona characteristics

Characteristic	Characteristic Type	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3
A Sales & Marketing manager	Activities	N	N	N
A professional	Activities	N	N	N

commuter				
Patterns of behaviour planned	Activities	Y	Y	Y
Is Family-centered	Attitudes	Y	Y	Y
Maintains a work-life split	Attitudes	Y	Y	Y
Keeps busy	Aptitudes	Y	Y	Y
Shares data to manage schedule	Motivations	Y	Y	N
Prepared to share her contextual data	Context & Events Security & Privacy Issues	N	N	Y

9.2. Helen Focus Group 2

9.2.1. Scenario

The Scenario was the same proposed by Oxford. The only difference has been translation to Italian for adapting to native focus group language

9.2.1.1 Introductions

9.2.1.1.1 English

You have recently won a car which is fitted with a new internet enabled in-vehicle entertainment system, together with a free one year subscription to one of the new 4G data provider. This system is a little like an aircraft in-flight entertainment system as it provides access to game, videos, and journey specific data such as where you are, how far you are from your destination, etc. However, unlike aircraft entertainment systems, these games can be played online with other people, and videos can be streamed from your own home entertainment system library. Moreover, internet based audio and visual streaming is also supported which allows passengers to talk in real time to other people, and collaborate on activities such as games. However, from the stories you've heard in the media, you know that with great power comes responsibility. Therefore, before you and your family use this system, you need to think about its security and privacy implications.

To do this, we will develop a model indicating how data in this system should or should not be

used, by whom, and in what contexts. This model will take the form an affinity diagram that will be built up progressively over a number of stages. When complete, this model will be used to design security controls which will allow your passengers to take advantage of this new system, without being taken intentionally or unintentionally taken advantage of.

Please remember that this exercise is being built around you and what you would allow, so do think about yourself and not about what others think or rather than what you think others in your group might expect.

9.2.1.1.2 Italian

Hai vinto di recente una macchina con un innovativo sistema di intrattenimento in grado di connettersi a Internet, con allegato un anno di abbonamento gratuito ad un nuovo provider 4G. Il sistema è simile al sistema di intrattenimento presente su alcuni voli di linea, in quanto fornisce accesso a giochi, video, dati sul viaggio (es: dove ti trovi in questo momento, quanto è lontana la destinazione, etc). A differenza dei sistemi presenti sui voli di linea, questi giochi possono essere giocati con altri giocatori on-line, ed i video possono essere messi in stream dal sistema della macchina stesso. Sono supportati anche contenuti internet audio e video. Ciò significa che i passeggeri dell'auto possono parlare in tempo reale con altre persone, e collaborare in attività remote, oltre che giocare assieme.

C'è un però! Dalle storie che appaiono di frequente sui media generalisti, sai che con grande potere vengono grandi responsabilità. Quindi, prima che tu e la tua famiglia iniziate ad usare questo sistema, è necessario riflettere attentamente sulle implicazioni di sicurezza informatica e di privacy.

A questo scopo, svilupperemo un modello per indicare come i dati debbano o non debbano essere usati, da chi, ed in quale contesto. Questo modello prenderà la forma di un "affinity diagram" che verrà costruito in alcuni passi successivi. Una volta completo, questo modello sarà usato per progettare i controlli di sicurezza che permetteranno agli utenti legittimi del sistema di trarne beneficio, senza divenirne vittima (ad opera di comportamento errato sia intenzionale sia involontario).

Ricorda che questo esercizio viene svolto da te sulla base delle cose che tu permetteresti o no, quindi esprimi le tue opinioni, e non cosa gli altri partecipanti si aspettano (o tu pensi si aspettino) riguardo i concetti da elaborare.

9.2.1.2 Object clustering

9.2.1.2.1 English

To celebrate your windfall, you and your family are planning to drive up to Provence for a week long holiday, and you hope the new in-car entertainment system will keep the kids quiet on the journey. You plan to connect the system to your home entertainment system which contains a

number of films that your kids can watch, and they will also be able to download games from your home entertainment system, as well as other compatible gaming sites as well.

The first part of this exercise will involve thinking about different aspect of the system which need to be controlled. Using the yellow post-it note pads, please list concepts associated with this system and add them to the whiteboard. Please feel to discuss your concepts with your colleagues, or remove any duplicated concepts. You should also cluster these items as you and your group see fit. Using the orange post-it notes provided, each cluster should be labelled with a term or phrase which you feel best characterises it.

9.2.1.2.2 Italian

Per celebrare l'inaspettata macchina nuova, tu e la tua famiglia state pensando di guidare fino in Provenza per una settimana turistica, sperando al contempo che il nuovo sistema di intrattenimento della macchina possa tenere buoni i bambini durante il viaggio. Inoltre hai in mente di collegare il sistema della macchina con il tuo sistema home-theatre casalingo, il quale contiene un sacco di film che piacciono ai ragazzi. Per i tuoi ragazzi potresti anche scaricare dei giochi dal tuo sistema casalingo, come anche collegarti a siti di giochi con lo stesso obiettivo di gioco on-line o di downloading di altre applicazioni.

La prima fase di questo esercizio richiederà di pensare ai differenti aspetti dell'applicazione che necessitano di esser controllati. Usando i post-it gialli, per favore elenca i concetti associati con questo sistema e aggiungili alla superficie/lavagna. Sei assolutamente libero di discutere i tuoi concetti con gli altri partecipanti, o di rimuovere concetti duplicati. Puoi anche raggruppare questi concetti nel modo che tu ed i tuoi compagni di gruppo ritenete opportuno. Usa i post-it arancioni per etichettare il gruppo con un termine o una breve frase che descriva cosa caratterizzi il gruppo stesso.

9.2.1.3 Subject clustering

9.2.1.3.1 English

After speaking to your parents about the trip and your plans to keep your kids occupied, they mentioned that they have a compatible entertainment system. This potentially allows them to play games with your children, as well as talking to them at the same time. This seems like a good way to connect your children to their grand-parents while, simultaneously, keeping them occupied. However, thinking about sharing with other people also gets you thinking about who or what else the system might be sharing information with as well.

In this part of the exercise, you should begin by noting on the board or flipchart the people or groups with an interest in the entertainment system and the data it has access to. For each of these people or groups, and starting with your own children, you should label the person/group name on a green and red post-it note, add these notes to the white-board, and re-cluster the information according to what these groups should and should not have access to. If you think of new items then you are welcome to add these as the exercise progresses.

9.2.1.3.2 Italian

Dopo aver parlato con i tuoi genitori del viaggio e dei tuoi piani per tenere i bambini quieti, sei venuto a scoprire che anche i tuoi genitori hanno un entertainment system compatibile. Questo potenzialmente permette ai tuoi figli di giocare con i nonni e comunque di interagire e parlare con loro durante il viaggio. Ottimo! Questo sembra una buon modo per far crescere la relazione tra i tuoi genitori ed i tuoi figli... e nel frattempo tenerli occupati.

Pensando a questo tipo di condivisione, inizi anche a pensare con chi o quali altre informazioni potresti volere il tuo sistema condivida.

In questa parte dell'esercizio, tu dovresti iniziare ad annotare le persone o i gruppi con un interesse nell'applicazione e nei dati cui hanno accesso. Per ciascuno di queste persone o gruppo dovresti etichettare il nome della persona/gruppo su di un post-it verde e rosso, aggiungendo queste note sulla lavagna/superficie, a procedere ad un nuovo raggruppamento delle informazioni sulla base di come questi gruppi dovrebbero o non dovrebbero potervi accedere. Se pensi che nuovi concetti debbano essere introdotti, aggiungili pure man mano che l'esercizio procede.

9.2.1.4 Context clustering

9.2.1.4.1 English

Having thought about this policy a great deal, it dawns on you that subtle variations in the context within which the car and its in-car entertainment system is used might lead you re-think some of the decisions you have already made. For example, would this model still be the same if you loaned your car out to a friend and they used it to take their children away, or if you handed your car over to a garage to do repairs on the car or entertainment system. In this part of the exercise, you should write down different contexts where the in-car entertainment system might get used. These should be written on the light blue post-it notes provided. If you think of new data items or new people who should or should not be allowed access to data then this can be added as necessary. Like the previous stages, if you think of new data items or new people who should or should not have access to data then these should be added as necessary.

9.2.1.4.2 Italian

A questo punto dell'esercizio, potrebbe esser emerso come variazioni nel contesto d'uso dell'applicazione possano portarti a ripensare alcune delle decisioni prese in precedenza. Per esempio, il modello sarebbe lo stesso se tu prestassi la tua macchina ad un amico (e, ad esempio lui la usasse per fare una gita coi suoi bambini)? O se lasciassi la tua macchina dal meccanico per fargli riparare il sistema di entertainment?

In questa parte dell'esercizio, pensa a "contesti" differenti in cui l'applicazione potrebbe essere usata. Questi dovrebbero essere scritti sui post-it blu. Se tu pensassi che nuovi dati o nuove persone dovrebbero o meno avere accesso a certi dati, aggiungili pure quando richiesto.

9.2.2. Participant match to persona characteristics

Characteristic	Characteristic Type	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3
A Sales & Marketing manager	Activities	N	N	N
A professional commuter	Activities	N	N	N
Patterns of behaviour planned	Activities	Y	Y	Y
Is Family-centered	Attitudes	Y	Y	Y
Maintains a work-life split	Attitudes	Y	Y	Y
Keeps busy	Aptitudes	N	N	Y
Shares data to manage schedule	Motivations	Y	Y	Y
Prepared to share her contextual data	Context & Events Security & Privacy Issues	Y	Y	N

9.3. Helen Focus Group 3

9.3.1. Scenario

The Scenario was the same proposed by Oxford. The only difference has been translation to German for adapting to native focus group language.

9.3.1.1 Introductions

9.3.1.1.1 English

You have recently won a car which is fitted with a new internet enabled in-vehicle entertainment system, together with a free one year subscription to one of the new 4G data provider. This system is a little like an aircraft in-flight entertainment system as it provides access to game, videos, and journey specific data such as where you are, how far you are from your destination, etc. However, unlike aircraft entertainment systems, these games can be played online with other people, and videos can be streamed from your own home entertainment system library. Moreover, internet based audio and visual streaming is also supported which allows passengers to talk in real time to other people, and collaborate on activities such as games. However, from the stories you've heard in the media, you know that with great power comes responsibility. Therefore, before you and your family use this system, you need to think about its security and privacy implications.

To do this, we will develop a model indicating how data in this system should or should not be used, by whom, and in what contexts. This model will take the form an affinity diagram that will be built up progressively over a number of stages. When complete, this model will be used to design security controls which will allow your passengers to take advantage of this new system, without being taken intentionally or unintentionally taken advantage of.

Please remember that this exercise is being built around you and what you would allow, so do think about yourself and not about what others think or rather than what you think others in your group might expect.

9.3.1.1.2 German

Sie haben vor kurzem versehentlich ein Auto gewonnen, dass mit einem Internet im Fahrzeug-Entertainment-System ausgestattet ist, zusammen mit einem kostenlosen 1 Jahr Abonnement für einen der neuen 4G-Datenanbieter. Dieses System ist ein wenig wie ein Flugzeug in-flight-Entertainment-System, wie es den Zugang zu Spielen ermöglicht, Videos und Reisedaten anbietet, die zeigen wo Sie sind, wie weit Sie von Ihrem Ziel entfernt sind, etc. Im Gegensatz zu Flugzeugen-Entertainment-Systemen, Spiele können online mit anderen Personen gespielt werden, und Videos können von Ihrer eigenen Home-Entertainment-System-Bibliothek

gestreamt werden. Darüber hinaus ist das Internet-basierte Audio- und Video-Streaming unterstützt, die Passagiere können in Echtzeit mit anderen Leuten reden, und können gemeinsam an Aktivitäten wie Spiele arbeiten. Doch aus den Geschichten, die Sie in den Medien gehört haben, wissen Sie, dass mit großer Macht auch die Verantwortung kommt. Daher, bevor Sie und Ihre Familie mit diesem System fahren, müssen Sie über seine Sicherheit und Auswirkungen auf den Datenschutz nachdenken.

Um dies zu tun, werden wir ein Modell entwickeln, das angibt, wie Daten in diesem System verwendet oder nicht verwendet werden sollen, von wem und in welchen Kontexten. Dieses Modell wird in Form eines Affinitäts-Diagramm erstellt, bis dahin wird schrittweise über mehrere Stufen ein Diagramm aufgebaut. Wenn Sie fertig sind, wird dieses Modell verwendet, um Sicherheitskontrollen zu identifizieren.

Bitte denken Sie daran, dass diese Übung durch Ihre Gruppe motiviert wird, es ist interessant was andere denken und es ist besser als das, was Sie denken, als das was andere in Ihrer Gruppe vielleicht erwarten.

9.3.1.2 *Object clustering*

9.3.1.2.1 English

To celebrate your windfall, you and your family are planning to drive up to Provence for a week long holiday, and you hope the new in-car entertainment system will keep the kids quiet on the journey. You plan to connect the system to your home entertainment system which contains a number of films that your kids can watch, and they will also be able to download games from your home entertainment system, as well as other compatible gaming sites as well.

The first part of this exercise will involve thinking about different aspect of the system which need to be controlled. Using the yellow post-it note pads, please list concepts associated with this system and add them to the whiteboard. Please feel to discuss your concepts with your colleagues, or remove any duplicated concepts. You should also cluster these items as you and your group see fit. Using the orange post-it notes provided, each cluster should be labelled with a term or phrase which you feel best characterises it.

9.3.1.2.2 German

Zur Feier Ihres Jahrestages, planen Sie und Ihre Familie, bis in die Provence für einen einwöchigen Urlaub zu fahren, und Sie hoffen, dass das neue In-Car-Entertainment-System Ihre Kinder ruhig auf der Reise in den Sitzen halten wird. Sie planen, das System an Ihr Home-Entertainment-System anzuschließen, das eine Reihe von Filmen, die Ihre Kinder schauen können, zu verbinden. Und sie werden auch in der Lage sein, Spiele von Ihrem Home-

Entertainment-System herunterzuladen sowie andere kompatiblen Spiele-Websites zu konsumieren.

Der erste Teil der Übung wird folgendes beinhalten. Denken Sie über die verschiedenen Aspekte des Systems nach, die kontrolliert werden müssen. Mit den gelben Post-it Notizblöcken, geben Sie bitte Konzepte an, die mit diesem System verbunden sind und fügen Sie diese an die Pinnwand. Bitte zögern Sie nicht, Ihre Konzepte mit Ihren Kollegen zu diskutieren, oder entfernen Sie alle doppelten Konzepte. Sie sollten auch Cluster dieser Konzepte bilden, die Sie und Ihre Gruppe für richtig halten und mit dem orangenen Post-it Notizblock beschriften, die jeweiligen Cluster sollten mit einem Begriff oder Satz, der diese am besten charakterisiert gekennzeichnet werden.

9.3.1.3 Subject clustering

9.3.1.3.1 English

After speaking to your parents about the trip and your plans to keep your kids occupied, they mentioned that they have a compatible entertainment system. This potentially allows them to play games with your children, as well as talking to them at the same time. This seems like a good way to connect your children to their grand-parents while, simultaneously, keeping them occupied. However, thinking about sharing with other people also gets you thinking about who or what else the system might be sharing information with as well.

In this part of the exercise, you should begin by noting on the board or flipchart the people or groups with an interest in the entertainment system and the data it has access to. For each of these people or groups, and starting with your own children, you should label the person/group name on a green and red post-it note, add these notes to the white-board, and re-cluster the information according to what these groups should and should not have access to. If you think of new items then you are welcome to add these as the exercise progresses.

9.3.1.3.2 German

Nach dem Gespräch mit den Eltern über die Reise und Ihre Pläne, erwähnten Sie, dass sie ein kompatibles Entertainment-System haben. Dieses ermöglicht es ihnen, Spiele mit Ihren Kindern zu spielen, sowie mit Ihnen zur gleichen Zeit zu sprechen. Dies scheint ein guter Weg, um Ihre Kinder mit ihren Großeltern zu verbinden.

In diesem Teil der Übung sollten Sie mit der Feststellung auf dem Flipchart beginnen, um Personen oder Gruppen zu identifizieren, welche Interesse an dem Entertainment-System haben. Und im Weiteren die Daten zu identifizieren, auf welche Sie Zugriff haben. Für jede

dieser Personen oder Gruppen sollten Sie die Person / Gruppe auf einem grünen und roten Post-it schreiben. Fügen Sie diese auf das White-Board, und re-clustern Sie die Informationen nach wozu diese Gruppen keinen bzw. Zugang haben sollten. Wenn Sie über neue Konzepte nachdenken, dann fügen Sie diese hinzu.

9.3.1.4 Context clustering

9.3.1.4.1 English

Having thought about this policy a great deal, it dawns on you that subtle variations in the context within which the car and its in-car entertainment system is used might lead you re-think some of the decisions you have already made. For example, would this model still be the same if you loaned your car out to a friend and they used it to take their children away, or if you handed your car over to a garage to do repairs on the car or entertainment system. In this part of the exercise, you should write down different contexts where the in-car entertainment system might get used. These should be written on the light blue post-it notes provided. If you think of new data items or new people who should or should not be allowed access to data then this can be added as necessary. Like the previous stages, if you think of new data items or new people who should or should not have access to data then these should be added as necessary.

9.3.1.4.2 German

Denken Sie über einen anderen Kontext nach, in dem das Home-Entertainment-System verwendet werden kann. Zum Beispiel sollten Kinder nur begrenzten Zugriff auf Filme haben, da diese altersbeschränkt sind, weil sie jugendgefährdende Inhalte enthalten. Versuchen Sie, mit unterschiedlichen Rollen von Eltern und Kindern zu experimentieren. In diesem Teil der Übung sollten Sie notieren, welche unterschiedlichen Kontexte es gibt, in denen das Home-Entertainment-System genutzt werden kann. Diese sollte auf den hellblauen Post-its geschrieben werden. Wenn Sie neuen Daten oder neue Personen identifizieren, welche Zugriff / keinen Zugriff auf die Daten haben, dann sollten diese bei Bedarf hinzugefügt werden.

9.3.2. Participant match to persona characteristics

Characteristic	Characteristic Type	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3
A Sales & Marketing manager	Activities	?	?	?
A professional commuter	Activities	?	?	?

Patterns of behaviour planned	Activities	?	?	?
Is Family-centered	Attitudes	?	?	?
Maintains a work-life split	Attitudes	?	?	?
Keeps busy	Aptitudes	?	?	?
Shares data to manage schedule	Motivations	?	?	?
Prepared to share her contextual data	Context & Events Security & Privacy Issues	?	?	?

9.4. Jimmy Focus Group 1

9.4.1. Scenario

9.4.1.1 Introductions

Oxford's Software Engineering site has long been the front-shop for advertising the programme by allowing both current and prospective students to learn more about the programme, as well as registering for courses and degrees. As more and more people are moving to smart phones, it seems sensible to think turning about the Software Engineering site into a mobile web app which will allow them to do this without being tied to a desktop PC or laptop. Such an app would not only be better augmented with the back-end systems for managing student and course information, but also lead to possibilities for integrating learning management systems like Sakai to facilitate teaching activities as well. With the aid of webinos, the possibilities become even greater as overlay networks might facilitate discussions and sharing of information in group exercises, as well as the ability for content to be seamless customised based on the most appropriate platform. For example, TAs might be able to use the app to control the installation of course specific material from any device which can run the webinos runtime.

However, such an app leads to threats as well as opportunities, so it's useful to think about the app's security and privacy implications now before starting any detailed design. To do this, we will develop a model indicating how data in this system should or should not be used, by whom, and in what contexts. This model will take the form an affinity diagram that will be built up progressively over a number of stages. When complete, this model will be used to design security controls which will allow your passengers to take advantage of this new system, without being taken intentionally or unintentionally taken advantage of.

Please remember that this exercise is being built around you and what you would allow, so do think about yourself and not about what others think or rather than what you think others in your group might expect.

9.4.1.2 Object clustering

It has been decided to pilot this system by thinking about how it might be used to support the delivery of the Software Development Management course module. The vision will be that the app will support the browsing and booking of courses, but will also support facilities required by lecturers and administrators such as recording information about course delegates, the upload of courseware, and its distribution to machines in the course teaching room.

The first part of this exercise will involve thinking about different aspect of the app which need to be controlled. Using the yellow post-it note pads, please list concepts associated with this system and add them to the whiteboard. Please feel to discuss your concepts with your colleagues, or remove any duplicated concepts. You should also cluster these items as you and your group see fit. Using the orange post-it notes provided, each cluster should be labelled with a term or phrase which you feel best characterises it.

9.4.1.3 Subject clustering

From the initial clustering exercise, it should become clear that different people have a stake in the app for different reasons, ranging from students, lecturers, administrators, assessors, and maybe even proctors. In this part of the exercise, you should begin by noting on the board or flip-chart the people or groups with an interest in the app and the data it has access to. For each of these people or groups, starting with course attendees, you should label the person/group name on a green and red post-it note, add these notes to the white-board, and re-cluster the information according to what these groups should and should not have access to. If you think of new items then you are welcome to add these as the exercise progresses.

9.4.1.4 Context clustering

Having thought about this policy a great deal, it dawns on you that subtle variations in the context where the app is used might lead you re-think some of the decisions you have already made. For example, if a TA was at home or out and about in Oxford while running the app, would you want him/her to have the capability of installing content on teaching machines. In this part of the exercise, you should write down different contexts where the app might get used. These should be written on the light blue post-it notes provided. If you think of new data items or new people who should or should not be allowed access to data then this can be added

as necessary. Like the previous stages, if you think of new data items or new people who should or should not have access to data then these should be added as necessary.

9.4.2. Participant match to persona characteristics

Characteristic	Characteristic Type	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3
Focused on mobile and web development	Activities	N	Y	N
Passionate and experienced professional software developer	Activities	Y	Y	Y
Passionate and successful blogger	Activities	N	N	N
Knows what he wants and chooses tool-chain and architectural design accordingly	Attitudes	Y	Y	Y
Prefers open source	Attitudes	Y	Y	Y
Follows a pragmatic hands-on design and implementation approach	Aptitudes	Y	Y	Y
Is self-employed	Aptitudes	N	N	N
Knows how to do business with his applications	Aptitudes	N	N	Y
Stays up-to-date on various technologies	Aptitudes	Y	Y	N
Is fond of gadgets which interact on his home network	Motivations	Y	Y	N
Is comfortable with developing low-level functional details	Skills	Y	Y	Y

9.5. Jimmy Focus Group 2

9.5.1. Jimmy scenario politico

The Scenario was the same proposed by Oxford. The only difference has been translation to Italian for adapting to native focus group language

9.5.1.1 Introductions

9.5.1.1.1 English

Oxford's Software Engineering site has long been the front-shop for advertising the programme by allowing both current and prospective students to learn more about the programme, as well as registering for courses and degrees. As more and more people are moving to smart phones, it seems sensible to think turning about the Software Engineering site into a mobile web app which will allow them to do this without being tied to a desktop PC or laptop. Such an app would not only be better augmented with the back-end systems for managing student and course information, but also lead to possibilities for integrating learning management systems like Sakai to facilitate teaching activities as well. With the aid of webinos, the possibilities become even greater as overlay networks might facilitate discussions and sharing of information in group exercises, as well as the ability for content to be seamless customised based on the most appropriate platform. For example, TAs might be able to use the app to control the installation of course specific material from any device which can run the webinos runtime.

However, such an app leads to threats as well as opportunities, so it's useful to think about the app's security and privacy implications now before starting any detailed design. To do this, we will develop a model indicating how data in this system should or should not be used, by whom, and in what contexts. This model will take the form an affinity diagram that will be built up progressively over a number of stages. When complete, this model will be used to design security controls which will allow your passengers to take advantage of this new system, without being taken intentionally or unintentionally taken advantage of.

Please remember that this exercise is being built around you and what you would allow, so do think about yourself and not about what others think or rather than what you think others in your group might expect.

9.5.1.1.2 Italian

Il sito web del gruppo di ingegneria del software di Oxford da lungo tempo permette allo studente di interagire ed avere informazioni sul programma dei vari corsi correlati, come anche di registrarsi ai corsi ed agli esami. Grazie alla diffusione sempre più massiccia di smart-phone, sembra strategico trasformare il sito anche in una applicazione web per mobile, che permetta

agli studenti di interagire senza aver bisogno di un desktop o di un laptop. Questa applicazione potrebbe non solo essere migliorata con un back-end per gestire informazioni inerenti gli studenti e i corsi, ma anche permettere l'integrazione di sistemi di e-learning come Sakai per facilitare le attività di insegnamento. Con l'ausilio di Webinos, le possibilità aumentano ulteriormente in quanto l'infrastruttura di webinos potrebbe facilitare discussioni e condivisione di informazioni in gruppi di studio, così come permettere l'adattamento del contenuto in base alla piattaforma di fruizione, in modo trasparente. Per esempio, un professore potrebbe usare l'applicazione per controllare l'installazione di materiale specifico per il proprio corso da qualsiasi device "webinos enabled".

Una simile applicazione porta non solo opportunità, ma anche possibili minacce. Diventa così importante pensare alle implicazioni di sicurezza e privacy, prima di iniziare lo sviluppo vero e proprio. Per far questo, svilupperemo un modello per indicare come i dati debbano o non debbano essere usati, da chi, ed in quale contesto. Questo modello prenderà la forma di un "affinity diagram" che verrà costruito progressivamente in alcuni passi successivi. Una volta completo, questo modello sarà usato per progettare i controlli di sicurezza che permetteranno agli utenti legittimi del sistema di trarne beneficio, senza divenirne vittima (ad opera di comportamento errato sia intenzionale che non). Ricorda che questo esercizio viene svolto da te sulla base delle cose che tu permetteresti o no, quindi esprimi le tue opinioni, e non cosa gli altri partecipanti si aspettano (o tu pensi si aspettino) riguardo i concetti da elaborare.

9.5.1.2 Object clustering

9.5.1.2.1 English

It has been decided to pilot this system by thinking about how it might be used to support the delivery of the Software Development Management course module. The vision will be that the app will support the browsing and booking of courses, but will also support facilities required by lecturers and administrators such as recording information about course delegates, the upload of courseware, and its distribution to machines in the course teaching room.

The first part of this exercise will involve thinking about different aspects of the app which need to be controlled. Using the yellow post-it note pads, please list concepts associated with this system and add them to the whiteboard. Please feel free to discuss your concepts with your colleagues, or remove any duplicated concepts. You should also cluster these items as you and your group see fit. Using the orange post-it notes provided, each cluster should be labelled with a term or phrase which you feel best characterises it.

9.5.1.2.2 Italian

Si è deciso di provare questo sistema pensando a come potrebbe essere usato per facilitare lo svolgimento del modulo di “Gestione dello sviluppo software” La prospettiva è che l'applicazione supporti il browsing e la prenotazione di corsi, ma anche supporti funzionalità richieste da professori e amministratori come tener traccia di informazioni riguardo professori, la scaricamento di materiale, e la sua distribuzione sulle macchine degli studenti ed ai terminali disponibili per gli studenti del corso.

La prima fase di questo esercizio richiederà di pensare ai differenti aspetti dell'applicazione che necessitano di esser controllati. Usando i post-it gialli, per favore elenca i concetti associati con questo sistema e aggiungili alla superficie/lavagna. Sei assolutamente libero di discutere i tuoi concetti con gli altri partecipanti, o di rimuovere concetti duplicati. Puoi anche raggruppare questi concetti nel modo che tu ed i tuoi compagni di gruppo ritenete opportuno. Usa i post-it arancioni per etichettare il gruppo con un termine o una breve frase che descriva cosa caratterizzi il gruppo stesso.

9.5.1.3 Subject clustering

9.5.1.3.1 English

From the initial clustering exercise, it should become clear that different people have a stake in the app for different reasons, ranging from students, lecturers, administrators, assessors, and maybe even proctors. In this part of the exercise, you should begin by noting on the board or flip-chart the people or groups with an interest in the app and the data it has access to. For each of these people or groups, starting with course attendees, you should label the person/group name on a green and red post-it note, add these notes to the white-board, and re-cluster the information according to what these groups should and should not have access to. If you think of new items then you are welcome to add these as the exercise progresses.

9.5.1.3.2 Italian

A seguire dall'esercizio di raggruppamento iniziale, sarà probabilmente emerso come differenti categorie di persone corrano rischi differenti, ad esempio pensando a studenti, insegnanti, personale amministrativo, ed eventualmente anche personale di controllo durante gli esami. In questa parte dell'esercizio, tu dovresti iniziare ad annotare le persone o i gruppi con un interesse nell'applicazione e nei dati cui hanno accesso. Per ciascuno di queste persone o gruppo, a cominciare dagli studenti del corso, dovresti etichettare il nome della persona/gruppo su di un post-it verde e rosso, aggiungendo queste note sulla lavagna/superficie, a procedere ad un nuovo raggruppamento delle informazioni sulla base di come questi gruppi dovrebbero o non

dovrebbero potervi accedere. Se pensi che nuovi concetti debbano essere introdotti, aggiungili pure man mano che l'esercizio procede.

9.5.1.4 Context clustering

9.5.1.4.1 English

Having thought about this policy a great deal, it dawns on you that subtle variations in the context where the app is used might lead you re-think some of the decisions you have already made. For example, if a TA was at home or out and about in Oxford while running the app, would you want him/her to have the capability of installing content on teaching machines. In this part of the exercise, you should write down different contexts where the app might get used. These should be written on the light blue post-it notes provided. If you think of new data items or new people who should or should not be allowed access to data then this can be added as necessary. Like the previous stages, if you think of new data items or new people who should or should not have access to data then these should be added as necessary.

9.5.1.4.2 Italian

A questo punto dell'esercizio, potrebbe esser emerso come variazioni nel contesto d'uso dell'applicazione possano portarti a ripensare alcune delle decisioni prese in precedenza. Per esempio, se un professore fosse a casa o comunque lontano dalla sede dell'università, anziché all'interno dell'università durante l'uso dell'applicazione, potresti volere o meno che all'applicazione sia permesso installare o trasmettere contenuti accessibili dai terminali dell'università.

In questa parte dell'esercizio, dovresti scrivere contesti differenti in cui l'applicazione potrebbe essere usata. Questi dovrebbero essere scritti sui post-it blu. Se tu pensassi che nuovi dati o nuove persone dovrebbero o meno avere accesso a certi dati, aggiungili pure quando richiesto.

9.5.2. Participant match to persona characteristics

Characteristic	Characteristic Type	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3	Participant 4
Focused on mobile and Web development	Activities	Y	Y	Y	Y
Passionate and experienced professional software developer	Activities	Y	Y	Y	Y

Passionate and successful blogger	Activities	N	N	N	N
Knows what he wants and chooses tool chain and architectural design accordingly	Attitudes	Y	Y	Y	Y
Prefers open source	Attitudes	Y	Y	Y	N
Follows a pragmatic hands-on design and implementation approach	Aptitudes	Y	Y	Y	Y
Is self-employed	Aptitudes	N	N	N	N
Knows how to do business with his applications	Aptitudes	Y	N	N	N
Stays up-to-date on various technologies	Aptitudes	Y	Y	Y	Y
Is fond of gadgets which interact on his home network	Motivation	Y	Y	Y	Y
Is comfortable with developing low-level functional details	Skills	Y	Y	Y	Y
Experienced in software security, to some extent	Context & Events Security & Privacy Issues	N	N	N	N
He does not like to be limited by access control while using his computer and while implementing	Context & Events Security & Privacy Issues	Y	Y	Y	Y

software					
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9.6. Jimmy Focus Group 3

9.6.1. Scenario

9.6.1.1 Introductions

The University's web site has long been the front-window for advertising to students, parents, and businesses by allowing them to learn more about the departments, as well as registering for courses and degrees. Based on student and academic needs, the University has decided that they will provide an e-learning system where student information and course information is made available on smart phones. The University web site will be turned into a mobile web app that will bring students, employees, and alumni closer together. The new solution will allow everyone access to the information without being tied to a desktop or laptop computer.

The app could be augmented with the back-end systems for managing student and course information. It would also be possible to integrate with e-learning management systems to facilitate teaching activities as well. It might facilitate discussions and sharing of information in group exercises, as well access to the content across multiple devices. For example, one might be able to use the app to control the installation of course material on other devices, or to make it available for specific persons. Thus, the new web application will not only better streamline the management of students and courses, but will also better facilitate the teaching activities as well.

However, such an app leads to threats as well as opportunities, so it's useful to think about the app's security and privacy implications now before starting any detailed design. To do this, we will develop a model indicating how data in this system should or should not be used, by whom, and in what contexts. This model will take the form of an affinity diagram that will be built up progressively over a number of stages. When complete, this model will be used to design security controls which will allow your users to take advantage of this new system, without being intentionally or unintentionally taken advantage of.

Please remember that this exercise is being built around you and what you would allow, so do think about yourself and not about what others think or rather than what you think others in your group might expect.

9.6.1.2 Object clustering task

It has been decided to pilot this system by thinking about how it might be used to support the delivery of the Advanced Programming course module. The vision will be that the app will support the browsing and booking of courses, but will also support facilities required by lecturers and administrators such as recording information about course delegates, the upload of courseware, and its distribution to machines in the course teaching room.

The first part of this exercise will involve thinking about different aspect of the app that needs to be controlled. Using the yellow post-it note pads, please list concepts associated with this system and add them to the whiteboard. Please feel to discuss your concepts with your colleagues, or remove any duplicated concepts. You should also cluster these items as you and your group see fit. Using the orange post-it notes provided, each cluster should be labelled with a term or phrase which you feel best characterises it.

9.6.1.3 Subject clustering task

From the initial clustering exercise, it should become clear that different people have a stake in the app for different reasons, ranging from students, lecturers, administrators, assessors, and may be even others. In this part of the exercise, you should begin by noting on the board or flip-chart the people or groups with an interest in the app and the data it has access to. For each of these people or groups, starting with course attendees, you should label the person/group name on a green and red post-it note, add these notes to the white-board, and re-cluster the information according to what these groups should and should not have access to. If you think of new items, then you are welcome to add these as the exercise progresses.

9.6.1.4 Context clustering task

Having thought about this privacy policy a great deal, it dawns on you that a small change in context might lead you to re-think some of the decisions that you have already made. For example, if a lecturer was at home or out and about in the city while running the app, would you want her to have the capability of installing content on teaching machines.

In this part of the exercise, you should write down different contexts where the app might get used. These should be written on the light blue post-it notes provided. If you think of new data items or new people who should or should not be allowed access to data then this can be added as necessary. Like the previous stages, if you think of new data items or new people who should or should not have access to data then these should be added as necessary.

9.6.2. Participant match to persona characteristics

Characteristic	Characteristic Type	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3
Focused on mobile and web development	Activities	?	?	?
Passionate and experienced professional software developer	Activities	?	?	?
Passionate and successful blogger	Activities	?	?	?
Knows what he wants and chooses tool-chain and architectural design accordingly	Attitudes	?	?	?
Prefers open source	Attitudes	?	?	?
Follows a pragmatic hands-on design and implementation approach	Aptitudes	?	?	?
Is self-employed	Aptitudes	?	?	?
Knows how to do business with his applications	Aptitudes	?	?	?
Stays up-to-date on various technologies	Aptitudes	?	?	?
Is fond of gadgets which interact on his home network	Motivations	?	?	?
Is comfortable with developing low-level functional details	Skills	?	?	?

9.7. Clara Focus Group 1

9.7.1. Scenario

The scenario is the same proposed by Oxford for the Jimmy persona, but is discussed from the perspective of the Clara persona.

9.7.1.1 Introductions

9.7.1.1.1 English

Oxford's Software Engineering site has long been the front-shop for advertising the programme by allowing both current and prospective students to learn more about the programme, as well as registering for courses and degrees. As more and more people are moving to smart phones, it seems sensible to think turning about the Software Engineering site into a mobile web app which will allow them to do this without being tied to a desktop PC or laptop. Such an app would not only be better augmented with the back-end systems for managing student and course information, but also lead to possibilities for integrating learning management systems to facilitate teaching activities as well. With the aid of webinos, the possibilities become even greater as overlay networks might facilitate discussions and sharing of information in group exercises, as well as the ability for content to be seamless customised based on the most appropriate platform. For example, TAs might be able to use the app to control the installation of course specific material from any device which can run the webinos runtime.

However, such an app leads to threats as well as opportunities, so it's useful to think about the app's security and privacy implications now before the application run. To do this, we will develop a model indicating how data in this system should or should not be used, by whom, and in what contexts. This model will take the form an affinity diagram that will be built up progressively over a number of stages. When complete, this model will be used to design security controls which will allow students to take advantage of this new system, without being taken intentionally or unintentionally taken advantage of.

Please remember that this exercise is being built around you and what you would allow, so do think about yourself and not about what others think or rather than what you think others in your group might expect.

9.7.1.1.2 Italian

Il sito web del gruppo di ingegneria del software di Oxford da lungo tempo permette allo studente di interagire ed avere informazioni sul programma dei vari corsi correlati, come anche di registrarsi ai corsi ed agli esami. Grazie alla diffusione sempre più massiccia di smart-phone, viene pianificato di arricchire il sito, trasformandolo anche in una applicazione web per mobile, che permetta agli studenti di interagire senza aver bisogno di un desktop o di un laptop. Questa applicazione potrebbe non solo esser migliorata con un back-end per gestire informazioni inerenti gli studenti e i corsi, ma anche permettere l'integrazione di sistemi di e-learning per facilitare l'attivazione e fruizione di corsi a distanza. Con l'ausilio di webinos, le possibilità aumentano ulteriormente in quanto l'infrastruttura di webinos potrebbe facilitare discussioni e condivisione di informazioni in gruppi di studio, così come permettere l'adattamento del

contenuto in base alla piattaforma di fruizione (smart-phone, PC, Home TV, ...), in modo trasparente. Per esempio, un professore potrebbe usare l'applicazione per condividere materiale specifico per il proprio corso da qualsiasi device “webinos enabled”.

Una simile applicazione porta non solo opportunità, ma anche possibili minacce. Diventa così importante pensare alle implicazioni di sicurezza e privacy, prima di progettare e mettere in funzione l'applicazione. Per far questo, svilupperemo un modello per indicare come i dati debbano o non debbano essere usati, da chi, ed in quale contesto. Questo modello prenderà la forma di un “affinity diagram” che verrà costruito in alcuni passi successivi. Una volta completo, questo modello sarà usato per progettare i controlli di sicurezza che permetteranno agli utenti legittimi del sistema di trarne beneficio, senza divenirne vittima (ad opera di comportamento errato sia intenzionale sia involontario).

Ricorda che questo esercizio viene svolto da te sulla base delle cose che tu permetteresti o no, quindi esprimi le tue opinioni, e non cosa gli altri partecipanti si aspettano (o tu pensi si aspettino) riguardo i concetti da elaborare.

9.7.1.2 *Object clustering*

9.7.1.2.1 English

It has been decided to pilot this system by thinking about how it might be used to support the delivery of the Software Development Management course module. The vision will be that the app will support the browsing and booking of courses, but will also support facilities required by lecturers and administrators such as recording information about course delegates, the upload of courseware, and its distribution to machines in the course teaching room.

The first part of this exercise will involve thinking about different aspects of the app which need to be controlled. Using the yellow post-it note pads, please list concepts associated with this system and add them to the whiteboard. Please feel to discuss your concepts with your colleagues, or remove any duplicated concepts. You should also cluster these items as you and your group see fit. Using the orange post-it notes provided, each cluster should be labeled with a term or short phrase which you feel best characterises it.

9.7.1.2.2 Italian

Si è deciso di provare questo sistema pensando a come potrebbe essere usato per facilitare lo svolgimento del modulo di “Gestione dello sviluppo software” La prospettiva è che l'applicazione supporti il browsing e la prenotazione di corsi, ma anche supporti funzionalità richieste da professori e amministratori come tener traccia di informazioni riguardo professori, la scaricamento di materiale, e la sua distribuzione sulle macchine degli studenti ed ai terminali disponibili per gli studenti del corso.

La prima fase di questo esercizio richiederà di pensare ai differenti aspetti dell'applicazione che

necessitano di esser controllati. Usando i post-it gialli, per favore elenca i concetti associati con questo sistema e aggiungili alla superficie/lavagna. Sei assolutamente libero di discutere i tuoi concetti con gli altri partecipanti, o di rimuovere concetti duplicati. Puoi anche raggruppare questi concetti nel modo che tu ed i tuoi compagni di gruppo ritenete opportuno. Usa i post-it arancioni per etichettare il gruppo con un termine o una breve frase che descriva cosa caratterizzi il gruppo stesso.

9.7.1.3 Subject clustering

9.7.1.3.1 English

From the initial clustering exercise, it should become clear that different people have a stake in the app for different reasons, ranging from students, lecturers, administrators, assessors, and maybe even proctors. In this part of the exercise, you should begin by noting on the board or flip-chart the people or groups with an interest in the app and the data it has access to. For each of these people or groups, starting with course attendees, you should label the person/group name on a green and red post-it note, add these notes to the white-board, and re-cluster the information according to what these groups should and should not have access to. If you think of new items then you are welcome to add these as the exercise progresses.

9.7.1.3.2 Italian

A seguire dall'esercizio di raggruppamento iniziale, sarà probabilmente emerso come differenti categorie di persone corrano rischi differenti, ad esempio pensando a studenti, insegnanti, personale amministrativo, ed eventualmente anche personale di controllo durante gli esami. In questa parte dell'esercizio, tu dovresti iniziare ad annotare le persone o i gruppi con un interesse nell'applicazione e nei dati cui hanno accesso. Per ciascuno di queste persone o gruppo, a cominciare dagli studenti del corso, dovresti etichettare il nome della persona/gruppo su di un post-it verde e rosso, aggiungendo queste note sulla lavagna/superficie, e procedere ad un nuovo raggruppamento delle informazioni sulla base di come questi gruppi dovrebbero o non dovrebbero potervi accedere. Se pensi che nuovi concetti debbano essere introdotti, aggiungili pure man mano che l'esercizio procede.

9.7.1.4 Context clustering

9.7.1.4.1 English

Having thought about this policy a great deal, it dawns on you that subtle variations in the context where the app is used might lead you re-think some of the decisions you have already made. For example, if a TA was at home or out and about in Oxford while running the app,

would you want him/her to have the capability of installing content on teaching machines. In this part of the exercise, you should write down different contexts where the app might get used. These should be written on the light blue post-it notes provided. If you think of new data items or new people who should or should not be allowed access to data then this can be added as necessary. Like the previous stages, if you think of new data items or new people who should or should not have access to data then these should be added as necessary.

9.7.1.4.2 Italian

A questo punto dell'esercizio, potrebbe esser emerso come variazioni nel contesto d'uso dell'applicazione possano portarti a ripensare alcune delle decisioni prese in precedenza. Per esempio, se un professore fosse a casa o comunque lontano dalla sede dell'università, anziché all'interno dell'università durante l'uso dell'applicazione, potresti volere o meno che all'applicazione sia permesso installare o trasmettere contenuti accessibili dai terminali dell'università.

In questa parte dell'esercizio, dovresti scrivere contesti differenti in cui l'applicazione potrebbe essere usata. Questi dovrebbero essere scritti sui post-it blu. Se tu pensassi che nuovi dati o nuove persone dovrebbero o meno avere accesso a certi dati, aggiungili pure quando richiesto.

9.7.2. Participant match to persona characteristics

Characteristic	Characteristic Type	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3	Participant 4
Is a teenager	Activities	N (20 years old)	N (20)	N (20)	N (20)
Lives with her family	Activities	Y	Y	Y	Y
Manages her data with cloud services	Activities	Y	Y	Y	Y
Manages her diabetes by herself	Activities	N (does not have diabetes)			
Uses modern technology	Activities	Y	Y	Y	Y
Is careless with her disease but is	Attitudes	Not	Not	Not	Not

basically willing to manage it		applicable	applicable	applicable	applicable
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9.8. Clara Focus Group 2

9.8.1. Scenario

9.8.1.1 Introductions

9.8.1.1.1 English

Imagine following scenario. You bought a brand new home entertainment system with features like video on demand, user centric video playback and mobile device support. The system has a high speed internet access to video portals like Hulu, Netflix, Apple iTunes and further 3rd party content providers. TV, Desktop, Smartphones and Tablets are commonly connected to the system via WLAN. The innovative aspect initially lies in the multi-level shared content access providing personalized content streams for video, audio and games. These content streams can be accessed online in the whole house through your personal device like TV set in your child's room. Rather you can switch seamless from TV set to Smartphone if you like to see your popular TV show in the bathroom. All content will be streamed real time from the home entertainment system library. Regarding the user centric video playback feature, you can see films in your language of choice and choose another language of choice for the subtitle. Language and subtitles will be translated real time in your preferred language. Therefore, before you and your friends use this system, you need to think about its security and privacy implications.

To do this, we will develop a model indicating how data in this system should or should not be used, by whom, and in what contexts. This model will take the form an affinity diagram that will be built up progressively over a number of stages. When complete, this model will be used to design security controls which will allow your friends to take advantage of this new system, without being taken intentionally or unintentionally taken advantage of.

Please remember that this exercise is being built around you and what you would allow, so do think about yourself and not about what others think or rather than what you think others in your group might expect.

9.8.1.1.2 German

Stellen Sie sich folgendes Szenario vor. Sie kaufen ein nagelneues Home-Entertainment-System mit Funktionen wie Video on Demand, Videowiedergabe und Unterstützung für mobile Geräte. Das System verfügt über einen High Speed Internet Zugang zu Video-Portalen wie Hulu, Netflix, Apple iTunes und weitere 3rd party Content Anbietern. TV, Desktop, Smartphones und Tablets werden in der Regel zu dem System via WLAN verbunden. Der innovative Aspekt liegt in der

Bereitstellung personalisierter Streams für Video, Audio und Spiele. Diese Streams können online in das ganze Haus über Ihr persönliches Gerät wie Fernseher im Zimmer Ihres Kindes abgerufen werden. Vielmehr können Sie nahtlos vom TV-Gerät auf das Smartphone wechseln, wenn Sie Ihre beliebten TV-Show im Badezimmer sehen möchten. Alle Inhalte werden in Echtzeit aus der Home-Entertainment-System-Library gestreamt. In Bezug auf den Benutzer zentrierten Video-Wiedergabe-Funktion können Sie Filme in der Sprache Ihrer Wahl sehen, und können eine andere Sprache die Untertitel wählen. Sprache und Untertitel werden in Echtzeit in Ihrer bevorzugten Sprache übersetzt. Bevor Sie und Ihre Freunde dieses System verwenden, müssen Sie sich um seine Sicherheit und Auswirkungen auf den Datenschutz Gedanken machen. Um dies zu tun, werden wir ein Modell entwickeln, welches angibt, wie Daten in diesem System verwendet oder nicht verwendet werden sollen, von wem und in welchen Kontexten. Dieses Modell wird in Form eines Affinitäten Diagramms entwickelt. Wenn Sie fertig sind, wird dieses Modell verwendet, um Sicherheitskontrollen, die es Ihren Freunden, um die Vorteile dieses neuen Systems übernehmen, ohne dass absichtlich oder unabsichtlich getroffen Anspruch genommen wird aufgebaut sein.

9.8.1.2 Object Clustering

9.8.1.2.1 English

Your parents are on vacation and you will enjoy the evening with your friends, thus you've invited your friends to a movie night. You and your friends are sitting together at home. You want to watch a movie which comes with extra audio and subtitle streams for different languages by using a user centric video playback system. The movie has also a special stream for hearing impaired users where the environmental noise is reduced in order to make the actors speech clearer.

That the movie has these different audio streams is a huge advantage for you and your friends. Bob is not that good in understanding German and prefers movies in the original language anyway. Charlie is hearing impaired. Bob and Charlie can use their mobile phones as private audio source. The TV set streams the needed audio streams to the mobile terminals where headphones can be used to hear the sound.

The first part of this exercise will involve thinking about different aspect of the system which need to be controlled. Using the yellow post-it note pads, please list concepts associated with this system and add them to the whiteboard. Please feel to discuss your concepts with your colleagues, or remove any duplicated concepts. You should also cluster these items as you and your group see fit. Using the orange post-it notes provided, each cluster should be labelled with a term or phrase which you feel best characterises it.

9.8.1.2.2 German

Ihre Eltern sind im Urlaub und Sie genießen den Abend mit Ihren Freunden. Sie und Ihre Freunde sitzen zusammen zu Hause. Sie wollen einen Film schauen, der mit zusätzlichen Audio- und Untertitel-Streams für verschiedene Sprachen zur Verfügung steht. Der Film hat auch einen speziellen Stream für hörgeschädigte Benutzer, wo die Lärmbelastung reduziert werden, um die Sprache der Schauspieler klarer zu machen.

Das dieser Film verschiedenen Audio-Streams hat, ist ein enormer Vorteil für Sie und Ihre Freunde. Bob ist nicht so gut im Verständnis der deutschen Sprache und schaut sowieso lieber Filme in der Originalsprache. Charlie ist hörgeschädigt. Bob und Charlie können ihr Handy als private Audio-Quelle nutzen. Das TV-Gerät streamt die benötigten Audio-Streams zu den mobilen Endgeräten, wo Kopfhörer verwendet werden, um den Ton zu hören.

Der erste Teil der Übung wird folgendes beinhalten: Denken Sie über die verschiedenen Aspekte des Systems nach, die kontrolliert werden müssen. Mit den gelben Post-its geben Sie bitte Konzepte an, welche mit diesem System verbunden sind und fügen Sie sie diese an die Pinnwand. Bitte zögern Sie nicht, Ihre Konzepte mit Ihren Kollegen zu diskutieren, und entfernen Sie alle doppelten Konzepte. Sie sollten auch Gruppen dieser Konzepte bilden, die Sie und Ihre Kollegen für richtig halten. Mit den orangenen Post-its werden die Gruppen von Konzepten bezeichnet. Die Gruppe sollte mit einem Begriff oder Satz der Sie sich am besten charakterisiert gekennzeichnet werden.

9.8.1.3 *Subject Clustering*

9.8.1.3.1 English

Once you've seen the movie, you can review these and share them with other friends. This is good way to share your thoughts with the community. Since the film was very exhausting, now you and your friends feel like watching a quiz show. The quiz show provides questions where you can interact real time with other viewers. To choose the right answer you can use your Smartphone. This seems like a good way to connect you to the entire audience of the quiz show for an interactive game experience.

However, thinking about sharing with other people also gets you thinking about who or what else the system might be sharing information with as well.

In this part of the exercise, you should begin by noting on the board or flipchart the people or groups with an interest in the entertainment system and the data it has access to. For each of these people or groups, and starting with your friends, you should label the person/group name on a green and red post-it note, add these notes to the white-board, and re-cluster the information according to what these groups should and should not have access to. If you think of new items then you are welcome to add these as the exercise progresses.

9.8.1.3.2 German

Sobald Sie den Film gesehen haben, können Sie diesen bewerten und mit anderen Freunden teilen. Das ist eine gute Möglichkeit, Ihre Gedanken mit der Community zu teilen. Da der Film sehr anstrengend war, würden Sie und Ihre Freunde gerne an einer Quiz-Show teilnehmen. Die Quiz-Show stellt Fragen, wo man in Echtzeit mit anderen Zuschauern interagieren können. So wählen Sie die richtige Antwort mittels Ihres Smartphones. Dies scheint ein guter Weg, um Sie mit dem gesamten Publikum der Quiz-Show zu verbinden für ein besseres Spielerlebnis. Sie sollten darüber nachdenken, wer oder was sonst mit dem System Informationen austauschen könnte.

In diesem Teil der Übung sollten Sie mit dem Brainstorming auf dem Flipchart beginnen, welche Personen Zugriff oder keinen Zugriff auf das System haben. Für jede dieser Personen oder Gruppen sollten Sie die Person / Gruppe auf einem grünen und roten Post-it schreiben. Fügen Sie diese dem White-Board hinzu und re-gruppieren Sie die Informationen nach dem, was Zugriff bzw. keinen Zugriff haben soll. Wenn Sie über neue Konzepte nachdenken, dann sollten diese hinzugefügt werden.

9.8.1.4 Context Clustering

9.8.1.4.1 English

Thinking about another context in which the home entertainment system can be used. For example children should have limited access to movies which are restricted to a certain age limit because they contain youth endangering content. Try to play with different roles of parents and childrens by using the home entertainment system might lead you to re-think some of the decisions you have already made. In this part of the exercise, you should write down different contexts where the home entertainment system might get used. These should be written on the light blue post-it notes provided. If you think of new data items or new people who should or should not be allowed access to data then this can be added as necessary. Like the previous stages, if you think of new data items or new people who should or should not have access to data then these should be added as necessary.

9.8.1.4.2 German

Denken Sie über einen anderen Kontext nach, in dem das Home-Entertainment-System verwendet werden kann. Zum Beispiel sollten Kinder nur begrenzten Zugriff auf Filme haben, da diese altersbeschränkt sind, weil sie jugendgefährdende Inhalte enthalten. Versuchen Sie, mit unterschiedlichen Rollen von Eltern und Kindern zu experimentieren. In diesem Teil der Übung sollten Sie notieren, welche unterschiedlichen Kontexte es gibt, in denen das Home-Entertainment-System genutzt werden kann. Diese sollte auf den hellblauen Post-its

geschrieben werden. Wenn Sie neuen Daten oder neue Personen identifizieren, welche Zugriff / keinen Zugriff auf die Daten haben, dann sollten diese bei Bedarf hinzugefügt werden.

9.8.2. Participant match to persona characteristics

Characteristic	Characteristic Type	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3	Participant 4
Is a teenager	Activities	N (22 years old)	N (21)	N (20)	N (23)
Lives with her family	Activities	N	N	N	N
Manages her data with cloud services	Activities	Y	Y	Y	Y
Manages her diabetes by herself	Activities	N (does not have diabetes)			
Uses modern technology	Activities	Y	Y	Y	Y
Is careless with her disease but is basically willing to manage it	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable

9.9. Clara Focus Group 3

9.9.1. Scenario

The scenario is the same proposed by Oxford for the Jimmy persona, but is discussed from the perspective of the Clara persona.

9.9.1.1 Introductions

9.9.1.1.1 English

Oxford's Software Engineering site has long been the front-shop for advertising the programme by allowing both current and prospective students to learn more about the programme, as well

as registering for courses and degrees. As more and more people are moving to smart phones, it seems sensible to think turning about the Software Engineering site into a mobile web app which will allow them to do this without being tied to a desktop PC or laptop. Such an app would not only be better augmented with the back-end systems for managing student and course information, but also lead to possibilities for integrating learning management systems to facilitate teaching activities as well. With the aid of webinos, the possibilities become even greater as overlay networks might facilitate discussions and sharing of information in group exercises, as well as the ability for content to be seamless customised based on the most appropriate platform. For example, TAs might be able to use the app to control the installation of course specific material from any device which can run the webinos runtime.

However, such an app leads to threats as well as opportunities, so it's useful to think about the app's security and privacy implications now before the application run. To do this, we will develop a model indicating how data in this system should or should not be used, by whom, and in what contexts. This model will take the form an affinity diagram that will be built up progressively over a number of stages. When complete, this model will be used to design security controls which will allow students to take advantage of this new system, without being taken intentionally or unintentionally taken advantage of.

Please remember that this exercise is being built around you and what you would allow, so do think about yourself and not about what others think or rather than what you think others in your group might expect.

9.9.1.1.2 Italian

Il sito web del gruppo di ingegneria del software di Oxford da lungo tempo permette allo studente di interagire ed avere informazioni sul programma dei vari corsi correlati, come anche di registrarsi ai corsi ed agli esami. Grazie alla diffusione sempre più massiccia di smart-phone, viene pianificato di arricchire il sito, trasformandolo anche in una applicazione web per mobile, che permetta agli studenti di interagire senza aver bisogno di un desktop o di un laptop. Questa applicazione potrebbe non solo esser migliorata con un back-end per gestire informazioni inerenti gli studenti e i corsi, ma anche permettere l'integrazione di sistemi di e-learning per facilitare l'attivazione e fruizione di corsi a distanza. Con l'ausilio di webinos, le possibilità aumentano ulteriormente in quanto l'infrastruttura di webinos potrebbe facilitare discussioni e condivisione di informazioni in gruppi di studio, così come permettere l'adattamento del contenuto in base alla piattaforma di fruizione (smart-phone, PC, Home TV, ...), in modo trasparente. Per esempio, un professore potrebbe usare l'applicazione per condividere materiale specifico per il proprio corso da qualsiasi device "webinos enabled".

Una simile applicazione porta non solo opportunità, ma anche possibili minacce. Diventa così importante pensare alle implicazioni di sicurezza e privacy, prima di progettare e mettere in funzione l'applicazione. Per far questo, svilupperemo un modello per indicare come i dati

debbano o non debbano essere usati, da chi, ed in quale contesto. Questo modello prenderà la forma di un “affinity diagram” che verrà costruito in alcuni passi successivi. Una volta completo, questo modello sarà usato per progettare i controlli di sicurezza che permetteranno agli utenti legittimi del sistema di trarne beneficio, senza divenirne vittima (ad opera di comportamento errato sia intenzionale sia involontario).

Ricorda che questo esercizio viene svolto da te sulla base delle cose che tu permetteresti o no, quindi esprimi le tue opinioni, e non cosa gli altri partecipanti si aspettano (o tu pensi si aspettino) riguardo i concetti da elaborare.

9.9.1.2 *Object clustering*

9.9.1.2.1 English

It has been decided to pilot this system by thinking about how it might be used to support the delivery of the Software Development Management course module. The vision will be that the app will support the browsing and booking of courses, but will also support facilities required by lecturers and administrators such as recording information about course delegates, the upload of courseware, and its distribution to machines in the course teaching room.

The first part of this exercise will involve thinking about different aspects of the app which need to be controlled. Using the yellow post-it note pads, please list concepts associated with this system and add them to the whiteboard. Please feel to discuss your concepts with your colleagues, or remove any duplicated concepts. You should also cluster these items as you and your group see fit. Using the orange post-it notes provided, each cluster should be labeled with a term or short phrase which you feel best characterises it.

9.9.1.2.2 Italian

Si è deciso di provare questo sistema pensando a come potrebbe essere usato per facilitare lo svolgimento del modulo di “Gestione dello sviluppo software” La prospettiva è che l'applicazione supporti il browsing e la prenotazione di corsi, ma anche supporti funzionalità richieste da professori e amministratori come tener traccia di informazioni riguardo professori, la scaricamento di materiale, e la sua distribuzione sulle macchine degli studenti ed ai terminali disponibili per gli studenti del corso.

La prima fase di questo esercizio richiederà di pensare ai differenti aspetti dell'applicazione che necessitano di esser controllati. Usando i post-it gialli, per favore elenca i concetti associati con questo sistema e aggiungili alla superficie/lavagna. Sei assolutamente libero di discutere i tuoi concetti con gli altri partecipanti, o di rimuovere concetti duplicati. Puoi anche raggruppare questi concetti nel modo che tu ed i tuoi compagni di gruppo ritenete opportuno. Usa i post-it arancioni per etichettare il gruppo con un termine o una breve frase che descriva cosa caratterizzi il gruppo stesso.

9.9.1.3 Subject clustering

9.9.1.3.1 English

From the initial clustering exercise, it should become clear that different people have a stake in the app for different reasons, ranging from students, lecturers, administrators, assessors, and maybe even proctors. In this part of the exercise, you should begin by noting on the board or flip-chart the people or groups with an interest in the app and the data it has access to. For each of these people or groups, starting with course attendees, you should label the person/group name on a green and red post-it note, add these notes to the white-board, and re-cluster the information according to what these groups should and should not have access to. If you think of new items then you are welcome to add these as the exercise progresses.

9.9.1.3.2 Italian

A seguire dall'esercizio di raggruppamento iniziale, sarà probabilmente emerso come differenti categorie di persone corrono rischi differenti, ad esempio pensando a studenti, insegnanti, personale amministrativo, ed eventualmente anche personale di controllo durante gli esami. In questa parte dell'esercizio, tu dovresti iniziare ad annotare le persone o i gruppi con un interesse nell'applicazione e nei dati cui hanno accesso. Per ciascuno di queste persone o gruppo, a cominciare dagli studenti del corso, dovresti etichettare il nome della persona/gruppo su di un post-it verde e rosso, aggiungendo queste note sulla lavagna/superficie, e procedere ad un nuovo raggruppamento delle informazioni sulla base di come questi gruppi dovrebbero o non dovrebbero potervi accedere. Se pensi che nuovi concetti debbano essere introdotti, aggiungili pure man mano che l'esercizio procede.

9.9.1.4 Context clustering

9.9.1.4.1 English

Having thought about this policy a great deal, it dawns on you that subtle variations in the context where the app is used might lead you re-think some of the decisions you have already made. For example, if a TA was at home or out and about in Oxford while running the app, would you want him/her to have the capability of installing content on teaching machines. In this part of the exercise, you should write down different contexts where the app might get used. These should be written on the light blue post-it notes provided. If you think of new data items or new people who should or should not be allowed access to data then this can be added as necessary. Like the previous stages, if you think of new data items or new people who should or should not have access to data then these should be added as necessary.

9.9.1.4.2 Italian

A questo punto dell'esercizio, potrebbe esser emerso come variazioni nel contesto d'uso dell'applicazione possano portarti a ripensare alcune delle decisioni prese in precedenza. Per esempio, se un professore fosse a casa o comunque lontano dalla sede dell'università, anziché all'interno dell'università durante l'uso dell'applicazione, potresti volere o meno che all'applicazione sia permesso installare o trasmettere contenuti accessibili dai terminali dell'università.

In questa parte dell'esercizio, dovresti scrivere contesti differenti in cui l'applicazione potrebbe essere usata. Questi dovrebbero essere scritti sui post-it blu. Se tu pensassi che nuovi dati o nuove persone dovrebbero o meno avere accesso a certi dati, aggiungili pure quando richiesto.

9.9.2. Participant match to persona characteristics

Characteristic	Characteristic Type	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3	Participant 4
Is a teenager	Activities	N (21 years old)	N (23)	N (20)	N (22)
Lives with her family	Activities	Y	Y	Y	Y
Manages her data with cloud services	Activities	N	N	N	N
Manages her diabetes by herself	Activities	N (does not have diabetes)			
Uses modern technology	Activities	Y	Y	Y	Y
Is careless with her disease but is basically willing to manage it	Attitudes	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable

10 Appendix 3: Concept References

10.1. Acknowledge target device

- Source: Installation and update of webinos applications use case

4. The User is asked whether the Application should be made available to all his Devices.

5. The User selects "yes" and installs the Application to his devices.

10.2. APIs throw errors when access control request denied

- Source: Requirement PS-USR-Oxford-36

APIs throw errors when access control request denied

10.3. Applications are up-to-date before execution

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification

.... or execute the application if already installed and up to date.

10.4. Applications contain nested applications

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification

... allows to package a number of sub-applications.

10.5. Applications installed in one go

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification

... packaged in a way to allow a single download and installation on a user's machine or mobile device.

10.6. Application instances spread across devices

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification

Deploy parts or whole application on each device needed / supported by the application.

10.7. Application launched via events

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification

Applications should be able to be automatically launched if certain events occurring.

10.8. Applications may ignore policy changes

- Source: Requirement PS-DEV-Oxford-56

.... and may alter their behaviour as a result.

10.9. Autostart programmatically controlled

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification

.... via application interface API this value could be set dynamically.

10.10. Buys a pink car

- Source: Converging applications within and across devices Story

Wow, his new pink metallic car with beige leather seats, is indeed his favourite pet by now

10.11. Child and parent apps available programmatically

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification

For both application parts, parent and child applications, an application context API is provided as extension to the API defined in [WidgetAPI].....Using this API application references to child and parent applications to allow communication between application parts by providing addressing information for the notification and eventing system.....

10.12. Consciously sets privacy settings

- Source: User Story Manageable privacy policies across the application lifecycle User Story

Jane gets home and decides to make sure her personal information is suitably protected by editing the privacy policy. She uses webinos to restrict which applications may have access to her name, online identity, current location and device information.

10.13. Copy protection stops webinos supported sharing

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification

...state this it is not allowed to copy/export/install the application on another device using webinos application sharing/advertisement features.

10.14. Daemonic applications

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification
- webinos applications can be in a no UI / invisible mode.

10.15. Early adopter of technology

- Source: Converging applications within and across devices Story

He is a keen user of new mobile applications....The tablet is like a wizard with lots of dazzling multi-media and in-depth information about each product. Once he finds his choice, he can check it and the system adds it to the customisation list.

10.16. Editors support fine and coarse grained policy editing.

- Source: Requirement PS-USR-Oxford-113

There shall be a method for users to view and edit policies at both a fine-grained level and separated for coarse, quick-to-use actions.

10.17. Has a second privacy policy for not being observable

- Source: User Story Manageable privacy policies across the application lifecycle User Story

She configures a new policy in webinos that will not keep records of what she is doing and where she is going, and will keep her devices hidden from nearby networks. She can switch to this policy very easily, and does so whenever she feels she would like greater unobservability.

10.18. Installs a third-party application

- Source: Converging applications within and across devices Story

he is offered a museum guide for mobile with free connection to the wireless network. He accepts and installs the application.

10.19. Interested in promotions and special deals of her preferred shops

- Source: User Story Manageable privacy policies across the application lifecycle User Story

When outside work, she enjoys shopping and is interested in hearing about promotions and deals at her favourite shops and on her hobby: fishing.

Jane has an excellent meal, and agrees to be notified when she is next in town (or searching for somewhere to eat) of any promotions that this restaurant is offering.

10.20. Keeps work and personal life separate in her online identities

- Source: User Story Manageable privacy policies across the application lifecycle User Story

he has many online identities, but likes to keep her work and personal life separate.

When using her mobile phone for work she switches to her Linked In identity, and during the weekends she moves to her Facebook-provided identity.

Jane thinks that this sounds fantastic, and agrees to share her allergy information, stored on her mobile. However, she also specifies that this information should not be shared with any other applications.

She makes sure that this is done from her personal online identity, as she does not want her company to be seen to be endorsing this restaurant.

Jane gets home and decides to make sure her personal information is suitable protected by editing the privacy policy. She uses webinos to restrict which applications may have access to her name, online identity, current location and device information.

10.21.No distributed application patterns

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification

... where the developer thinks that it makes sense to create specific application modules for certain tasks.....

.... actual signature of the functions as well as the function names of the exposed functions must be known by the developer....

10.22.Policies contain fine-grained rules.

- Source: Requirement PS-USR-Oxford-35

Webinos access control policies shall be able to specify fine-grained controls involving the source and content of an access control request.

10.23.Policy decision maker at the e-book store

- Source: User Story Manageable privacy policies across the application lifecycle User Story

Aaron works at Zamanon a company selling e-books through a webinos e-book application. He has been asked to write several policies governing the e-books and the application itself.

10.24.Policy impact is described textually

- Source: Requirement PS-DEV-Oxford-78

The webinos policy editing tool shall support the creation of example textual descriptions of how a particular change to a policy will affect the way the system will behave.

10.25.Proprietary extensions used

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification

In addition to the XML elements defined in [Widgets] webinos applications are allowed to make use of some proprietary extensions.

10.26.Shares personal data with BMW

- Source: Converging applications within and across devices Story

The adviser asks Peter to touch his phone onto a tablet with a larger screen. Peter does so and his name, contacts, and appointment appears automatically on the bigger tablet screen.

10.27.Simplified communication between sub-applications

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification

... in order to simplify application schemes between parent and child applications.

10.28.Sophisticated policy editing tools.

- Source: Requirement PS-DEV-Oxford-77

The webinos policy editing tool shall allow policy specification based on assets including data, data classes, signing authorities and APIs.

10.29.User alerted on policy warning

- Source: Requirement PS-USR-Oxford-75

The webinos runtime shall be able to alert the user at runtime.

10.30.Uses and contributes to online social networks

- Source: Converging applications within and across devices Story

Peter decides to buy the product with the best [online] review....He selects Recommend in the application and the recommendation is published to his friends.....Peter therefore adds a recommendation entry for the restaurant in the restaurant guide whilst eating dinner that becomes instantly visible for other people using the guide.

10.31.Uses mobile phone for complex tasks

- Source: Converging applications within and across devices Story

Some of his mobile applications are woven together and interplay already.....Peter pays by waving his mobile and the chosen product on the shop counter.....the calendar on his phone reminds his about his appointment for BMW car customisation.....He has planned for next day to walk to the BMW museum with the help of the mobile navigation software on his phone.....A confirmation of order automatically appears in his inbox on the mobile. It tells him where he can pick up the car keys tomorrow at 12:30.....He is told to pair the electronic car key with his mobile and he willingly does so.....Peter says as he holds up his mobile towards the customer consultant to clearly signal that he wants to pay.

10.32.Uses mobile phone to organise life

- Source: Converging applications within and across devices Story

...the calendar on his phone reminds his about his appointment for BMW car customisation.... A confirmation of order automatically appears in his inbox on the mobile. It tells him where he can pick up the car keys tomorrow at 12:30.

10.33.Webinos explains policy setting refusals

- Source: Requirement PS-USR-Oxford-58

If users are prevented from modifying some policy settings, webinos shall present users with an explanation of why modifications are denied.

10.34.Widget specification extensible

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification

The following specification for distributed webinos applications will add some further more complex extensions to the Widget application interface as well as to the Widget packaging and configuration specification.

10.35.Writes ZenSearch Application

- Source: Creating Applications for webinos Story

He [...] ports his latest iPhone app ZenSearch to webinos. That application searches the web for photos (in the public domain or with a certain CC licence) which are usable in Zen-style presentations.

10.36. Application consists of front-end and back-end part

- Source: Creating Applications for webinos Story

It consists of a back-end and a front-end. The back-end is a server that does the searching and 'scoring' of the photos. The front-end is the aforementioned iPhone app with its excellent navigational interface.

10.37. Ports this application to webinos

- Source: Creating Applications for webinos Story

For the porting effort the server, of course, is fine as it is. The mobile app however needs to be rewritten to HTML + CSS + JavaScript.

10.38. Is interested in new technologies

- Source: Jimmy Assumption Persona

As he is interested in new technologies and new market opportunities he always stays up-to-date in his field.

Jimmy enjoys experimenting with new technology and he adapts quickly.

10.39. Likes interconnecting devices

- Source: Jimmy Assumption Persona

Jimmy is fond of software-controlled gadgets which interact with other devices on his home network.

10.40. Likes trying things out and learns from examples

- Source: Jimmy Assumption Persona

He learns best by just trying out things.

Jimmy follows a pragmatic hands-on design and implementation approach. He is much more into trying out things rather than spending time on theory.

10.41.Likes writing mobile applications

- Source: Jimmy Assumption Persona

He is a self-employed professional software developer for mobile applications.

Jimmy is a passionate and experienced professional software developer. His focus is on mobile applications and Web applications.

10.42.Is a professional software developer

- Source: Jimmy Assumption Persona

He is a self-employed professional software developer for mobile applications.

Jimmy is a passionate and experienced professional software developer.

10.43.Does not pay attention on concepts

- Source: Jimmy Assumption Persona

Jimmy follows a pragmatic hands-on design and implementation approach. He is much more into trying out things rather than spending time on theory.

10.44.Considers security as annoying and restrictive

- Source: Jimmy Assumption Persona

Jimmy is experienced in software security to some extent. [...] On the other hand, he does not like to be limited by access control while using his computer and while implementing software.

10.45.Applications can store context data

- Source: Requirement ID-USR-Oxford-36

Applications shall be able to create context structures with addressable identities. Context structures refer to data structures containing context data.

10.46.Context data is stored in the user's Personal Zone

- Source: webinos Application and Runtime Specification

... so it can remain private.

10.47.Context data can be shared

- Source: Requirement PS-DEV-ambiesense-15
- Source: Requirement TMS-DEV-SEMC-018

It must be possible to define context information as public, shared, or private.

The webinos system shall support the possibility to share and edit data objects for online collaborative applications in a responsive manner.

10.48.Webinos Runtime can set dynamic access control policies for data sharing

- Source: Requirement PS-USR-Oxford-17

The webinos Runtime Environment shall be capable of setting dynamic access control policies for device data when initiating an association to another webinos Device.

11 Appendix 4: Concept Reference Sources

11.1. Converging applications within and across devices Story

- Author/s: Hans Myrhaug, Ayse Goker, Anders Isberg
- Date: November 2010

11.2. Installation and update of webinos applications use case

- Author/s: Katrin Jordan
- Date: January 2011

11.3. webinos Application and Runtime Specification: 41

- Author/s: Andre Paul
- Date: April 2011

11.4. Creating Applications for webinos Story

- Author/s: Victor Klos
- Date: January 2011